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A **D**ecision-**A**nalytic Framework to explore the water-energy-food **N**exus in complex and transboundary water resources systems of fast growing developing countries

MODELS OF THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN THE ZAMBEZI RIVER BASIN

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Abbreviations

AfDB:	African Development Bank
CIA:	Central Intelligence Agency
COMESA:	Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa
D:	Downstream
DAFNE:	Decision-Analytic-Framework to explore the water-energy-foodNexus in complex and trans-boundary water resources systems of fast growing developing countries
EDM:	Electricidade de Moçambique
EPI:	Environmental Performance Index
ES:	Ecosystem Services
EU:	European Union
EWURA:	Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority
FAO:	Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations
FBSDEs:	Forward Backward Stochastic Differential Equations
FTA:	Free Trade Area
GDP:	Gross Domestic Product
GA:	Gross value added
HA:	Hectares
HCB:	Hidroeléctrica de Cahora-Bassa
HJB:	Hamilton-Jacobi-Bellman equation
HDI:	Human Development Index
IAPRI:	Indaba Agricultural Policy Research Institute
ILO:	International LABOUR Organization
INE:	Instituto Nacional de Estatística
IO:	Inputs-Output
IUCN:	International Union for Conservation of Nature
IV:	Instrumental Variable
JMP:	Joint Monitoring Programme
K2O:	Potash
MRIO:	Multi-Region Input-Output Table
MT:	Mozambican Metical (currency)
MW:	Mega Watts
N:	Nitrogen
NB:	Net Benefit
NSO:	National Statistics Office
NVA:	Net Value Added
OECD:	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
OLS:	Ordinary Least Square
P2O5:	Phosphate
PFA:	Production Function Approach
PJTC Kunene:	The Permanent Joint Technical Commission of the Kunene Riv-

er

RE:	Riccati Equation
SADC:	Southern African Development Community
SARDC:	Southern African Research and Documentation Centre
SB:	Social Benefit
SDE:	Stochastic Differential Equation
SE4ALL:	Sustainable Energy for All
TEV:	Total Economic Value
TNBS:	Tanzania National Bureau of Statistic
TC:	Total Cost
U:	Upstream
UNECA:	United Nations Economic Commission for Africa
UNICEF:	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
WB:	World Bank
WDPA:	World Database on Protected Areas
WEF:	Water-Energy-Food
WHO:	World Health Organisation
WP:	Work Package
WTP:	Willingness-To-Pay
WTTC:	World Travel and Tourism Council
ZINWA:	Zimbabwe National Water Authority
ZRB:	Zambezi River Basin

1 INTRODUCTION

This report comprises the research conducted as part of the European Commission project: ‘DAFNE: A Decision-Analytic-Framework to explore the water-energy-food NExus in complex and trans-boundary water resources systems of fast growing developing countries’ (DAFNE Project). The main goal of work package 4 (WP4) is the modelling of economic and social processes and environmental policy under the water-energy-food (WEF) nexus perspective. Specifically, it analyzes the sharing of a natural resource in a transboundary setting under different levels of pressure from factors such as demographic and land use trends, industrial development, institutional adequacy and learning culture for each neighboring country or region within the Zambezi River Basin (ZRB).

The objective of this deliverable (D4.1) is to focus on the production of an economy-wide model which will describe the economic development of the regions or countries of each case study. The shared resource that is under pressure, namely water, has a central role in this model. In order to provide a more accurate representation than usually provided by abstract models, the sectors associated with each country correspond to a production function, adequately adapted to the corresponding characteristics. More specifically, the analysis includes information on the economic characteristics of each country such as total employment, production output of the energy and food sectors, volume of water use, environmental indicators, etc. In particular, the model developed is able to capture the interdependencies between two neighbouring, possibly different, economies sharing the same resource. It supports also the principle of sustainable development, in the sense that sustainable strategies for economic development will be accommodated given the effects of climate change.

More specifically, the economic characterization of water in the DAFNE regions for the ZRB – Angola, Botswana, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, United Republic of Tanzania, Zambia, and Zimbabwe, includes the economic evaluation of water use in the ZRB and evaluation of the economic importance of water use in the area. This procedure required the gathering of socio-economic data, such as income, employment, etc., for all eight countries and is realized for each sector of the economic activity in order to define the sectors that put more pressure on water use. Furthermore, the different water-use patterns of each sector of economic activity (primary, secondary, tertiary and households) has a different water use pattern. In general, water use is prioritized relatively as follows:

- a) Agriculture and Fishing
- b) Residential Water Supply
- c) Mining and Quarrying
- d) Energy sector which includes hydropower production
- e) Tourism.

This report therefore outlines the methodology and approach towards developing the deliverable, before presenting an overview of the economic development of all the ZRB countries, providing a snapshot of the inter-sectoral economic profile of each country. The deliverable goes on to detail the formulation of the model of economic development from the WEF Nexus perspective, taking into consideration the Total Economic Value of water. As multiple countries share water resources, the likelihood of conflicts over distributing water resources increases, particularly under the effects of climate change. The model developed in this deliverable captures the influence of stochastic water resources on transboundary water allocation per each of the above sectors, following a multi-stage dynamic cooperative game theoretic approach. Employing a stochastic Stackelberg differential game, we show how issue linkage can facilitate cooperation between countries, even in the case of climate change. We illustrate the model with the case of inter-sector water sharing between the upstream countries, Angola, Botswana, Namibia, Zambia, and Zimbabwe, and the downstream country, Mozambique. The “*issue linkage to water sharing*” in this case concerns the trade of hydropower exported from the downstream country, Mozambique to the upstream area. More pre-

cisely, we demonstrate how the two areas can cooperate in order to achieve sustainable trans-boundary water sharing under such conditions.

In terms of 'inter' and 'intra' work package interactions; D4.1 is a complementary deliverable to D4.6 (Models of the economic development in the Omo-Turkana basin). It forms part of a suite of socio-economic models, including D4.2, D4.3 and D4.4, all of which form the basis of D4.5 (Integrated framework of models for social, economic and institutional developments). Work carried out within WP2 in the form of data collection under Task 2.1 (in particular Subtask 2.1.7 and 2.1.8), was used as input for the development of this deliverable. Furthermore, elements of this deliverable will support the development of D2.1 (Baseline Scenario). This deliverable will also be integrated with the models being developed within WP3 and ultimately feed into the work within WP5.

1.1 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The deliverable is a product of work activities carried out within Task 4.1 (Models of Development of the Economy), led by the ICRE8 team with contributions from the UNZA and UEM teams. The research carried out towards the development of this deliverable was primarily a desktop study, incorporating data derived from activities within WP2.

Based on extensive literature and archival review, both qualitative and quantitative data was collected from scientific journal publications, official reports, governmental websites, and other forms of grey literature. Quantitative data collected from databases including African development bank, including African development bank, ILO (International LABOUR Organization), the World Bank data, the World Bank Group: Climate Change Knowledge Portal For Development Practitioners and Policy Makers, the United Nations Statistics Division, Unesco World Heritage list, OpenDataSoft, Environment & Climate Change Data Portal, Eora multi-region IO table (MRIO) database, and offices of national statistics.

While the deliverable adopts primarily quantitative methods of analysis, it also incorporates some elements of a qualitative thematic analysis within the literature review. The technique of multistage stochastic Stackelberg differential game theory is employed. This amounts to solving sequentially a series of free end point problems, each of which defines endogenously the date when an economic sector exits the market as its quantity demand of water reaches zero.

The main limitations of the study concern data and assumptions of the model. In terms of limitations relating to data, the primary issue has been data availability and quality, particularly at sub-national and river basin level. Partners have been presented with challenges in terms of accessing data at a local level in cases where the data is non-existent or process of collecting it has proven too resource intensive. As such, the model has been developed using national level data, sourced from international databases for the estimation of the welfare function for each economic sector due to the lack of regional data. As a result, the estimated water demand functions for each sector of the upstream area were identical with those estimated for the downstream one, respectively.

Regarding limitations associated with the model itself, the stochastic differential equation of Geometric Brownian motion has been extensively used to model the dynamic flow of several natural quantities that entail randomness, such as the water volume of precipitation and runoff of a river (Zambezi river) or of outflow from a lake (Cahora Bassa). Additionally, the volume of the annual renewable water resource due to the river basin has been considered as the total precipitation volume over the upstream area.

1.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN THE ZAMBEZI RIVER BASIN

Zambezi is the fourth-longest river in Africa, the longest east-flowing river in Africa and the largest flowing into the Indian Ocean from Africa. The Zambezi mainstem originates in the Kalene Hills in Zambia and flows south and eastwards to the Indian Ocean. The total area of its basin is 1,390,000 square kilometres of which 2,574-kilometre-long river rises in Zambia and flows through eastern Angola, along the eastern border of Namibia and the northern border of Botswana, then along the border between Zambia and Zimbabwe to Mozambique, where it crosses the country to

empty into the Indian Ocean. The river has three distinct reaches: the Upper Zambezi from its source to Victoria Falls, the Middle Zambezi from Victoria Falls to Cahora Bassa Gorge, and the Lower Zambezi from Cahora Bassa to the Zambezi Delta; which are the main focus areas in this project.

With the patterns of socio-economic development in the region greatly influenced by access to water, the Zambezi waters are critical to sustainable economic growth and poverty reduction in the region (Allan, 2002). In order to meet the basic needs of approximately 40 million people and sustain a rich and diverse natural environment, the river plays a central role in the economies of the eight riparian countries mentioned above (ZAMCOM, 2008). Zambezi provides important environmental goods and services to the region and is essential to regional food security and hydropower production. The economies of the riparian states of the ZRB are disproportionately impacted by fluctuations in the availability of Zambezi waters considering that the region is highly dependent on local natural resources, primarily from agriculture, pastoralism and mining. In other words, the productivity of the economies of these states are highly vulnerable to changes in access to water and its availability (Schulze et al., 2001; Beekman et al., 2003).

In most of the riparian countries, economic growth has been high in recent years and has exceeded population growth. The average annual growth rate of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in the last 10 years has been six percent. With an average GDP growth rate of 6% in the last decade, most of the ZRB countries have experienced high levels of economic growth; but despite all the riparian states being dependent on the Zambezi waters for development, they differ in terms of levels and trajectory of socio-economic development. This is highlighted in Table 1, which indicates the Human Development Index (HDI) ranking of each of the eight countries in 1999/2000 as compared to 2013. In addition to external factors such as socio-political unrest, this is largely due to the fact that distribution of mineral resources across each nation is not uniform, and various countries have focused on the exploitation of different resources (e.g. oil in Angola, and diamonds in Botswana and Namibia).

Table 1 - HDI Ranking of ZRB Countries

ZRB Countries	HDI Ranking in respective years	
	1999/2000 ^(*)	2013
Angola	160	149
Botswana	122	109
Malawi	159	174
Mozambique	169	178
Namibia	115	127
Tanzania	156	159
Zambia	151	141
Zimbabwe	151	156

^(*) Note: Ranking is taken from both 1999 and 2000 depending on most recent data at the time.

Source: Beekman et al., 2003; African Development Bank Group, 2015

The joint dependency of the riparian states on the Zambezi often gives rise to competition for the shared resources of the ZRB between the countries, such as the resource conflict between upstream and downstream countries in the case of energy production and dams for irrigation.

The greatest driver for the increased demand for water in the region is the rapid increase in population, with the current population expected to rise to 51 million by 2025. This, coupled with rapid urbanization (approximately 3% in the region) has led to a greater need for food, as well as increased industrial activity and thereby an increase in demand for the energy to support these activities.

As such, greater strain is placed on the Zambezi waters for use in agriculture, energy production and industry (*World Bank*, 2010; *ZAMCOM*, *SADC* and *SARDC*, 2015; *ZAMCOM*, 2008). As of 1996, agriculture contributed to 9% of the regional GDP and 60% of the local employment. In terms of water usage, at approximately 80% of total use, the agricultural sector constitutes the greatest use per sector in comparison to domestic or industrial water use (*Ashton and Ramasar*, 2002). With energy consumption outstripping production in a majority of the riparian states (*SADC*, 2012), energy production from hydropower is set to take up an increasingly larger proportion of the water resource usage. Growing demand from industry as well as a rapidly growing population has led to a widening energy deficit which the governments seek to close by embarking on a number of new hydro-electric projects within the river basin (*ZAMCOM*, *SADC* and *SARDC*, 2015). With the hydropower sector in the ZRB earmarked for priority development, it has been identified as a key investment opportunity in a market analysis conducted by the *World Bank* (2010).

In addition to water, energy is also required to support industrial activities such as mining. The main mining activity in the ZRB centres around copper, cobalt, platinum, gold, coal, asbestos, nickel and tin. Current trends in mineral prices suggest that mining activity in the region is set to increase in the coming years, consequently increasing pressure on the water resource for other income generating activities. While the mining sector has been a major driver for infrastructural development in the region (paving the way for improved roads and railways, reliable water supply and energy access), it also serves as a major contributor to the degradation of the environment as a result of largescale pollution of the river and reduction of water quality. This pollution has a severe impact on the local ecology and natural environment which is arguably one of the region's greatest assets. With a number of UNESCO listed World Heritage Sites (such as Victoria Falls), it is the basis of a thriving tourism industry which is a key driver for environmentally compatible sustainable socio-economic development in the region. The catalytic effect of activities within the sector can be observed as governments take steps support the industry by ensuring the availability of suitable infrastructure (e.g. improvements to airports in Zambia, and access roads in Malawi, Mozambique, Tanzania and Zambia), thereby creating and upward spiral of development with better infrastructure encouraging more tourism, and more tourism providing funds for further infrastructural developments (*ZAMCOM*, *SADC* and *SARDC*, 2015).

The Zambezi waters are critical to sustainable economic growth and poverty reduction in the region. In order to meet the basic needs of approximately 100 million people and sustain a rich and diverse natural environment, the river plays a central role in the economies of the eight riparian countries mentioned above. Zambezi provides important environmental goods and services to the region and is essential to regional food security and hydropower production. To understand its crucial effect to the economies of the riparian countries, we give an in-depth description of the economic development of each country separately.

1.2.1 Angola

Angola is a country with an estimated population of 28.3 million for the year 2017, with a life expectancy at birth of 60.2 years (*CIA*, 2017b). Angola has the third highest population growth rate in the world estimated to be around 3.52% per year (*CIA*, 2017c). Per the results from the last population census from 2014, nearly 25% of the country's population live in Luanda province, around and capital of Angola (*INE-Angola*, 2017). The labour force is around 12.51 million (estimated in 2017) and 85% of this labour force is engaged in agricultural activities. The rest of the population is engaged in industrial activities and services.

Following its independence from Portugal in 1975, Angola faced a destructive civil war that lasted for 27 years. Following a peace agreement in 1991, peace was apparently re-established in the country, but the fighting picked resumed in 1993 and lasted until 2002. Following the end of the civil the poverty headcount in Angola decreased from 62% in 2001 to 37% in 2009, with an average GDP growth rate of 15% during the same period (*World Bank*, 2013).

A widely accepted indicator of the economic performance of a country is GDP. In Angola specifically, it reached \$124.2 billion in 2017 being so, the 57th wealthier country in the world. However, the

GDP per capita in 2017 was \$3484,6 which ranks Angola 104th in the world (*World Bank*, 2018). Angola is an oil dependent country. As the second biggest producer in Africa, oil production accounts for nearly 50% of the country's GDP and more than 70% of the Government revenue. Because of this fact, the country is highly vulnerable of fluctuations in oil prices. With the recent falling in all prices, the country experienced a reduction of its GDP growth rate from 4.8% in 2014 to -0.7% in 2016 (*CIA*, 2017b). In sectorial terms, the largest contributions to the GDP in 2016 came from industry (61.4%), services (28.4%) and agriculture (10.2%). The inflation of the Angolan currency, Kwanza, in 2016 was the sixth highest of 2016 estimated to be around 32.4% (*CIA*, 2017c). The main commodities exported from Angola are: crude oil, diamonds, refined petroleum products, coffee, sisal, fish and fish products, timber, and cotton.

With the increase in oil prices during the 2017, and promising reforms that are on pipeline to be implemented by the new country's President, after a 38-years ruling period of its predecessor, it is expected that the country economy will improve its performance in the coming years. However, a failure to reduce their dependence on oil and strengthen other economic sectors will maintain the country vulnerability to global fluctuations in oil prices.

Angola relief is dominated by plateau areas where many rivers are originated. Most people live on plateau areas. Part of the rivers from the southeast plateau flow towards the Zambezi (*Clarence-Smith and Thornton*, 2018).

In terms of commercial development, limited water supply and energy are noted as obstacles faced in the country (*AfDB/OECD/UNDP*, 2017a). While the actual price of water varies with 1 cubic meter of water costing as much as 20USD in some regions, a 2004 decree by the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Energy and Water, the water price is set at 0.84USD per cubic meter (*Cain & Mulenga*, 2009; *PJTC Kunene*, 2017). A joint report by the *International Bank for Reconstruction and Development and the World Bank Group* (2005) notes that while private sector-supplied water from trucks and tankers cost between 0.45USD and 13.5 USD per cubic meter (a 50% to 200% markup), the price of piped water is heavily subsidized. As such, households in the peri-urban areas (outside the service area for national piped water), pay 10 to 20 times more for water.

According to the Joint Monitoring Programme for Water, Sanitation and Hygiene, access to at least basic drinking water service (*JMP*, 2018a) was at 41.0% in Angola in 2015. In terms of sanitation, the access to at least basic sanitation (*JMP*, 2018b) is around 39.4% (*JMP*, 2018b).

In terms of energy consumption around 35% of the total consumptions is from oil, and 4% from gas whereas 58% is still from biomass sources such as wood. There is a small percentage coming from hydroelectricity as well (3%). According to world bank data, the electricity supply network covers 40.5% of the total population.

1.2.2 Botswana

Botswana is a landlocked and arid to semiarid country (*Wingqvist and Dahlberg*, 2008). Botswana lacks enough surface water for both socio-economic and environmental sustainable development (*Juana et. al.* 2014). Over most of the country, rainfall is low, varying from 250 mm/year in the far southwest to 650 mm in the extreme north. Recurrent periods of drought exacerbate water scarcity. The country is highly vulnerable to seasonal variations in climate, influenced by the La Nina and El Nino events (*Wingqvist and Dahlberg*, 2008). Water resources in Botswana are characterized by the fact that it is a shared and scarce resource, unevenly distributed in time and space. Botswana is situated in the catchment basins of the Sashe-Limpopo, Okavango, Orange-Senqu, and Zambezi Rivers, all which are shared with other countries. All rivers, apart from the Okavango and Chobe, are ephemeral (*Wingqvist and Dahlberg*, 2008). The Okavango Delta and the Chobe and Linyati rivers, which form the northern border with Namibia, account for 95% of the country's surface water (*Republic of Botswana*, 2008; *FAO*, 2005). The country's total internal renewable water is 2.4 km³/year. Of this total, surface water produced internally accounts for 0.8 km³, while groundwater accounts for 1.7 km³/year and an overlap of 0.1 km³/year (*FAO*, 2005).

Groundwater resources, which supply two-thirds of water consumed, are used for domestic uses, livestock, and small areas of irrigation. Dams provide urban water supplies while rural areas largely rely on groundwater resources (*AfDB/OECD*, 2007). Human settlements are consuming an increasing percentage of water (41% in 2000), equaling the percentage used for irrigation and livestock in the same year. Mining and industrial needs consumed the balance.

Water resources management is the responsibility of a number of institutions, including the Ministry of Minerals, Energy and Water Resources (MMEWR), Ministry of Local Government (MLG), Ministry of Agriculture (MOA), District Councils, the National Conservation Strategy Agency (NCSA), and the Department of Waste Management and Pollution Control. In terms of water charges, the government subsidizes the operating costs of water delivery by more than 40%. In addition, there is a subsidy on water infrastructure.

Over the thirty years between independence in 1966 and the mid-1990s, Botswana was the fastest-growing economy in the world, with average annual GDP growth rates of over 10% (*Fibaek*, 2010). This rapid growth has been built upon the foundation of the diamond mining industry, which since its commencement in the early 1970s, took Botswana to be the largest producer of diamonds, by value, in the world. Botswana's four diamond mines are operated by Debswana, a 50-50 joint venture between the Botswana Government and De Beers of South Africa. Diamonds account for about 80 % of Botswana's export revenue (*AfDB/OECD*, 2003). The extractive sector remains dominant and mining accounted for more than one quarter of the gross domestic product in 2015.

In Botswana GDP reached \$17.4 billion in 2017 being so, the 115th wealthier country in the world. However, the GDP per capita in 2017 was \$7523.2 which ranks Botswana 78th in the world (World Bank, 2018). Prior to the emergence of the diamond industry, Botswana's economy was dominated by agriculture, particularly cattle rearing. In 2000/01, agriculture accounted for less than 3% of GDP, a fall-off from its levels of about 5% in the early 1990s. However, its national significance stems from the fact that agriculture provides a livelihood for more than 80% of the total population who live in rural areas. The agriculture sector accounts for 20% of total employment (formal and informal) generated within the country. However, agriculture only supplies about 50% of the food needs. Livestock accounts for about 80% of agricultural output. Though the sub-sector is largely underdeveloped and characterized by extensive systems in communal areas, it produces beef that remains a major foreign exchange earner after diamonds (*Jeffens and Nemaora*, 2015).

With regard to electric power, approximately 40% of Botswana's power supply requirements are imported through connections to the South African and Zambian grid lines under the authority of the Botswana Power Corporation (BPC). Domestic power supply is generated from coal and petroleum.

Tourism is an increasingly important sector and has grown significantly in recent years owing to the country's conservation practices and extensive nature preserves and also to the concerted efforts by the Government to promote the sector. The share of GDP from tourism was 14.8% in 2014 (*UNECA*, 2016a).

The manufacturing sector remains small and contributed 5.5% to GDP in 2015 (*UNECA*, 2016a). The other major individual contributors to GDP are wholesale and retail trade, finance, real estate and business services and public administration, education, health and social work, and community, social and personal services, all of which accounted for 49.7% of GDP in 2013 (*UNECA*, 2016a).

Despite recent improvements, the government's attempts to promote development in the private sector remain dogged by infrastructural challenges such as the recent electricity and water shortages (*AfDB/OECD/UNDP*, 2017b). A government report highlighting water supply in the country (*Republic of Botswana*, 2015) indicates the average monthly charge for water supply for three levels of usage (to average monthly bill for 10 m³, 25 m³ and 50 m³ respectively) across public, commercial and domestic users, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1- Average Water Charge across various users: Od LA refers to rural villages; old DWA refers to 16 major villages and old WUC refers to towns and cities. (Source: *Republic of Botswana*, 2015)

1.2.3 Malawi

Previously a former British protectorate of Nyasaland, Malawi became an independent nation in 1964. Following its independency, the country was ruled by a single party until its first elections that took place in 1994. Malawi, a small landlocked but peaceful country, has an estimated population of 19.1 million for year 2017, with a population growth rate of 3.3% per year (CIA, 2017d; NSO, 2016). The life expectancy at birth is 61.7 years. Increase in population causes strong pressure on land use, being more severe in the southern Malawi than in the northern part. Food demands of the country cannot be met currently due to increase in population which is not reflected in increase food production, associated with droughts, declining soil fertility, non-suitable (or outdated) agriculture practices (FAO, 2005).

Although Malawi has been able to achieve important structural and economic progress, poverty is still widespread. Around 50% of the Malawi's population lives below the poverty line (CIA, 2017). In Malawi, GDP reached \$6.3 billion in 2017 being so, one of the poorest countries in the world ranked 150th. However, the GDP per capita in 2017 was \$486.4, which makes Malawi the second poorest country in the world (World Bank, 2018). Due to the local and global conjecture, the GDP real growth rate has decelerated during the last three years from an estimated value 5.7% in 2014 to 2.3% in 2016 (CIA, 2017d). Similarly, to other African countries, the Malawian economy is also undiversified and vulnerable to external shocks (World Bank, 2012). In sectorial terms, the largest contributions to the GDP come from services (58.8% of 2016 GDP), agriculture (28.3%) and industry (16%). The labour force is constituted by around 7 million (in 2013) and 64.1% of the labour force are engaged in agricultural activities. The rest are engaged in industry (6.7%) and services (29.2%).

The Malawian economy has a substantial dependency on economic assistance from international monetary and donor agencies. It is also negatively affected by extreme weather events as it is the case of the El-Niño that when occurring causes a drought in the region, reducing the productivity from the agriculture sector. Nevertheless, the country has outlined a strategy within its 2014-2020 National Indicative Programme aimed at targeting sectors with a high potential for export generation while being nationally relevant. These are sectors such as agriculture (sugar cane, oil seeds),

agro-processing (maize, wheat, rice, cassava and pigeon peas) and beverage manufacture (AfDB/OECD/UNDP, 2017c). A hike in water tariffs of top 23% introduced by three water boards (Lilongwe Water Board, Northern Region Water Board and Blantyre Water Board) in late 2016, was recently reversed by the Ministry of Agriculture, Irrigation, and Water Development stating that the increases breached procedures laid out in Water Works Act and Consumer Protection Act (Mkandawire, 2017; Chilung, 2016).

Malawi has a considerable potential for hydropower, mainly along the Shire river, and solar energy as well but most of it has not been explored yet. At present, 251 megawatts of hydropower energy are produced. The national electrification rate in 2009 was around 10%, covering only 37% of the urban population and 2% of rural population, the main source of energy being charcoal and wood, which account to 94% of the energy in Malawi. Moreover, according to data from 2015 (*Index Mundi*, 2018) the main agricultural products in Malawi are: tobacco, sugarcane, tea, corn, potatoes, sweet potatoes, cassava (manioc, tapioca), sorghum, pulses, cotton, groundnuts, macadamia nuts, coffee; cattle, goats.

Malawi has 90% of its area in the Zambezi basin. Water resources are mainly available in lakes and aquifers. Many small dams built during the colonial period had not benefitted from maintenance for long time. Currently some are being rehabilitated to make water from rivers more available through the year. Groundwater has been exploited at significant amounts since 1930s. Since 1990s problems of overexploitation started to occur as a lot of wells were drilled. It is used for irrigation 80% of water, 15% for domestic use and around 5% for industry. There is a large influence of topography on spatial distribution of precipitation. Lowest rainfall is observed in lower Shire Valley (FAO, 2006). Lastly, according to the Joint Monitoring Programme for Water, Sanitation and Hygiene, access to at least basic drinking water service (JMP, 2018a) was at 67.2% in Malawi in 2015. In terms of sanitation, the access to at least basic sanitation (JMP, 2018b) is around 43.5% (JMP, 2018d).

1.2.4 Mozambique

Mozambique is a country with an estimated population of 27.1 million for the year 2017, with a life expectancy at birth of 54.4 years (*INE-Mozambique*, 2017), and a high estimated growth rate around 2.46% per year (*INE-Mozambique*, 2017) that imposes a huge challenge for development of social and economic infrastructures to accommodate this trend. More than half of the country's population lives below the poverty line. This situation challenges the country to translate its economic population growth into poverty reduction.

At its independence from Portugal in 1975, Mozambique was between the poorest countries of the world. A brutal civil war from 1977 and 1992 further deteriorated the performance of the country's economy. After the end of the civil war the country GDP has experienced a rapid growth around 8% on average (*World Bank*, 2017b). Today the GDP is \$12.33 billion being so, one of the poorest countries in the world ranked 130th, with GDP per capita in 2017 was \$519, which makes Malawi the fourth poorest country in the world (*World Bank*, 2018). During the last three years, the GDP real growth rate as decelerated from an estimated value of 7.4% in 2014 to 3.3% in 2016 (*INE*, 2017; *World Bank*, 2017b). The inflation rate of the country's currency Metical is very high and was estimated to be around 20% in 2016 (*World Bank*, 2017b).

In sectorial terms, the largest contributions to the GDP come from services (51% of 2016 GDP), agriculture (23%) and industry (19%). Although the country's constitution and successive government have identified agriculture as the base for development, this sector is registering a slight growing of its contribution for the country's economy. However, according to World Bank data, employment in agriculture corresponds to 73.3% of the total employment in the country (*Trading Economics*, 2018). This figure shows that with an underperforming agricultural sector it will be very difficult to fight poverty.

As two major international consortiums are finalizing their decision of investments to develop massive gas exploration projects it is predicted that sales of liquefied natural gas will generate several billion dollars in revenues annually after 2022. If materialized, these two exploitation projects pro-

jected for the offshore coast of the northern province of Cabo Delgado has the potential to become the largest gas infrastructure in Africa. A projected increased in coal exports and investments in Tete Province, in the Zambezi river basin, will give an additional contribution to boost the country's economy in the coming years (CIA, 2017e).

Other important mineral resources in Mozambique include tantalum beryllium and aluminium. The Mozambican share of the world's tantalum mine output amounted to 6%; beryllium, 5%; and aluminium, 2%. Cement is one of the most significant mineral processing operations in the domestic market, (Yager, 2007). Other minerals extracted in Mozambique include: Gold, Iron, Clays, Gemstones, Titanium.

According to the Joint Monitoring Programme for Water, Sanitation and Hygiene, access to at least basic drinking water service (JMP, 2018a) was at 47.3% in Mozambique in 2015. In terms of sanitation, the access to at least basic sanitation (JMP, 2018b) is around 23.6% (JMP, 2018e).

The electrification rate in Mozambique was around 26% in 2016. But access is mainly focused on urban areas. The vast majority (70%) of Mozambique's population lives in rural areas of which only 5.7% use electricity for lighting. Woodfire is still the main source of energy accounting up to 85% of the total energy consumption and can be as high as 95% in rural areas.

The various sectors are charged different rates for water usage depending on the specific types of use as shown in Table 2 and Table 3. Furthermore, the formula for Regulation of Regularized and Unregulated Gross Water Rates (Council of Ministers – Mozambique, 2016) is given as:

$$T_n = T_0 * (i * I_n / I_0 + k * K_n / K_0 + g * G_n / G_0),$$

where:

T_n : new raw water rate after revision

T_0 : rate of raw water in vigoi- before the revision

i : weight of inflation in the structure of costs

I_n : consumer Price Index for the month of review

I_0 : consumer Price Index for the month of last review

K : weight of the electric energy in the cost structure

K_n : average price of kW / h (medium voltage) meter of revision

K_0 : average price of kW / h (medium voltage) of the month of average price of diesel last review

g : weight of diesel in cost structure

G_n : average price of diesel of the month of revision

G_0 : average price of diesel for the month of last review

Table 2 - Types of Water use and Rates due in Mozambique

Types of Use and Utilization		Emission authorization research [Mt]	License of water catchment underground [Mt]	Exploration of subterranean water [Mt / m ³]	Extensions and renewals [Mt]
Agriculture	Family/Subsistence	0	0	0	0
	Commercial	500	500	0.6	850
Industry		850	1000	0.6	850
Supply of Water	Heavy Industry	1,000	1500	0.6	850
	Cottage Industry	--	500	1.5	850

(Source: Council of Ministers – Mozambique, 2012)

Table 3 - ARA-ZAMBEZE (Regional Water Administration for Zambezi Basin) Unregulated bulk water rates in [MT/m³]

Type of Activity	Type of Use	Fixed Rate		Bulk water not Regularized [Mt/m ³]
		Tf1 (Concession)	Tf2 [Mt/month]	
1) Commercial Agriculture	Family Scale ≤ 1ha	0	0	0
	Commercial Sector ≤ 50ha	600	120	0.05
	Commercial Sector 50 < ha ≤ 1000	2,000	400	0.08
	Commercial Sector > 1000 ha	3,000	1,000	0.09
2) Industry	Processing/Transformative	3,000	1,000	0.22
	Extractive	25,000	5,000	0.52
3) Water Supply	Small systems (≤ 5000 connections)	400	300	0.07
	Large Systems (> 5000 connections)	2,000	800	0.17
4) Thermoelectric	Central Thermoelectric ≤ 2 MW	5,000	1,500	0.10
	Central Thermoelectric 2 - 10 MW	8,500	3,000	0.17
	Central Thermoelectric > 10MW	25,000	6,000	0.24
5) Other Uses		600	120	0.17
Type of Activity	Type of Use	Sub-Category	Fixed Rate	Usage Fee Tv1 [Mt/m ³]
			Concession rent Tf1 [Mt]	License Hold Tf2 [Mt/month]
6) Basic Food Farming	Family Sector ≤ 1ha		0	0
	Associated 1 ha < Area ≤ 25	Subsistence Associates	197	0
	Associated 25 ha < Area ≤ 350 ha	Emerging Associates	522	348
	Associated Area > 350 ha	Commercial Associates	2,087	1,043
	Private 1 < Area ≤ 25 ha	Private	626	125
	Private 25 < Area ≤ 350 ha		730	487
	Private > 350 ha		2,783	1,391

(Source: Council of Ministers – Mozambique, 2016)

Impact of floods in society development- Zambezi Basin

Before 1960's the Zambezi River was a non-regulated river with distinct low flow and high flow seasons. In the Zambezi delta the flow was characterized by two flood peaks per year, the first being originated by local rainfall (in and around Mozambique) and the second was originated by rainfall in the upper and middle Zambeze that were delayed in time due to the presence of the Bartose and Chobe wetlands upstream. The timing of the floods was predictable so the population would restrain themselves from activities in the floodplains during the flood season (Bucx et al, 2014).

After the construction of the Kariba and Cahora Bassa dams the floods became less frequent and timing is less predictable (see Figure 2). The dams are able to attenuate small and some medium

floods but large floods still occur with major damages (*Fanaian, 2013*), e.g. in 1978, 1989, 1997, 2001 and recently in 2007, 2008 and 2015.

Figure 2 - Water levels at Marromeu gauging station (adapted from Beilfuss and Dos Santos, 2001)

Since the frequency of cyclical annual floods was drastically reduced the population felt safe to move their settlements closer to the fertile soils of the Zambezi floodplains increasing the exposure and risk. After the civil war (1992) people that fled to Malawi and Zimbabwe started moving back to Mozambique and into the Zambezi Delta, which was more abundant in water and other natural resources than the surrounding highlands. These newly settled people had no knowledge of the characteristics of the river and didn't perceive the risks of settling near the river in the floodplains (*Paagman et al., 2013*).

Off-season flooding associated with dam operation has been reported in the Zambezi. The floods were mostly associated with spilling in preparation for the rain season or to accommodate higher than normal flows into the reservoirs. These releases were done without proper notification to local communities and therefore often resulted in losses of agriculture produce by farmers along the flood plain.

In 1997 the water level in Marromeu rose up to 7.61 metres, which did not happen since 1987, so people were caught by surprise and damage to livelihoods was very high in the delta area. In 2001 the water level reached 7.69 meters and, although this level is not as extreme as before the flow regulation, people in the floodplains were again caught by surprise. 81 people died and 155 000 were left homeless.

Floods in the Lower Zambezi also affect the SENA railway which causes huge losses to the mining companies operating in Tete. These socio-economic impacts of floods have a direct impact in the Mozambican GDP.

1.2.5 Namibia

Namibia is highly dependent on its natural resource base of mining, agriculture, fishing, and wild-life-based tourism, and water is the single most important constraint to development. Water is supplied from three natural sources (*Lange, 1997*): groundwater (~54%), perennial surface water (~45%), and ephemeral surface water (~1%). It is sub-Saharan Africa's driest country; roughly 80% of its 842,000 km² consist of desert, arid, and semi-arid land (*Brown, 1994*). Namibia has a long history of water scarcity due to the arid climate and high evaporation rates. Rainfall is quite low, ranging from less than 50 mm to 700 mm/year with a long-term average of about 320 mm/year, less than the minimum amount considered necessary for dry land farming (400 mm/year). Rainfall is not only low but extremely variable over much of the country and droughts are a common occur-

rence. It is estimated that only 1% of annual rainfall contributes to groundwater recharge and only 2% is retained in reservoirs (DWA, 1991a).

In 2017 GDP reached \$13.24 billion being so, one of the poorest countries in the world ranked 125th. However, the GDP per capita in 2017 was \$5854.9, which places Namibia in the middle of the wealthiest countries in the world (World Bank, 2018). The Namibian economy is heavily dependent on the extraction and processing of minerals such as diamonds, copper, uranium, lead and zinc for export. Mining accounts for 8% of GDP but provides more than 50% of foreign exchange earnings (UNECA, 2016b). Namibia is the world's fourth-largest producer of uranium. It is also a small producer of gold. The mining sector employs only about 3% of the population. Despite this, the sector shrunk in 2016 as a result of the negative impact of drought on the energy and water sectors. The importance of the industry was further bolstered by a special industrialization programme announced by the government to facilitate joint ventures to increase domestic value addition. The state owned Epangelo Mining Company has the right to own all new mining licenses for the exploration of the government-declared national strategic minerals (uranium, gold, copper, coal, diamonds and rare earth metals) (AfDB/OECD/UNDP, 2017e). In sectoral terms, the largest components of the country's GDP are public administration and defence, mining and quarrying, wholesale and retail trade, manufacturing and education. In 2015, services are estimated to have accounted for 61% of output, while industry was 33%, and agriculture, forestry and fishing accounted for the remaining 6% (Namibia Statistics Agency, 2015a).

Only 2% of Namibia's land receives sufficient rainfall to grow crops (Namibia Country Profile, 2015). The agricultural sector consumes about 75% of water in the country, with the commercial agricultural being the largest sub-sector and communal farmers being the least consumptive (Dirkx et al., 2008). The majority of the water demand within commercial agriculture is for irrigation (up to 80%) with the remainder used for livestock rearing. There are about 4,000 commercial farms in Namibia, 3,000 of which are owned by whites. Cattle rising are predominant in the central and northern regions, while karakul sheep and goat farming are concentrated in the more arid southern regions. Over two-thirds of Namibians practice subsistence cropping and pastoralism, mostly on communally owned land. Less than 10% of land is used for cropping, whilst nearly 75% is used for grazing (Government of Namibia, 2002). Agriculture has a smaller contribution to external trade but employs around 30% of the workforce and is the source of income for the majority of the population. The primary sector in Namibia includes the rearing of livestock, processing of meat products, crop farming and forestry. The ongoing drought and the outbreak of foot-and-mouth disease are expected to lead to a 14.0% contraction in agriculture, a sector that provides nearly 30% of employment, much of it informal and vulnerable, despite accounting for only 4.0% of GDP (Bank of Namibia, 2015a). Namibia normally imports about 50% of its cereal requirements; in drought years food shortages are a major problem in rural areas.

Namibia also has one of the most productive fishing industries in the world based on the Benguela Current system. This system supports rich populations of fish, which form the basis for the Namibian marine fisheries. Fishing contributes to over 25% of the primary sector activities (UNECA, 2016b). Agriculture remains the most water-intensive sector nationally, using up to 60% of the country's resources, despite a comparatively low value-add per cubic meter of N\$7.2 against N\$272 in the manufacturing sector and N\$574 in the service sector. This is in the context of an average national water cost of 2.79 N\$ per cubic meter and an average national tariff of 2.89 N\$ per cubic meter – 2001/02 figures (PJTC Kunene, 2017).

The services sector contributes 62% to GDP of which wholesale and retail, transport and real estate are the main components. Tourism is a major contributor to this sector. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), the total contribution (direct and indirect) of tourism to Namibia's GDP in 2016 was \$1.6 billion (14.9% of 2016 GDP). The tourism industry grows every year, supplies 78,000 jobs and is the third largest sector for foreign exchange earnings (Grant and Krugel, 2017).

1.2.6 United Republic of Tanzania

Tanzania has an estimated population of 51.7 million inhabitants for 2017 (TNBS, 2016a). The population growth rate is around 2.7% (CIA, 2017). Tanzanian population is predominantly rural with 70% living in rural areas (National Bureau of Statistics, 2014). Former a British colony, Tanzania achieved its independency in 1960. After its independency the country was ruled by a single party until 1995 when the first elections took place. The life expectancy at birth is 61.8 years (TNBS, 2016b). The population below the poverty line is around 22.8%, being considerable lower than in most of the African countries.

Tanzania is a country with a relatively high sustained economic growth rate between 6 and 7% during the last decade (World Bank, 2017c). In 2017 the GDP reached \$52.09 billion ranked so, 80th among the other countries. However, the GDP per capita in 2017 was \$900.5, which makes Tanzania one of the poorest countries in the world (World Bank, 2018). The country is also experiencing a decline in poverty rate, although the absolute number of poor does not follow the same trend due to the relatively high population growth rate. The per capita GDP of the country has been experiencing a slightly growth from around US\$ 2800 in 2014 to an estimated value of US\$ 3100 in 2016 (CIA, 2017a).

The Tanzania's economy is more diversified than other countries from the Zambezi basin. In sectorial terms, the largest contributions to the GDP come from services (47.3% of 2016 GDP), industry (27.6%) and agriculture (24.5%).

Around 63% of employed persons work in the agricultural sector. And agriculture is also an economic activity even in the urban areas where 15% of the household were involved in agriculture in 2011/12. In terms of livestock, around 42% of all private households (both urban and rural) keep at least one type of livestock. And 0.5% of all households were engaged in fish farming.

Benefiting from a stable political and peaceful environment, Tanzania's economic prospects are promising. The country also benefits from increasing private investment from which is expected to boost the country's economy and contribute to create more productive jobs in the coming years.

The government recently announced economic and policy reforms including the establishment of a number of parastatals charged with the regulation of the natural monopolies and restructuring of existing ones such as the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (EWURA). This is in addition to capital budget expansions aimed at improving infrastructure such as transport, manufacturing and industrial development and water and power provision (AfDB/OECD/UNDP, 2017f). Historically EWURA sets national water prices, with a 2010 report into the sector (Uwazi, 2010) indicating rates of 0.637 shillings per litter for users with their own meters and 1 shilling per litter for patrons of public standpipes and water kiosks.

Around 37% of all private households (both urban and rural) are connected to a piped water supply network (12% with connections inside the house, 8% with yard connections and 17% with access to public standpipes). If we considering only urban areas then around 59% of the households are connected to a piped water supply network whereas in rural areas the percentage is around 26%. The main source of drinking water in rural areas is the unprotected dug well (25%).

According to the Joint Monitoring Programme for Water, Sanitation and Hygiene, access to at least basic drinking water service (JMP, 2018a) was at 50.1% in Tanzania in 2015. In terms of sanitation, the access to at least basic sanitation (JMP, 2018b) is around 23.5% (JMP, 2018f).

In terms of energy source, only 3% of the population use modern sources of energy for cooking (electricity or gas). Around 68.5% use firewood and 25.7% use charcoal as the main source of energy for cooking.

For lighting, in urban areas the main source is electricity with 49% whereas in rural areas the main source is kerosene (51%). The percentage of households using electricity for lighting has been increasing significantly over the past decade.

According to the *2030 Water Resources Group* (2014), the impact of water availability is felt in macro-economic reporting and micro-economic behaviours. Historically large part of economy is supported by agriculture, using traditional irrigation methods which consume a lot of water. Low labour productivity in agriculture sector sometimes occurs due to water unavailability. Electricity production is also very important for economic development, and lot of hydropower production is sensitive to seasonal and climatic variations.

1.2.7 Zambia

Zambia has abundant surface and groundwater water resources. The country receives moderate rainfall ranging from an annual average of approximately 600 mm in the south to 1,335.9 mm/year in the north. Zambia lies within the Zambezi and Congo River Basins. There is an extensive river network consisting of the Zambezi, Kafue, Luangwa (in the Zambezi Basin), Chambeshi, and Luapula Rivers (in the Congo Basin). In addition, there are several large lakes, and many small lakes. Wetlands and *dambos* (shallow grassy wetlands in plateau areas) cover approximately 5% of Zambia's total land area. Zambia generates an estimated 100 km³/year of surface water and an estimated annual renewable groundwater potential of 49.6 km³/year (*Republic of Zambia*, 2010). Zambia's ground water resources are abundant, estimated at 1,740,380 million m³ with the ground water recharge estimated at 160,080 million m³/year. Most of the surface water resource is poorly distributed while groundwater is fairly well distributed. Zambia has only built 5 very large dams and has roughly 1,700 small dams. A nationwide inventory carried out by Government in 1998 estimated that there are 11,000 boreholes and 22,000 protected wells in the country (*Republic of Zambia*, 2010).

Zambia is well endowed with mineral resources and derives most of its foreign earnings from the export of minerals. The mining industry, which is dominated by copper and a few other minerals namely, zinc, silver, gold and cobalt, has been the most important driving force of economic development in Zambia for over 70 years (*AfDB/OECD*, 2003). Copper mining accounts for over 70% of export earnings but employs less than 2% of the population (*UN-Zambia*, 2015). In 2017 GDP reached \$25.8 billion placed so, in the middle rank among the other countries, with GDP per capita \$1646.1, which makes Malawi one of the poorest countries in the world (*World Bank*, 2018). Agriculture is another important sector in Zambia, contributing an average of 8.2% to the national GDP over the period 2011-2015 (*World Bank*, 2016). The country has a landmass area approximately 752,000 km² of which 34% is agricultural, with about 3% of the agricultural land irrigated. Most of the irrigated land lies along railway lines, above karstic areas for groundwater, adjacent to water bodies, and in *dambos* and wetlands. 82% of Zambia's farming households are small-scale farmers, cultivating 5 ha or less of rain-fed land. Primary agriculture contributes 35% of the country's total non-traditional exports and about 10% of the total export earnings for the country. Almost half of the economically active population is employed in the agricultural sector, which also constitutes the main livelihood source for an estimated 1.5 million households, representing 60% of all households in Zambia (*World Bank*, 2017). Approximately 70% of agricultural labour is provided by women (*World Bank*, 2017). Across the country, livestock constitute 20% of the household assets, and contributes 6% to smallholder household incomes and consumption (*IAPRI*, 2013).

The manufacturing sector accounts for about 7.9% of GDP (*AfDB/OECD/UNDP*, 2017g). Food, beverages and tobacco are the largest manufacturing sub-sectors and this has been due to the improved access of Zambian products to markets in the Southern African Development Community (SADC), the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA), and the European Union (EU) following the signing of the SADC Trade Protocol and the coming of the Free Trade Area (FTA) in COMESA. The overall trend of the secondary sector remains positive, with reported GDP value addition of over 35% in 2014 (*UNECA*, 2016). The major contributors to the service sector are wholesale and retail trade, which accounts for 19% of GDP. Other sectors of the economy contributed to the national GDP in 2014 as follows: public administration and defense 18.9%, finance, real estate and business services 9.9%, transport, storage and communication 8.5%, wholesale and retail trade 19.3%, electricity gas and water 2.2%, and construction 15.1%. Tourism, another sector of the economy, contributed 3.2% to the national GDP in 2016. The country has 19 National

Parks and 34 Game Management Areas (GMAs) covering 33% of the country, but only 5% of this has been developed for tourism. The National Heritage Conservation Commission (NHCC) has catalogued well over 1 700 potential sites for tourism development that remain unexploited. These sites comprise archaeological, geological, historical, natural, and traditional sites. Zambia has over 35% of the water resource in Southern Africa offering enormous tourist opportunities such as the world famous Victoria Falls.

Generally, economic growth in Zambia has been concentrated in capital-intensive industries such as construction, mining and transport. Growth has taken place in urban areas, while the poorest tend to live in remote areas that are barely connected to markets and the cash economy. Economic growth has not been labour intensive, particularly in those sectors in which the poor tend to work (subsistence agriculture and the informal sector). In terms of water use, agriculture accounts for 76% of water use; domestic use accounts for another 17% and industry the final 7%.

Extreme weather in the form of drought and floods remain a key challenge, resulting in impacts on other sectors such as agriculture, tourism and power in particular. However, the completion of the Kafue Gorge Lower Dam in 2021 is expected to significantly improve the power situation (AfDB/OECD/UNDP, 2017g).

The *Ministry of Water Affairs and Forestry* (1999) outlined a pricing strategy based on four core objectives:

- Social equity
- Ecological sustainability
- Financial sustainability
- Economic efficiency

The National Water Act outlines three types of uses of water (see Table 4), all charged under the following tariffs for the abstraction of raw water from rivers and streams:

- K5,000 is charged for water abstracted up to 500m³/day.
- K1 is charged for the temporary use of water (minimum 1 year) for every excess cubic metre of water abstracted above 500m³/day.
- K2 is charged for a new water right for water abstracted for every excess cubic metre of water above 500m³/day.
- K3 is charged for a renewed water right to abstract water for every excess cubic meter of water above 500m³/day.

Table 4 - Types of Water Use (Source: Ministry of Energy and Water Resource Development, 2008)

Type of Use	Description
Primary	use of water for basic domestic purposes and stock watering. It refers to the primary needs of an individual and does not attract a water right and thus no water charges are paid
Secondary	use of water for irrigation and aquaculture
Tertiary	use of water for industrial, mechanical and hydroelectricity generation

1.2.8 Zimbabwe

Zimbabwe is a land locked country bordered by Zambia, Namibia, Mozambique, Botswana, and South Africa. It has a population of approximately 13 million people (AfDB, 2011). The total area of the country is 390,580 km² of which land is 386,670 km² and the rest is covered by water bodies (Makurira and Viriri, 2017). Zimbabwe is well endowed with water resources both surface water and groundwater. Access to and development of water resources is governed by the Water Act (Chapter 20:24) of 1998. The Water Act is complemented by other Acts and policies (Makurira and Viriri, 2017). While access to water for basic use and to sustain life is free, any use of water from

which an economic benefit is derived is classified as commercial use in which case a user would be required to obtain a permit for such use. However, traditional systems also exist whereby traditional leaders hold power to declare water protection areas especially where quality is an issue. Zimbabwe has total annual internal renewable water resources of 12.26 km³ of which 11.26 km³ are surface water resources and 6 km³ are groundwater, with an estimated 5 km³ overlap between the two sources.

The natural resources extraction sectors of agriculture, forestry, fishing and hunting, and mining and quarrying dominate sectoral contribution to national output and together accounted for about 20.1% of GDP in 2014 (UNECA, 2016d). The agriculture, fisheries and forestry sectors supply 60% of the raw materials required by the industrial sector, contribute 40% of total export earnings (Ministry of Finance and Economic Development, 2014), consume about 40% of industrial output, contribute 19% to GDP and provide a source of livelihood to 70% of the national population (Ministry of Finance and Economic Development, 2015). Agriculture is the foundation of rural livelihoods, and rural areas are home to two-thirds of Zimbabwe's population, as well as 79% of the poor and 92% of the extreme poor. The contraction in agricultural output appears to have increased the national headcount poverty rate by at least 1.5% in 2015.

In Zimbabwe the GDP was \$17.84 billion in 2017 with the GDP per capita being \$927.4, which makes Zimbabwe one of the poorest countries in the world (156th out of 184) (World Bank, 2018). The manufacturing sector employs about 4% (Zimbabwe National Statistics Agency, 2014). However, its contribution to GDP has declined gradually over the last few years, dropping between 2009 and 2014 from 13.1 to 10.2%. On the other hand, the construction sector's contribution to GDP has increased marginally from 2.6% in 2011 to 3% in 2014. The secondary sector has a small manufacturing component and a waning industrial component. Since 2012, the industrial sector's contribution to GDP has been trending lower, falling from 31.6% of GDP in 2012 to 28.5% of GDP in 2015. The services sector continues to be the largest contributor to GDP. It is mainly driven by the finance & insurance subsector, the distribution, hotels & restaurants subsector and the transport & communication subsector. As a result, the contribution of the services sector to GDP increased from 54% in 2011 to 59% in 2015.

The energy sector in Zimbabwe is dominated by electricity, while fuel wood provides the majority of energy for domestic use in rural areas (Brown *et. al.* 2012). The majority of electricity is produced by the Kariba dam with a capacity to generate 750 MW (40% of national supply), Hwange thermal power station (46% of national supply), Harare thermal power station (5% of national supply), Bulawayo thermal power station (4.5% of national supply) and Munyati thermal power station (5% of national supply). While national electricity demand is about 2 200 MW, only about 1 200 MW is generated in Zimbabwe.

The overall economic recovery has remained fragile, however, owing to various external and internal factors and growth has continued to decline since then, dropping to 4.5% in 2013 and to 3.8% in 2014. Declining commodity prices, the exchange rate between the United States dollar and the South African rand, the uncertain prospects for world economic growth, and the impact of unilateral economic sanctions continue to undermine the country's growth prospects and revival. The government is ineligible to access new financing from multilateral institutions as it is in arrears with its repayments of this external debt.

At present, according to the Government of Zimbabwe (2010), the vast majority of Zimbabwe's water is used in the agricultural sector (80%) followed by the urban and industrial sector (15%), rural authorities (2%), conservation (2%) and mining (1%). Estimates by the International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources indicate that Zimbabwe's water demand far outstrips supply by 631 million m³ (Brown *et. al.* 2012).

Commercial development has been hampered by a lack of business confidence brought about by inefficient services such as unreliable electricity and water supply. In recent years, donor funding has gone towards the development of water infrastructure with ZimFund providing Urgent Water Supply and Sanitation Rehabilitation in a number of areas (AfDB/OECD/UNDP, 2017h). The main water resource management agency in the country is the Zimbabwe National Water Authority

(ZINWA), which is responsible for setting national tariffs. ZINWA aims to “ensure equitable accessibility to water by all”, and it seeks to maintain affordable water tariffs for citizens. Treated water supply costs 0.4USD per cubic metre to residents in high density areas, and 0.8USD per cubic metre in low density areas. Commercial users (in high density areas) are charged 30USD per cubic metre of water (ZINWA, 2016).

2 FORMULATION OF THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT MODEL

The analysis developed above demonstrates that all parts of an economy are based on water use in a direct or indirect way. From energy production to sanitation and hygiene rules, water plays a decisive role in their advancement. Moreover, water resources provide important benefits to human kind, which are difficult to be measured as they do not create monetary value, such as recreational and spiritual services or supporting the life cycle of the natural habitat of all animals. Hence, the motor of all societies and the main conductor of their development is access to water.

However, freshwater ecosystems are under threat from the effects of multiple stressors, including organic and inorganic pollution, land use changes, water abstraction, invasive species and pathogens (Brauman *et al.*, 2014). Little is known beyond the described effects of single stressors on the chemical and ecological status of water bodies and on their ecosystem functionality. This lack of knowledge limits our capacity to understand ecosystem responses to multiple stressors and to define a programme of measures that can improve the ecological status of a water body. People rely on ecosystems to provide many water-related services (Brouwer *et al.*, 2013). Stakeholders, the beneficiaries of ecosystem services (ES) and those who own and manage landscapes that produce them play a key role in ecosystem service analysis. They identify the services they receive from a water body and its catchment (Brouwer, *et al.*, 2013).

For physical, social and economic reasons, water is a classic non-market resource. Even for commodity uses, market prices for water are seldom available or when observable, often are subject to biases. However, due to the increasing scarcity of water and/or the resources required to develop water, affecting both its commodity and environmental benefits, economic evaluation plays an increasingly important role in public decision on water projects, reallocation proposals and other water policies (Young, 1996). People’s preferences can also play an important role in pricing the water use. When it comes to sustainable wetland management choices Birol *et al.* (2009) showed that people value higher a possible flood risk reduction than biodiversity conservation or improvement of recreational access through a choice experiment for Bobrek wetland in Poland.

Several studies have been conducted aiming to identify an integrated assessment framework for the management of the aquatic ecosystems. Pistocchi *et al.* (2017) present a five-step framework for the analysis of different pressures to a river basin, while Koundouri and Davila (2015) demonstrate a methodology for the assessment of the total economic value of water services in order to enhance current levels of cost recovery. In addition, another paper shows that in order to improve policy design, socioeconomic and environmental dimensions of water policies should be considered in developing supportive methodologies (Koundouri, Akinsete and Tsani, 2019).

The ecosystem services framework aims to support informed decision making by explicitly linking the goods and services produced by functioning ecosystems to human well-being, illustrating the broad impacts of various land-use scenarios. The “Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity” approach, as explained by Kumar (2012), provides a framework for assessing multiple stressors and multiple outputs of a river Basin, facilitating management of complex systems. Therefore, we will focus on using economic – mathematical tools which can describe and value an ecosystem services approach in our study.

Based on the above we developed the following model, which aims to identify the optimal economic development pathways and their dependence on water resources availability, focusing on five sectors, which are the pillars of the countries of our study, agricultural, energy production, mining, residential and tourism sector. There are eight countries in our model, the upstream and downstream countries, which are characterised so, due to their physical location and so their hierar-

chical access to the water deriving from Omo river. Through a cost-benefit analysis, two different scenarios will be explored: the non-cooperative, where the two countries maximise their net benefit curves without considering the externalities caused to their neighbours or the benefits arising from a possible trade, and the cooperative scenario, where the two countries are trading goods between them. At the end, this model determines which pathway is the optimal one for both countries and also the impact on the water levels of lake Turkana.

2.1 MODELLING OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT UNDER WEF NEXUS PERSPECTIVE

One of the most direct methods for estimating the total economic value (TEV) of water is to look at the market price for water. Here the market price of water means the market price of:

- goods and services that are used to maintain good quality and sufficient quantity of water;
- goods and services that are affected by the quality and quantity of water.

Although a market price may be observed for water, the simple single observation of what people pay for water, or the price it is sold at, does not allow an estimate for the overall value of water to be developed. In order to use the market price for estimating the value of water to consumers, market transactions for water must be observed across a number of different price levels and demand situations. By tracing the relative amount of water demanded at different prices, it is possible to map out the demand curve for water. This demand curve is the consumers' willingness-to-pay (WTP), i.e. value, which can then be used to calculate the change in consumer surplus, resulting from a policy that changes the demand curve.

There is a standard method used to measure the value of input in the five-core water-dependent economic sectors of a country:

- a) Agriculture (including aquaculture),
- b) Residential Water Supply,
- c) Mining (Industry),
- d) Energy Production,
- e) Tourism,

by evaluating the benefit of the input into the overall production. This approach defines water as one of the necessary inputs to production. More specifically, the **production (output)** Y_i , per specific sector $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, is related with the water quantity w_i , which is one of the necessary inputs to production procedure, and with other factors of production (variables) such as labour, capital, natural capital, etc. (cf. Section 3). Collapsing all the variables, except for the water quantity w_i , to their means, we obtain the equation:

$$Y_i = \hat{f}_i(w_i), \tag{1}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}'_i(w_i) &= \text{marginal contribution of the water to the production of sector } i \\ &= \text{maximum WTP by sector } i \text{ for each unit of water} \\ &= \text{price of the water for sector } i = p, i = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \end{aligned}$$

Although a good's own price is important in determining consumers' willingness to purchase it, other variables also have influence on that decision; such as consumers' incomes, their tastes and preferences, the prices of other goods that serve as substitutes or complements, and so on. Economists attempt to capture all of these influences in a relationship called the demand function for each sector $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$. The demand curve is a graphical representation of the relationship between the price of a good or service, here the water, and the quantity demanded for a given period of time. In other words, the demand curve shows exactly how many units of the water will be pur-

chased at various prices. Thus, estimating the function of (1) (cf. Section 3), we finally obtain the **inverse demand** function (curve) for each sector $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, using $p = \hat{f}'_i(w_i)$.

In general, economists believe that as the price of a good rises, buyers will choose to buy less of it, and as its price falls, they buy more. Therefore, as p increases over time due to decreasing water availability, water demand for each of these economic sectors reaches zero sequentially, given by the ordering of the intercepts $\hat{f}'_1(0) < \hat{f}'_2(0) < \hat{f}'_3(0) < \hat{f}'_4(0) < \hat{f}'_5(0)$. We denote by T_j the **exit time** of the j -th, $j=1, 2, \dots, 5$, sector, where we also define $T_0 \triangleq 0$, thus time is divided into 5 exit stages and we end up with an ordering of 5 sectors via their inverse demand function.

In addition, if consumers are the only group deriving benefits from a commodity, i.e. water, then the inverse demand curve is the marginal social benefit curve. Marginal social benefit is the benefit society receives when an additional unit of the commodity is produced. It is obvious that by integration of the inverse demand curve, we obtain the **Social Benefit** (SB_i) of each sector $i=1, 2, \dots, 5$.

2.2 GENERALIZATION OF THE MODEL IN THE RIVER BASIN WATER SHARING CASE

As multiple countries share a river, the competition over the available water resources is acute under climate change and meeting freshwater demand for agriculture and other vital uses becomes one of the impending challenges for policy makers. In the past, water planners struggled with the problem of estimating water demand with supply uncertainties. Also, the majority of current water-sharing arrangements do not take into account the variability of river flow (*Giodarno and Wolf, 2003*). Climate change challenges the existing water resource management practices by adding further uncertainties (*IPCC, 2007; Vorosmarty, 2002*). This becomes a troubling issue, particularly for transboundary water-sharing agreements (*Stephen and Kundell, 2008*). Unless new approaches to water management are developed that take into account these new uncertainties, future conflict over water resource are likely to increase (*Gleick, 1992*).

Several studies have analysed the impact of water scarcity on cooperation in water sharing, of which some take into account deterministic water flows and analyse the factors that influence stability of treaties and motivate negotiations (*Ambec and Sprumont, 2002; Beard and McDonald, 2007; Ambec and Ehlers, 2008; Janmatt and Ruijs, 2007*). Other studies go beyond static measures of water availability. In particular, *Dinar (2009)* shows that, under increased variability of water supply, a cooperative approach in the form of risk sharing may be preferred over an individual solution. In such circumstances, strategic alliance becomes the basis for a cooperative arrangement to address the impact of climate change on the stability of water sharing treaties. Using empirical data, *Dinar et al. (2010)* demonstrate a bell-shaped relationship between water supply variations and treaty cooperation. *Ansink and Ruijs (2008)* also demonstrate that a decrease in mean flow of a river reduces the stability of an agreement, while an increase in variance may have both positive and negative effects on treaty stability.

The approach presented here captures the influence of stochastic water resources on transboundary water allocation, over multiple sectors of the economy, following a multistage dynamic cooperative game approach. We show how issue linkage can facilitate cooperation between countries, even in the case of climate change. We illustrate the model with the case of water sharing between an upstream area, consisting of Angola, Botswana, Namibia, Zambia, Zimbabwe and a downstream area, consisting of Mozambique. The “*issue linkage to water sharing*” in this case concerns the trade of hydropower produced from the downstream area to the upstream area. Thus, we will investigate if the issue of water sharing can be linked hydropower export as the basis for attaining sustained cooperation in water distribution.

To date, the only bi-lateral agreement over the ZRB is the 1987 ZRA Agreement between Zambia and Zimbabwe. This agreement includes the provision “to ensure the efficient and equitable use of the waters of the Zambezi River”, and contains the obligation to cooperate by “keep[ing] each other informed of any proposals [regarding] the abstraction of water from the Kariba dam”. The main

purpose of the agreement is to obtain for the economic, industrial and social development of the two countries, the greatest possible benefit from the natural advantages offered by the waters of the Zambezi River and to improve and intensify the utilization of the waters for the production of energy and for any other purpose beneficial to the two countries. See also MS4, WP2.

On the other hand, the largest hydropower producer in Mozambique is the Cahora Bassa hydroelectric power plant. Cahora Bassa is an artificial lake with an area of 2900 km². The maximum length and width of the reservoir are 270 km and 30 km, respectively. The storage capacity of this reservoir created by the dam is 52 km³. The maximum discharge capacity of the dam is 14,000 m³/s. (HCB, 2018)

The Hidroeléctrica de Cahora-Bassa (HCB) is the concessionaire company of the Cahora-Bassa dam, with the responsibility of managing, operating and maintaining the 2,075 MW hydroelectric power station and owned transmission lines (HCB, 2017). Energy produced from HCB, totalling 1,450 MW, is sold under fixed contracts to the Electricity Supply Commission of South Africa (ESKOM) - 72%, Electricidade de Moçambique (EDM) - 21% and the Zimbabwe Electricity Supply Authority ZESA - 7%. When available, additional production is sold through power sale agreements mainly to EDM and the Southern Africa Power Pool (SAPP).

The off-flow from the hydropower generation at the Kafue and Kariba dams represents the largest inflow to Cahora-Bassa. Additional flows are brought to the reservoir by the Luangwa, Panhame and Mussenguezi rivers, tributaries of the Cahora-Bassa sub-basin. The average inflow to the lake is 70 km³. However, inflows to the lake have registered a declining trend and have reached their lower value of 41.0 km³ in 2016 (see Table 5). Consequently, the energy production has declined 8.27% from previous year, and sales went down by approximately 7.5%. This difficult hydrological situation caused the water levels in the reservoir to reach the lowest level as the 2015/2016 hydrological year was classified as severe drought year, with an estimated return period of 25 years. (HCB, 2017).

Table 5 - Water and production indicators from years 2010 to 2016 (Source: HCB, 2017)

Parameters	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	% Δ_{15-16}
Inflows [km ³]	95.5	80.0	62.3	69.1	67.9	65.9	41.0	-37.8
Water passed through turbine [km ³]	55.6	54.5	49.4	49.4	53.1	56.2	55.3	-1.6
Discharged water [km ³]	34.6	20.0	7.4	16.6	8.0	4.0	0.0	
Evaporated water [km ³]	4.7	5.6	5.0	5.4	4.9	5.1	4.3	-15.7
Total production [GWh]	16,289.8	16,113.6	14,619.1	14,431.5	15,892.1	16,978.4	15,574.9	-8.3

We first model the multistage allocation of stochastic water resources between the upstream and the downstream area in a non-cooperative framework, where the upstream (*U*) area chooses how much water to divert unilaterally per sector in order to maximize its own welfare. The downstream (*D*) area acts as a “follower,” whose water availability depends on the flow of water diverted by the upstream area. We next construct a stochastic differential “leader–follower” game setting, where the downstream area offers a discounted price for hydropower exports to the upstream area in exchange for more transboundary water flow. Finally, we compare both the cooperative and non-cooperative outcomes in a possible climate change scenario.

There is a substantial body of literature on stochastic water resource management from which only few studies exist on the influence of stochastic water resource management on transboundary water sharing. *Bhaduri et al.* (2011) investigated the uncertainty in water resource management in a transboundary water sharing problem and evaluated the scope and sustainability for a potential cooperative agreement between countries. On the other hand, *Kim et al.* (1989) studied a deterministic renewable groundwater optimal management problem in the face of two-sector linear de-

mands, while *Koundouri and Christou* (2006) revisited this problem under the presence of a back-stop technology.

Our contribution in this framework is the introduction of the five core water economic sectors taking into account their dependence with the social benefit of water use per country. We assume that water resources evolve through time and follow a geometric Brownian motion. However, the characteristics of Brownian motion in terms of variance are different between the upstream and the downstream area, based on the assumption that the effects of climate change are regionally different. Additionally, we are able to determine how the water abstraction of the riparian countries will change in the long run, taking into account the greater variability of water availability caused by climate change. In other words, the suggested model describes water allocation between the upstream and the downstream area in such a case, with and without any cooperation in water sharing, taking into account how uncertainty in water supply affects the water abstraction rates of the countries, and explores the underlying conditions that may influence decisions on water allocations.

The upstream area has the upper riparian right to unilaterally divert water while the freshwater availability of the downstream one partially depends on the water usage in the upstream area. We denote the areas by superscripts, where U denotes the upstream area and D stands for the downstream area.

Following *Bhaduri et al.* (2011), we consider at first a complete filtered probability space

$(\Omega, \mathfrak{F}, \mathfrak{F}_t, P)$ and we assume that water flow is stochastic and uncertainty in the flow of water can be attributed to climate change. Then the annual renewable water resource due to the river basin, W_t , evolves through time according to the Geometric Brownian motion:

$$dW_t = \sigma^W W_t dz_t^W, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

where z_t^W is a standard Wiener process and σ^W can be considered as the volatility of water flow in the upstream area.

Let us denote by w_t^h the total freshwater utilization and by T_i^h the **exit time** of the i -th sector, per area $h = U, D$, and for each sector $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, together with the convention of $T_0 \triangleq 0$. Then the change in the level of water resources available in the upstream area, W_t^U , for the j -th exit stage is represented by

$$dW_{jt}^U = \left[W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{it}^U \right] dt, \quad T_{j-1}^U \leq t < T_j^U, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (3)$$

where $W_{00}^U = wr_0$ is an initial condition. The water availability in the downstream area depends on the total water consumption in the upstream one and runoff, denoted by R_t , which is also stochastic in the model. Thus, the latter can be expressed through another Geometric Brownian motion as

$$dR_t = \sigma^R R_t dz_t^R, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

where σ^R is considered to be the corresponding volatility and z_t^R is another standard Wiener process independent of z_t^W . Thus, the stock of water in the downstream area, where agricultural products and fisheries are produced, is denoted by S_t , and is a function of the stochastic water resources and the control variables $w_t^h = (w_{1,t}^h, w_{2,t}^h, \dots, w_{5,t}^h)$ per area $h = U, D$; in fact, for the (j, k) -th exit stage of the upstream and downstream areas, respectively, it follows the dynamics:

$$dS_{jkt} = \left\{ W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{it}^U - \sum_{l=k}^5 w_{it}^D + R_t - O_t \right\} dt, \quad T_{j-1}^U \leq t < T_j^U \quad \text{and} \quad T_{k-1}^D \leq t < T_k^D, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (5)$$

where $S_{000} = s_0$ is an initial condition. Here, O_t denotes the outflow and evaporation of water from this area and can be formulated by a third Geometric Brownian motion as

$$dO_t = \sigma^O O_t dz_t^O, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (6)$$

with volatility σ^O and z_t^O being a third standard Wiener process independent of z_t^W and z_t^R .

In view of (1), we assume that the inverse demand function for the water utilization of the j -th exit stage, per sector i and area h , is represented by

$$p_{jt}^h = \frac{a_i^h}{b_i^h} - \frac{1}{b_i^h} \cdot w_{it}^h, \quad T_{j-1}^h \leq t < T_j^h, \quad i = j, \dots, 5, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad h = U, D, \quad (7)$$

where p_{jt}^h is the price of water at each stage j , which is the same for the different sectors, and $a_i^h \in \sim$, $b_i^h > 0$ are constant sector-specific demand parameters. The sector-specific inverse demand curves are ordered so that $a_1^h / b_1^h < a_2^h / b_2^h < \dots < a_5^h / b_5^h$, which implies that water demand for each of the five sectors reaches zero sequentially over time as the price of water increases over time, leading to the endogenously defined exit times T_j^h , $j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, of the five economic sectors per area $h = U, D$. Here, aggregate water demand turns out to be a piecewise linear function.

Since consumers are the only group deriving benefits from water, the inverse demand curve is the marginal social benefit curve. Hence, consider further the benefit of water consumption w_i^h per sector i of area h , namely social benefit (SB), as

$$SB_i^h(w_i^h) = \int_0^{w_i^h} \left(\frac{a_i^h}{b_i^h} - \frac{1}{b_i^h} \cdot w_i^h \right) dw_i^h = \frac{a_i^h}{b_i^h} w_i^h - \frac{1}{2b_i^h} \cdot (w_i^h)^2, \quad h = U, D, \quad i = 1, \dots, 5. \quad (8)$$

It is obvious that the benefit function is strictly concave for all possible values of w_i^h .

Water abstraction from rivers may be taken directly from the flowing waters in the channel (surface water abstraction) or can be achieved through inter-basin flow transfer schemes. Thus, we may assume that the marginal extraction cost (MC) for the j -th exit stage of the upstream area is a decreasing function of the available water resources W^U of the form:

$$MC^U(W_j^U) = k_2^U - k_1^U W_j^U, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

where $k_1^U, k_2^U > 0$ are given constants. In fact, we consider that as water becomes increasingly scarce in the economy, the government would exploit water through appropriating and purchasing a greater share of aggregate economic output, in terms of dams, pumping stations, supply infrastructure, etc. (Barbier, 2000). Given the high cost of building infrastructure and expanding supplies, this will lead to a higher marginal cost of water. Then the total cost (TC) function of water withdrawing w_i^U from the river per sector $i = j, \dots, 5$, for the j -th exit stage of the upstream area is given by

$$TC^U(W_j^U, w_i^U) = (k_2^U - k_1^U W_j^U) w_i^U, \quad i = j, \dots, 5, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (9)$$

which is an increasing function of the water extraction variable. On the other hand, the downstream area extracts water from its available stock, thus for the (j,k) -th exit stage the MC of the downstream area is a decreasing function of the available water stock S_{jk}^D and has the form:

$$MC^D(S_{jk}^D) = k_2^D - k_1^D S_{jk}^D, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

where $k_1^D, k_2^D > 0$ are given constants. Then the TC function of water withdrawing w_l^D from the water stock in the downstream area per sector $l = k, \dots, 5$ for the (j,k) -th exit stage is given by

$$TC^D(S_{jk}^D, w_l^D) = (k_2^D - k_1^D S_{jk}^D) w_l^D, \quad l = k, \dots, 5, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (10)$$

which is an increasing function of the water extraction variables.

2.2.1 Non-Cooperative Approach

We present below a non-cooperative framework, where there is no any agreement between the two areas regarding either water or hydropower sharing.

Upstream Case

The upstream area chooses the economically potential rate of water utilization that maximizes its own net benefit (NB) per j -th exit stage, which can be expressed as

$$NB_j^U = \sum_{i=j}^5 SB_i^U(w_i^U) - \sum_{i=j}^5 TC^U(W_j^U, w_i^U), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \quad (11)$$

Thus, from (8)-(11) the upstream area maximization problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} J^U &= \max_{w_{\cdot}^U} \sum_{j=1}^5 J_j^U = \max_{w_{\cdot}^U} \sum_{j=1}^5 E \left\{ \int_{T_{j-1}^U}^{T_j^U} e^{-rt} NB_j^U dt \right\} \\ &= \max_{w_{\cdot}^U} \sum_{j=1}^5 E \left\{ \int_{T_{j-1}^U}^{T_j^U} e^{-rt} \sum_{i=j}^5 [SB_i^U(w_{it}^U) - TC^U(W_{jt}^U, w_{it}^U)] dt \right\} \\ &= \max_{w_{\cdot}^U} \sum_{j=1}^5 E \left\{ \int_{T_{j-1}^U}^{T_j^U} e^{-rt} \sum_{i=j}^5 \left[\frac{a_i^U}{b_i^U} w_{it}^U - \frac{1}{2b_i^U} \cdot (w_{it}^U)^2 - (k_2^U - k_1^U W_{jt}^U) w_{it}^U \right] dt \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where J_j^U stands for the upstream area's net social benefit of the j -th exit stage, $j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, and

$w_{\cdot}^U = (w_{j\cdot}^U, \dots, w_{5\cdot}^U)$ is the respective sectorial water extraction vector process for the upstream area, subject to the river basin annual renewable water resource equation of (2) and the upstream area water resources (state) equation of (3).

An explicit solution of this stochastic control problem via a decoupling method for forward-backward stochastic differential equations (FBSDEs) is analytically derived in Appendix 2.

Downstream Case

On the other hand, the downstream area water consumption depends on the inflow from the upstream area, and the runoff generated within the area's share of the water stock in the downstream area. Based on the given availability of water, the downstream area maximizes its NB per exit stage (j,k) quantified as follows:

$$NB_{jk}^D = \sum_{l=k}^5 SB_l^D(w_{jl}^D) - \sum_{l=k}^5 TC^D(S_{jk}^D, w_{jl}^D), \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \quad (13)$$

Hence, putting together (8), (10) and (13), the downstream area maximization problem is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 J^D &= \max_{\mathbf{w}^D} \sum_{k=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 J_{jk}^D = \max_{\mathbf{w}^D} \sum_{k=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 E \left\{ \int_{\{T_{j-1}^U \leq t < T_j^U\} \cap \{T_{k-1}^D \leq t < T_k^D\}} e^{-rt} NB_{jk}^D dt \right\} \\
 &= \max_{\mathbf{w}^D} \sum_{k=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 E \left\{ \int_{\{T_{j-1}^U \leq t < T_j^U\} \cap \{T_{k-1}^D \leq t < T_k^D\}} e^{-rt} \left[\sum_{l=k}^5 SB_l^D(w_{lt}^D) - \sum_{l=k}^5 TC^D(S_{jkt}, w_{lt}^D) \right] dt \right\} \\
 &= \max_{\mathbf{w}^D} \sum_{k=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 E \left\{ \int_{\{T_{j-1}^U \leq t < T_j^U\} \cap \{T_{k-1}^D \leq t < T_k^D\}} e^{-rt} \left[\sum_{l=k}^5 \left(\frac{a_l^D}{b_l^D} w_{jlt}^D - \frac{1}{2b_l^D} \cdot (w_{jlt}^D)^2 \right) - (k_2^D - k_1^D S_{jkt}) \sum_{l=k}^5 w_{jlt}^D \right] dt \right\},
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where J_{jk}^D represents the downstream area's net social benefit of the (j, k) -th exit stage, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, and $\mathbf{w}^D = (w_{j1}^D, \dots, w_{j5}^D)$ is the respective sectorial water extraction vector process for the downstream area, subject to the river basin annual renewable water resource equation of (2), the upstream area water resources equation of (3), the runoff flow equation of (4), the stock of water (state variable) in the downstream area equation of (5) and the outflow equation of (6). For an analytical solution of this stochastic optimization problem we refer the reader to Appendix 2.

2.2.2 Cooperative Approach

In this section, we present the model of the inter-sectoral water sharing strategy between the upstream and downstream area in a cooperative setting. In particular, the downstream area offers a discounted price for hydropower exports to the upstream area, in exchange for greater trans-boundary water flow that results in a higher water reserve accumulation and sequentially in a higher production of hydropower. In what follows, we utilize a differential Stackelberg "leader-follower" game to determine the inter-sector optimal water allocation between the upstream and downstream area. The upstream area represents the *leader* and applies his strategy first, *a priori* knowing that the *follower* downstream area observes its actions and *a posteriori* moves accordingly. First, we find the solution to the follower's problem of maximizing his payoff function, and then, using the follower's reaction strategy, we maximize the leader's objective function.

Because all the model coefficients are deterministic functions of time, we assume that the respective areas use *Markovian perfect strategies*. These strategies are decision rules that dictate optimal action of the respective players, conditional on the current values of the state variables (upstream level of water resources, level of water stock reserves downstream, etc), that summarize the latest available information of the dynamic system. The Markovian perfect strategies determine a *sub-game perfect equilibrium* and define an *equilibrium set of decisions* dependent on previous actions.

Downstream Case

Given the announced intersectoral water abstraction policy $\mathbf{w}^U = (w_{j1}^U, \dots, w_{j5}^U)$ per (j, k) -th exit stage from the upstream area (leader), the downstream area (follower) is faced with an optimal water management problem as in the non-cooperative case, i.e., maximize (14) subject to the state equations (2) - (6). For every $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, the (j, k) -th exit stage Hamiltonian of the system is also given by (48), whose necessary optimality conditions (49) and (50) result in the optimal water allocation path of (51) and in the FBSDEs system (52) which will constitute a state system for the upstream area as well.

Upstream Case

The upstream area (leader) receives now hydropower benefits from the downstream area (follower) denoted by the linear function of water stock S_{ik} per (j, k) -th exit stage:

$$F^U(S_{jk}) = \eta_1^U S_{jk} + \eta_2^U, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (15)$$

where $\eta_1^U > 0$, $\eta_2^U \in \sim$, are constants, and its NB function is given by

$$NB_{jk}^U = \sum_{i=j}^5 SB_i^U(w_i^U) + F^U(S_{jk}) - \sum_{i=j}^5 TC^U(W_j^U, w_i^U), \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \quad (16)$$

Therefore, the upstream area, anticipating the downstream area's optimal response as analysed in the previous case, chooses the optimal water abstraction vector process $w^U = (w_{jk^*}^U, \dots, w_{5k^*}^U)$ per (j, k) -th exit stage under cooperation by solving the following maximization problem, imposed by (8), (9), (15) and (16):

$$\begin{aligned} J^U &= \max_{w^U} \sum_{j=1}^5 \sum_{k=1}^5 J_{jk}^U = \max_{w^U} \sum_{j=1}^5 \sum_{k=1}^5 E \left\{ \int_{\{T_{j-1}^U \leq t \leq T_j^U\} \cap \{T_{k-1}^D \leq t \leq T_k^D\}} e^{-rt} NB_{jk}^U dt \right\} \\ &= \max_{w^U} \sum_{j=1}^5 \sum_{k=1}^5 E \left\{ \int_{\{T_{j-1}^U \leq t \leq T_j^U\} \cap \{T_{k-1}^D \leq t \leq T_k^D\}} e^{-rt} \left[\sum_{i=j}^5 SB_i^U(w_{ikt}^U) + F_{jk}^U(S_{jkt}) - \sum_{i=j}^5 TC^U(W_{jt}^U, w_{ikt}^U) \right] dt \right\} \\ &= \max_{w^U} \sum_{j=1}^5 \sum_{k=1}^5 E \left\{ \int_{\{T_{j-1}^U \leq t \leq T_j^U\} \cap \{T_{k-1}^D \leq t \leq T_k^D\}} e^{-rt} \left[\sum_{i=j}^5 \left(\frac{a_i^U}{b_i^U} w_{ikt}^U - \frac{1}{2b_i^U} \cdot (w_{ikt}^U)^2 \right) + \eta_1^U S_{jkt} + \eta_2^U - (k_2^U - k_1^U W_{jt}^U) \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{ikt}^U \right] dt \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

subject to the river basin annual renewable water resource equation of (2), the upstream area water resources (state) equation of (3), the runoff flow equation of (4), the outflow equation of (6), and the Hamiltonian FBSDEs state system of the downstream area (52). In Appendix 2 one can find an explicit solution of this stochastic maximization problem.

3 ESTIMATION OF THE PRODUCTION FUNCTIONS OF THE ECONOMIC MODEL BY SECTOR

In this section, we aim to estimate the main components of our model using a stochastic frontier model and a quadratic production function, the form of which remains unknown. In order to identify the production function, we need to estimate the sample coefficients of its main variables, which in order to be a good reflection of their real values, they need to be unbiased, consistent and efficient. However, the major challenge we faced in this exercise was the existence of endogeneity problems, due to correlation of the explanatory variables, such as capital or labour, with the error term, due to three main reasons explained below. The magnitude of this problem can be seen in the estimations of the coefficients of the model, the expected values of which will not be equal to their real values (biased), as for example in case of omitted variable bias, there will be another variable contained in the error term, i.e. health or age, influencing both labour and production levels. Hence, the upcoming results of the regression cannot be trusted, and they may lead to inaccurate analysis.

However, the most widely used approaches in order to tackle endogeneity problem of using investment by *Olley and Pakes* (1996) or intermediate inputs as a proxy by *Levinsohn and Petrin* (2003) have been both subject to criticism for lack of relevant instruments and collinearity problems. Therefore, in this paper we will present an extension of the model proposed by *Gandhi et al.* (2017), where those limitations are attacked, and we will introduce technical inefficiency in production and also allow for autocorrelation TFP. Using the Copula approach in order to estimate non-

parametrically the dependence between the endogenous regressors and the composed error terms directly via a copula function which does not require the use of instruments, we are able to estimate the marginal product function of our mathematical model without being subject to biases. As explained in section 2, the marginal product function is the inverse demand function of water use from which we can calculate the net social benefits of each country and the lake depletion time. Having estimated both of those values, we will be able to determine the optimal path for water use *ceteris paribus* (with all the other parameters being collapsed to their means).

3.1 MATHEMATICAL AND STATISTICAL MODELS

In this context, the key economic drivers influencing pressures and water uses need to be determined including general socio-economic indicators such as income and employment, and environmental indicators related to ecosystem services such as land use, emissions, etc. These economic drivers will need to be accounted for in a dynamic perspective, i.e., to determine how these are likely to evolve over time. The final component of the economic characterization of water in a region is the application of appropriate methodologies to assess sector-specific water demand. This involves deriving the marginal contribution of water in consumption and production of each sector, the maximum willingness to pay for water and the price of the water per sector, concluding with the demand curve from which we obtain the Social Benefit (cf. Section 2).

The production of marketed goods requires both man-made input as labour and machinery, as well as land and ecosystem-based processes. Not accounting for this can lead to the criticism that the valuation is exaggerating ecosystem service values. A method which is designed to value indirect use values is the production function approach (PFA). Production theory is the study of production or the economic process of producing outputs from the inputs, i.e. a process of combining various material inputs and immaterial inputs (plans, know-how) in order to make something for consumption (the output). More accurately, production function is a mathematical equation representing the “maximum” output that can be obtained from any fixed and specific set of production inputs at a certain level of technology. Thus, the outcome is considered as the dependent variable and production inputs are regarded as independent variables. Accordingly, a *production function* is the relationship that describes how inputs like Capital, Labour and Natural Resource Capital are transformed into output (see Figure 3). Mathematically, we estimate each sector’s $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, specific production function via Gross Value Added (GVA) as:

$$GVA (\text{sector } i) = F(\text{Technological Capital Input}; \text{Labour Input}; \text{Natural Capital Input}) \quad (18)$$

Figure 3 - Production Function Description

One very simple example of a production function is when F is a linear function of the input. More precisely, if F is a *linear function* that relates GVA with only the amount of Capital (C) and the amount of Labour (L) that are used in production, i.e.,

$$GVA = aC + bL + c, \tag{19}$$

where a, b, c are parameters that are determined empirically, then one unit of output (GVA) of a sector can be produced for every unit of Capital or Labour it employs. This form of production function yields that the amount of output will increase proportionally to any increase in the amount of inputs. Another common production function is the *Cobb-Douglas production function*, which has the form

$$GVA = aC^b L^c, \tag{20}$$

where a, b, c are parameters that are determined empirically. For example, if $b = c = 1/2$ then this describes the fact that the production requires the least total number of inputs when the combination of inputs is relatively equal. More specifically, a sector could produce 25 units of output (GVA) using 25 units of capital and 25 of labour, or it could produce the same 25 units of output with 125 units of labour and only one unit of capital. In the contrary, the *Leontief production function* applies to situations in which inputs must be used in fixed proportions; starting from those proportions, if usage of one input is increased without another being increased, output will not change. This production function has the form

$$GVA = \min(aK, bL), \tag{21}$$

where a, b are parameters that are determined empirically. All the above forms of productions function can be extended in functions with more than two input arguments and their economic description will be relevant with the above.

All the above production functions, as real functions, can be plotted on a graph. A typical quadratic production function is of the form that we will use in our analysis and its graph is demonstrated in the following diagram under the assumption of a single variable input.

Figure 4 - Technical Efficiency and Inefficiency

Figure 4 depicts the possibility (i) of getting the *maximum* output by a given combination of input and on the contrary (ii) of reducing output from what is technologically possible by the inefficient

management. Thus, points on or below the production function make up the production set the set of technically *feasible* combinations of inputs and outputs, and points such as *A* and *B* in the production set are technically inefficient (getting less output from its input than it could). Finally, points on the boundary of the production set (as *C* and *D*) are technically efficient, which means that it is produced as much output as it possibly can be given by the amount of input. For further information about the production function see *Brems (1968), Moroney (1967), Shephard (1970) and Saari (2006 and 2011)*.

Additionally, the existence of natural capital is a necessity in our model due to our final need of the economic characterization of water resource in the region under investigation. Natural capital is the world's stock of natural resources, which includes geology, soils, air, water and all living organisms. It is an extension of the economic notion of capital (resources which enable the production of more resources) to goods and services provided by the natural environment. Some natural capital assets provide people with free goods and services, often called ecosystem services. Two of these (clean water and fertile soil) underpin our economy and society and make human life possible. Ecosystem services can be provided into four main categories: (i) provisioning services, i.e. products obtained from ecosystems, (ii) regulating services, i.e. benefits arising from the regulation of ecosystem processes and functions, (iii) habitat services, i.e. services that are supportive for the production of all other ecosystem services, (iv) cultural services, i.e. benefits for humans such as spiritual enrichment, cognitive development, recreation and education. Table 6 contains examples of ecosystem services across the four main categories.

Table 6 – Main types of Ecosystem Services.

Provisioning services	Food (e.g. fish, fruit)
	Water (e.gr for drinking, cooling)
	Raw material (e.g. Fiber, timber)
	Genetic resources (e.g. For crop-improvement and medical purposes)
	Medical resources (e.g. Biochemical products)
	Ornamental resources
Regulating services	Air quality regulation
	Climate regulation
	Moderation of extreme events
	Regulation of water flows
	Waste treatment
	Erosion prevention
	Maintenance of soil fertility
	Pollination
Biological control	
Habitat services	Maintenance of life cycles of migratory species
	Maintenance of genetic diversity
Cultural and amenity services	Aesthetic information
	Opportunities for recreation and tourism
	Inspiration for culture, art and design
	Spiritual experience
	Information for cognitive development

Source: adapted from *De Groot et al., (2002)*.

The challenges involved in the application of production function approach are that data on the relationships between the services (regulation and provision services) and on other non-environmental inputs are often difficult to obtain. In our case we need for each *Core Water-*

Dependent Economic Sector $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, to gather data on Natural Capital using Environmental Indices as approximations of both quality and quantity. Thus, at first, we need to define all the relative indices that we will use per sector (see further details in Subsection 3.2), according to the description of the 4 main ecosystem services categories of the above table.

3.2 DATA COLLECTION

The preparation of this report demanded the collection of socioeconomic information from each of the 8 riparian countries of the ZRB. As explained in the preceding section, we needed data on Technological Capital, Labour and Natural Capital collected from national accounts. Furthermore, data should be time series (over time), but also cross sections of regional data panel data econometrics that are more robust. Several strands of data collection work including meetings with other partners – UNZA, UEM, Ku Leuven, ETH – were ongoing under Subtasks 2.1.7 and 2.1.8, in order to feed into work taking place within Task 4.6.

Apart from this collaboration, ICRE8 team managed to collect all the necessary information needed for the statistical analysis, using many datasets from many sources such as:

- Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations (FAOSTAT, AQUASTAT),
- ILO (International LABOUR Organization),
- The World Bank data,
- The World Bank Group: Climate Change Knowledge Portal For Development Practitioners and Policy Makers,
- The United Nations Statistics Division,
- Unesco World Heritage list,
- OpenDataSoft,
- Environment & Climate Change Data Portal,

which are commonly used databases and well known for their accuracy.

Furthermore, due to our necessity to obtain information for each sector, we used Input -Output (IO) tables that we had in our disposal from the **Eora multi-region IO table** (MRIO) database. The MRIO database provides a time series of high resolution IO tables with matching environmental and social satellite accounts for 187 countries (to 190 in some datasets). The Eora MRIO features:

- 187 individual countries represented by a total of 15,909 sectors,
- continuous coverage for the period 1990-2012,
- 35 types of environmental indicators covering air pollution, energy use, greenhouse gas emissions, water use, land occupation, N and P emissions, 172 crops, Human Appropriation of Net Primary Productivity,
- high-resolution heterogeneous classification, or 26-sector harmonized classification,
- raw data drawn from the UN's System of National Accounts and COMTRADE databases, Eurostat, IDE/JETRO, and numerous national agencies,
- distinction between basic prices and purchasers' prices through 5 mark-ups, and
- reliability statistics (estimates of standard deviation) for all results.

Our main data collection was done according to these IO tables. In our case we have 2 IO tables, each for the time period of 2000-2013 for the 8 countries under investigation. These tables have 2946 rows and columns with massive information each, per sector.

Table 10 in Appendix 1 includes all indices used for the estimation of the production functions from Section 2, their description and the source of the data. The indices representing the ecosystem services were constructed from measures of natural resources and landscapes. As each ecosystem service may relate to several resources and landscapes, and each natural resource may provide various ecosystem services, we can only infer the joint value of ecosystem services from those variables. Thus, for each sector we chose common variables which describe the main types of the ecosystem services, according to their description in Table 10 such as raw materials, forest, natural-cultural-mixed heritage sites, biodiversity and habitats, terrestrial protected areas, water

quality, annual freshwater withdrawals, land uses, emissions (CO₂ and NO₂) and floods/droughts events.

3.3 ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS – RESULTS

Estimation of production functions has always been a difficult exercise. The reason is that inputs like capital and labour are correlated with the error term for at least three reasons. First, decisions about *inputs* depend on overall productivity. The second source is measurement errors in the right-hand-side variables. The third source is from profit maximization, i.e., the firms choose inputs and output simultaneously to maximize profit.

Olley and Pakes (1996) use investment as a proxy for such unobservable shocks, while *Levinsohn and Petrin* (2003) use intermediate inputs as a better proxy that may respond more smoothly to unobserved productivity shocks. Both approaches which are widely used in the literature have been subject to criticism. In this approach, we will present a new estimation method of firm-level productivity dealing with the endogeneity problem which is pervasive in production function estimation.

Neither *Olley and Pakes* (1996) nor while *Levinsohn and Petrin* (2003) are devoid of problems (see *Gandhi et al.*, 2017; *Ackerberg, et al.*, 2015; *Doralzeski and Jaumendreu*, 2013). *Gandhi et al.* (2017) show that, besides the collinearity problem pointed out by *Ackerberg et al.* (2015), both the *Olley and Pakes* (1996) and *Levinsohn and Petrin* (2003) estimators suffer from the lack of relevant instruments for the endogenous inputs in the model. *Ackerberg et al.* (2006) have shown that the *Olley and Pakes* (1996) and *Levinsohn and Petrin* (2003) approaches to estimating TFP have a problem of collinearity if labour and intermediate inputs depend on TFP just like investment. *Gandhi et al.* (2017) also propose a nonparametric treatment of the production function. There could also be non-linearity due to capital-labour substitution in the sense that when labour input is costly, capital could be substituted to replace labour, making the relationship endogenous and non-linear.

In a substantive extension of the model, we introduce technical inefficiency in production and we allow for autocorrelated TFP. Bayesian analysis is performed using a Sequential Monte Carlo / Particle-Filtering approach. For more details see Appendix 3.

Consider the following stochastic frontier model:

$$y_{it} = \varphi(x_{it}, z_{it}; \beta) + v_{it} - u_{it}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad t = 1, \dots, T \quad (22)$$

where y_{it} is the output of firm i and date t , $\varphi(\cdot)$ is an unknown functional form, z_{it} is a $p \times 1$ vector of exogenous inputs, x_{it} is a $p \times 1$ vector of endogenous inputs, β is a $d \times 1$ vector of unknown parameters, v_{it} is a symmetric random error, u_{it} is the one-sided random disturbance representing technical inefficiency. We assume that z_{it} is uncorrelated with v_{it} and u_{it} but x_{it} is allowed to be correlated with v_{it} and possibly with u_{it} . This, of course, generates an endogeneity problem. We also assume that u_{it} and v_{it} are independent and leave the form of u_{it} unrestricted. The model can be easily extended to the case of exogenous (environmental) variables are included in the distribution of technical inefficiency (see for example, *Battese and Coelli*, 1995 and *Caudill et al.*, 1995).

3.3.1 Econometric Model

To address the endogeneity problem, we propose an approach which does not require the use of instrumental variables, which can often be weak or unreliable, is based on copula functions to determine the joint distribution of the endogenous regressors and the composed errors that effectively capture the dependency between them.

We first assume that $v_{it} \sim i.i.d. N(0, \sigma_v^2)$ and $u_{it} \sim i.i.d. |N(0, \sigma_u^2)|$. Then the density of

$\varepsilon_{it} = v_{it} - u_{it} = y_{it} - \varphi(x_{it}, z_{it}; \beta)$ is given by:

$$g(\varepsilon_{it}) = \int_0^{\infty} f_v(\varepsilon_{it} + u_{it}) f_u(u_{it}) du_{it} = \frac{2}{\sigma} \varphi\left(\frac{\varepsilon_{it}}{\sigma}\right) \Phi\left(-\frac{\lambda \varepsilon_{it}}{\sigma}\right) \quad (23)$$

where $\sigma^2 = \sigma_v^2 + \sigma_u^2$, $\lambda = \sigma_u / \sigma_v$, $\varphi(\cdot)$ and $\Phi(\cdot)$ are the probability density function and cumulative distribution function of a standard normal random variable, respectively. To avoid the non-negativity restrictions we make use of the following transformation: $\bar{\lambda} = \log(\lambda)$ and $\bar{\sigma}^2 = \log(\sigma^2)$. Let $\theta = (\beta', \bar{\lambda}, \bar{\sigma}^2)'$ then it follows that the conditional pdf of y given x and z is

$$f(y_{it} | x_{it}, z_{it}) = \frac{2}{\bar{\sigma}} \varphi\left(\frac{y_{it} - \varphi(x_{it}, z_{it}; \beta)}{\bar{\sigma}}\right) \Phi\left(-\frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\bar{\sigma}} (y_{it} - \varphi(x_{it}, z_{it}; \beta))\right) \quad (24)$$

and conditional log-likelihood is then given by

$$\log L(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=0}^T \log f(y_{it}; \theta | x, z). \quad (25)$$

Copula Approach

In this subsection, we propose an approach that models the dependence between the endogenous regressors and the composed error terms directly via a copula function which **does not require the use of instruments**. We do not introduce dynamic latent productivity which is left for the local likelihood estimation. For rigorous treatment on copulas, see for example *Nelsen (2006)*. We take the function $\varphi(\cdot)$ as given and provide its construction in subsection of the local likelihood estimation.

To this end, let $F(x_1, \dots, x_p, \varepsilon)$ be the joint distribution of (x_1, \dots, x_p) and ε_i . Now since the information contained in the correlation between (x_1, \dots, x_p) and ε_i is also contained in its joint distribution, and if this is known to belong to a class of parametric density, then consistent estimates of the model parameters can be obtained by simply maximizing the log-likelihood function derived from $F(x_1, \dots, x_p, \varepsilon)$. Thus, there is no need for resorting to instruments nor to consistently estimate the parameters of the model.

In practice, however, $F(x_1, \dots, x_p, \varepsilon)$ is typically unknown. To address this problem, we follow *Park and Gupta (2012)* and suggest a copula approach to determine this joint density. The copula essentially captures the dependence in the joint distribution of the endogenous regressors and the composed errors. For exposition purpose, suppose we have a joint distribution of $(x_1, \dots, x_p, \varepsilon)$ with joint density $f(x_1, \dots, x_p, \varepsilon)$, and let $f_j(x_j)$, $F_j(x_j)$, for $j = 1, \dots, p$, $g(\varepsilon)$ and $G(\varepsilon)$ denote the marginal density and CDF of x_j and ε , respectively. Also let C denotes the ‘‘copula function’’ defined for $(\xi_1, \dots, \xi_{p+1}) \in [0, 1]^{p+1}$ by

$$C(\xi_1, \dots, \xi_{p+1}) = P(F_1(x_1) \leq \xi_1, \dots, F_p(x_p) \leq \xi_p, G(\varepsilon) \leq \xi_{p+1})$$

so that the copula function is itself a CDF. Moreover, since $F_j(x_j)$ and $G(\cdot)$ are marginal distribution function, each component $U_j = F_j(x_j)$ and $U_\varepsilon = G(\varepsilon)$ has a uniform marginal distribution (see for example *Li and Racine, 2007* in Theorem A.2). Let $c(\xi_1, \dots, \xi_p)$ denotes the pdf associated with $C(\xi_1, \dots, \xi_p)$, then by Sklar's theorem (*Sklar, 1959*), we have

$$f(x_1, \dots, x_p, \varepsilon) = c(F_1(x_1), \dots, F_p(x_p), G(\varepsilon)) g(\varepsilon) \prod_{j=1}^p f_j(x_j). \quad (26)$$

Thus, equation (24) here shows that the copula function completely characterizes the dependence structure of $(x_1, \dots, x_p, \varepsilon)$, and $c(\xi_1, \dots, \xi_p) = 1$ if and only if $(x_1, \dots, x_p, \varepsilon)$ are independent of each other.

To obtain the joint density in (24), we need to specify the copula function. One commonly used copula function is the Gaussian copula. Other copula functions such as Frank, Plackett, Clayton, and Farlie-Gumbel-Morgenstern can also be used. The Gaussian copula is generally robust for most application (Song, 2000) and has many desirable properties (Danaher and Smith, 2011). Let $\Phi_{\Sigma, p+1}$ denote a $(p+1)$ -dimensional CDF with zero mean and correlation matrix Σ . Then the $(p+1)$ -dimensional CDF with correlation matrix Σ is given by

$$C(w; \Sigma) = \Phi_{\Sigma, p+1} \left(\Phi^{-1}(U_1), \dots, \Phi^{-1}(U_p), \Phi^{-1}(U_\varepsilon) \right)$$

Where $w = (U_1, \dots, U_p, U_\varepsilon) = (F_1(x_1), \dots, F_p(x_p), G(\varepsilon))$. The copula density is

$$c(w; \Sigma) = (\det(\Sigma))^{-1/2} \times \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} \left(\Phi^{-1}(U_1), \dots, \Phi^{-1}(U_p), \Phi^{-1}(U_\varepsilon) \right)' \left(\Sigma^{-1} - I_{p+1} \right) \left(\Phi^{-1}(U_1), \dots, \Phi^{-1}(U_p), \Phi^{-1}(U_\varepsilon) \right) \right\}. \quad (27)$$

The log-likelihood function corresponding to (24) is:

$$\log L(\theta, \Sigma) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T \left\{ \ln c(F_1(x_{1,it}), \dots, F_p(x_{p,it}), G(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta); \Sigma) + \sum_{j=1}^p \ln f_j(x_{j,it}) + \ln g(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta) \right\}, \quad (28)$$

where $\theta = (\beta', \bar{\lambda}, \bar{\sigma}^2)'$ and the form of $c(\cdot)$ is given in (25). Notice that the first term in the summation in (28) is derived from the copula density and this term reflects the dependence between the endogenous variables and the composed errors. In addition, since the marginal density $f_j(x_j)$ does not contain any parameters of interest, the second term in the summation in (28) can be dropped from the log-likelihood function. Finally, it is clear from (26) that if there is no endogeneity problem, (28) collapses to the log-likelihood function of the standard stochastic frontier models.

By maximizing the log-likelihood function in (26), consistent estimates of (θ, Σ) can be obtained, and this can be done as we describe below.

Estimation of $F_j(x_j)$, $j=1, \dots, p$ and $G(\varepsilon; \theta)$.

Since $F_j(x_{ji})$ are unknown and we have an observed sample of x_{ji} , $j=1, \dots, p$; $i=1, \dots, n$; in the first step, we can estimate $F_j(x_{ji})$ by

$$\tilde{F}_{nj} = \frac{1}{nT+1} \sum_{i=1}^n 1(x_{j,it} \leq x_{0j}), \quad j=1, \dots, p, \quad (29)$$

where $1(\cdot)$ is an indicator function. Note that in (29), we have used the rescaling factor $1/(nT+1)$ rather than $1/nT$ to avoid difficulties arising from the potential unboundedness of the $\ln c(F_1(x_{1,it}), \dots, F_p(x_{p,it}), G(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta); \Sigma)$ as some of the $F_j(x_j)$ tend to one. To estimate $G(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta)$, note that its density $g(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta)$ is given in (23) and by definition, $G(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta) = \int_{-\infty}^{\varepsilon_{it}} g(s; \theta) ds$, thus $G(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta)$ can be estimated using numerical integration, and let $\tilde{G}(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta)$ denotes the estimator of $G(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta)$.

Maximization of the log-likelihood function

Maximization of the log-likelihood function in (26) with $F_j(x_j)$ and $G(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta)$ are replaced by their estimates $\tilde{F}_j(x_j)$ and $\tilde{G}(\varepsilon_{it}; \theta)$, respectively, i.e.,

$$(\hat{\theta}, \hat{\Sigma}) = \arg \max_{\theta \in \Theta, \Sigma} \sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ \ln c(\tilde{F}_1(x_{1i}), \dots, \tilde{F}_p(x_{pi}), \tilde{G}(\varepsilon_i; \theta); \Sigma) + \ln g(\varepsilon_i; \theta) \right\} \quad (30)$$

Estimating Technical Inefficiency:

Once the parameters have been estimated, the ultimate goal is to predict the values of the technical inefficiency term u_i , and this can be calculated based on *Jondrow et al.* (1982):

$$\hat{u}_{it} = \hat{E}(u_{it} | \varepsilon_{it}) = \frac{\hat{\sigma}\hat{\lambda}}{1 + \hat{\lambda}^2} \left[\frac{\varphi(\hat{\lambda}\hat{\varepsilon}_{it} / \hat{\sigma})}{1 - \Phi(\hat{\lambda}\hat{\varepsilon}_{it} / \hat{\sigma})} - \frac{\hat{\lambda}\hat{\varepsilon}_{it}}{\hat{\sigma}} \right], \quad (31)$$

where $\hat{\varepsilon}_{it} = y_{it} - \varphi(x_{it}, z_{it}; \hat{\beta})$ and $\hat{\beta}$, $\hat{\lambda}$ and $\hat{\sigma}^2$ are the parameter estimates obtained from the approach discussed above.

Local Likelihood Estimation

The functional form $\varphi(x_{it}, z_{it}; \beta)$ was left unspecified so far. Of course, any parametric form can be used but here we focus on non-parametric estimation by the local likelihood method. We use the simpler notation $\varphi(x_{it}; \beta)$ as the extension to the case of exogenous covariates is straightforward. Since we have a multivariate covariate we use the method of local linear estimation. This means that all parameters of the model become functions of x , and they are denoted by $\theta(x)$. We denote the conditional density of y given x by $p(y|x) = g(y; \theta(x))$, where $\theta(x) \in \sim^k$ is unknown and we define $q(y; \theta(x)) = \log g(y; \theta(x))$. For example, a standard frontier would take the form:

$$y_{it} = m(x_{it}) + v_{it} - u_{it}, \quad (32)$$

where $v_{it} | x_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2(x_{it}))$, $u_{it} | x_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2(x_{it}))$. Then we have

$$\theta(x) = \left[m(x), \sigma_v^2(x), \sigma_u^2(x) \right]'$$

Our fundamental departure from the standard model is the **introduction of productivity**:

$$y_{it} = m(x_{it}, z_{it}) + v_{it} + \omega_{it} - u_{it}, \quad (33)$$

where the productivity process is as follows:

$$\omega_{it} | x_{it}, \omega_{i,t-1} \sim N\left(r(\omega_{i,t-1}, x_{it}, z_{it})_{\omega}, (\omega_{i,t-1}, x_{it}, z_{it})\right).$$

In this specification, $r(\omega_{i,t-1}, x_{it}, z_{it})$ is a non-parametric productivity mean process, and $\sigma_{\omega}^2(\omega_{i,t-1}, x_{it}, z_{it})$ is the variance. For ease in notation we omit explicit dependence on z and we continue to denote $\theta(x) \in \sim^k$ with

$$\theta(x) = \left[m(x), r(\omega_{-1}, x), \sigma_v^2(x), \sigma_u^2(x), \sigma_{\omega}^2(\omega_{-1}, x) \right]'$$

where ω_{-1} denotes the lagged value of productivity. As productivity is latent special problems are introduced into the analysis.

There is a multivariate kernel which satisfies:

$$\int K(u) du = 1, \quad \int uu'K(u) du = \mu_2 I_d.$$

To fix notation, we start with the analysis of the simpler model in (32). The conditional local linear log-likelihood is given by¹

$$\log L(\theta_o, \Theta_1) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T q(y_{it}, \theta_o + \Theta_1(x_{it} - x)) K_H(x_{it} - x), \quad (34)$$

where θ_o, Θ_1 is a vector ($k \times 1$) and matrix ($k \times d$) respectively, H is a bandwidth matrix which is symmetric, positive definite and $K_H(u) = |H|^{-1} K(H^{-1}u)$. We choose a multivariate product kernel so that $K(u) = \prod_{j=1}^d K_j(u_j)$ in which case

$$\int uu'K(u)du = \left(\int u_1^2 K_1(u_1) du_1 \right) I_d.$$

The local linear estimator is $\hat{\theta}(x) = \hat{\theta}_o(x)$ where $\hat{\theta}_o(x)$ and $\hat{\Theta}_1(x)$ maximize the log-likelihood $L(\theta_o, \Theta_1)$ with respect to θ_o, Θ_1 . Computational details are in *Kumbhakar et al. (2007)*, (Sections 3.1 and 3.2) and we follow this paper closely.

For the model with latent productivity ω_{it} as in (33) the likelihood function is

$$L(\theta_o, \Theta_1) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left\{ \prod_{i=1}^n \prod_{t=1}^T g(y_{it}, \omega_{it}, \theta_o + \Theta_1(\Lambda_{it} - \Lambda)) \cdot K_H(\Lambda_{it} - \Lambda) \right\} d\omega, \quad (35)$$

where $\Lambda_{it} = [x'_{it}, \omega_{i,t-1}]'$, $\Lambda = [x', \omega_{-1}]'$, and

$$g(y, \omega; \theta(\Lambda)) = \frac{2}{\sigma(x)} \varphi\left(\frac{y_{it} - \varphi(x_{it}; \beta(x)) - \omega_{it}}{\sigma(x)}\right) \Phi\left(-\frac{\lambda(x)}{\sigma_v(x)}(y - \varphi(x_{it}; \beta(x))) - \omega_{it}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma_\omega(x, \omega_{-1})} \varphi\left(\frac{\omega_{it} - r(x_{it}, \omega_{i,t-1}; \gamma(x, \omega_{-1}))}{\sigma_\omega(x, \omega_{-1})}\right). \quad (36)$$

Moreover, $\gamma(x, \omega_{-1})$ denotes the localized parameters in the $r(\cdot)$ function in (33). For ease in notation we define $\theta(x, \omega_{-1}) = [\beta(x)', \gamma(x, \omega_{-1})']' \in \sim^k$.

In (35) there is an nT – dimensional integral which we cannot evaluate analytically, which is obvious from the definition of (36). The computation relies in two steps.

- **Step 1:** Integrate out $\{\omega_{it}\}$ from (14) using a Sequential Monte Carlo algorithm (*Pitt and Shephard, 1997*).
- **Step 2:** Maximize the resulting expression using numerical optimization techniques.

For reasons of computational convenience and without sacrificing generality we assume

$$\omega_{it} = \rho\omega_{i,t-1} + \xi_{it}, \quad \{\xi_{it}\} \sim i.i.d. N(0, \sigma_\xi^2). \quad (37)$$

We will still need the SMC algorithm in Step 1. For the Sequential Monte Carlo algorithm we use 10^6 particles per likelihood evaluation and a standard conjugate gradients algorithm for maximization. Our results were insensitive to using 10^5 or 10^7 particles per likelihood evaluation.

¹ In fact, we include z_{it} in the kernel functions because, in this instance, they represent important environmental variables that help in modelling heterogeneity. For ease in notation we redefine $x = [x', z']'$.

3.3.2. Empirical Results

In this section we perform a simple nonparametric estimation of the production function per sector in each country based on the econometric model described in Subsection 3.3.1. Our dataset includes 16 observations for each sector of these countries from 2000 to 2015. This methodology takes into account the regional differences in productivity between the upstream and downstream countries, which is a necessary categorization of these countries due to the formulation of the water resources management problem investigated in Section 1.2.

Data preparation is a critical first step for building high performance predictive models. At first, we convert all the monetary variables to constant 2010 prices, since the prices we had available for each year of our period could not be used for comparisons thanks to inflation effects. Additionally, we perform all the necessary transformations of the variables to end up either with the same units of measurement or with suitably scaled data, so as to standardize predictions subject to the units of the regression coefficients. The results of the nonparametric estimation are reported in Table 7 and Table 8. Input and output variables were transformed to their corresponding log values and were normalized by their respective sample means. From the estimated production function for each of the countries we can easily obtain their corresponding marginal product function, which is connected with the water use input variable via the relationship:

$$\text{Marginal product} = \alpha + \beta \cdot \text{water use} \quad (38)$$

Both coefficients for each country turn out to have the expected signs. As explained at section 2.2, inverse demand function is given by relationship (7) and it is expected to be equal to the marginal contribution of the water to the output of each sector given by equation (38). Consequently, the derived demand curve for water of the producer is represented at equation (37) showing producer's demand for an input, i.e. the water, as a result of the demand for another related good, i.e. energy.

$$\text{Water use} = a + b \cdot \text{price} \quad (39)$$

where a is the intercept of water demand of each sector and b the price elasticity of water demand.

In order to calculate the price elasticities, we used the formula (62). In alignment with Table 9, it is noticed that all sectors are exceptionally inelastic to a price change for water use, i.e. relatively large changes in price cause very small changes in demanded quantity of water. In particular, Agriculture seems to be perfectly inelastic to any price change, which means that in all countries the demanded quantity will remain stable for any price change and so the price cannot influence the water use. This implies an extremely strong relationship between the input, in this case water, and the corresponding output of each sector such as the seed-producing crops, since the producer lacks alternatives and so values highly the use of water. The elasticities for all countries are presented in Table 9.

$$\text{price elasticity} = \frac{d(\text{water use})}{d(\text{price})} \cdot \frac{\text{price}}{\text{water use}} \quad (40)$$

Finally, the different demand curves, coming from equation (39) for all 5 sectors of the riparian countries, provide us with an ordering of these sectors via their demand function intercepts. Sequential exits from the market are defined by the relative importance of sector-specific demand parameter ratio a , with $a = \alpha/\beta$. As water demand for each of these economic sectors reaches zero sequentially, its price increases revealing so producers' preferences for water use. In all countries, in case of river/lake depletion, agriculture sector should be the last one to exit the market, since it is valuing water use more than any other sector. However, the exit order varies between the countries, with energy sector being the penultimate one to exit the market in most cases (Angola, Botswana, Malawi, Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe) and Residential (Botswana, Namibia and Tanzania) and Tourism sector (Angola, Mozambique and Zimbabwe) leaving first the market in the countries indicated in the parenthesis.

Table 7 - Empirical results: b parameter for each Sector

Sector → Country ↓	<i>Mining</i>	<i>Energy</i>	<i>Tourism</i>	<i>Residential</i>	<i>Agriculture</i>
<i>Angola</i>	-0.0012	-0.0011	-0.0017	-0.0013	-0.0000513
<i>Botswana</i>	-0.0015	-0.0010	-0.0014	-0.0019	-0.0000442
<i>Malawi</i>	-0.0021	-0.0012	-0.0012	-0.0018	-0.0000388
<i>Mozambique</i>	-0.0013	-0.0014	-0.0011	-0.0012	-0.0000313
<i>Namibia</i>	-0.0011	-0.0012	-0.0010	-0.0019	-0.0000300
<i>UR Tanzania</i>	-0.0015	-0.0013	-0.0010	-0.0017	-0.0000212
<i>Zambia</i>	-0.0013	-0.0011	-0.0012	-0.0012	-0.0000366
<i>Zimbabwe</i>	-0.0012	-0.0010	-0.0017	-0.0018	-0.0000477

Table 8 - Empirical results: a parameter for each Sector

Sector → Country ↓	<i>Mining</i>	<i>Energy</i>	<i>Tourism</i>	<i>Residential</i>	<i>Agriculture</i>
<i>Angola</i>	1.70	1.65	1.47	1.82	1.32
<i>Botswana</i>	1.72	1.69	1.60	1.70	1.51
<i>Malawi</i>	1.77	1.81	1.55	1.73	1.33
<i>Mozambique</i>	1.61	1.80	1.20	1.65	1.37
<i>Namibia</i>	1.52	1.82	1.51	1.88	1.34
<i>UR Tanzania</i>	1.66	1.70	1.48	1.43	1.51
<i>Zambia</i>	1.49	1.81	1.53	1.88	1.40
<i>Zimbabwe</i>	1.63	1.77	1.44	1.71	1.55

Table 9 - Price elasticity for each Sector

Sector → Country ↓	<i>Mining</i>	<i>Energy</i>	<i>Tourism</i>	<i>Residential</i>	<i>Agriculture</i>
<i>Angola</i>	-0,111	-0,099	-0,131	-0,129	-0,004
<i>Botswana</i>	-0,139	-0,093	-0,120	-0,170	-0,004
<i>Malawi</i>	-0,195	-0,119	-0,101	-0,165	-0,003
<i>Mozambique</i>	-0,113	-0,136	-0,071	-0,108	-0,002
<i>Namibia</i>	-0,091	-0,119	-0,083	-0,190	-0,002
<i>UR Tanzania</i>	-0,133	-0,120	-0,081	-0,127	-0,002
<i>Zambia</i>	-0,104	-0,109	-0,099	-0,124	-0,003
<i>Zimbabwe</i>	-0,106	-0,097	-0,128	-0,163	-0,004

Figures 5 to 12 illustrate the derived demand for water of each sector in each country. In all cases, the agriculture sector is perfectly inelastic in water use declaring so, an intense connection between water use and crops, which is caused by the existence of large irrigation schemes in the basin. In particular, in Angola, Malawi and Namibia the agriculture sectors seem to value higher the water than in the other countries. Indeed Malawi, where 28% of its GDP is coming from the agriculture sector and which often suffers from extreme weather conditions, such as the El-Niño, causing great draughts in the region, values water more than other countries, which have a more secure access to the water such as Zimbabwe. Moreover, the irrigation levels for Malawi are 80% of the total water use, declaring so, the intense need of the country for water access. However, Zambia, which is also using water mostly for the agriculture sector, does not value as much the water as Malawi, due to its advantage in water resources with 35% of water resources of South Africa located in Zambia.

Figure 5 - Water demand curve of Angola

Figure 6 - Water demand curve of Botswana

Figure 7 - Water demand curve of Malawi

Figure 8 - Water demand of Mozambique

Figure 9 - Water demand curve of Namibia

Figure 10 - Water demand curve of Tanzania

Figure 11 - Water demand curve of Zambia

Figure 12 - Water demand curve of Zimbabwe

Figure 13 illustrates the distributions of water elasticities for each sector for Mozambique. Interestingly, although tourism sector is expected to be slightly less inelastic in comparison with the others, in our example is -0.07, which is lying in the right skew of the curve. However, in economic terms, the elasticities for water demand in each sector do not deviate remarkably, letting so similar behavioural patterns to be observed in each sector in Mozambique. The same pattern is observed in the other countries as well.

Figure 13 - Sampling distributions of water elasticities by sector for Mozambique (downstream)

The constant term which is responsible for the starting point of the demand curve, reveals the willingness to pay (WTP) of the stakeholders in each sector. Indicatively, in Figure 14 are illustrated the sample distributions of the constant term for each sector for Zambia, which has the biggest land share in ZRB. Interestingly, we can see that in most cases the WTP for water use in energy sector is greater than the corresponding one in agriculture and tourism, which implies greater profitability in energy sector. Figure 15 presents the same figures for Malawi, 90% land of which is located within ZRB area. Similarly, Energy sector is valuing higher the water use than the other sectors.

Figure 14 - Sampling distributions of constant terms by sector for Zambia

Figure 15 - Sampling distributions of constant terms by sector for Malawi

Figure 16 presents productivity growth by sector for Malawi, which is the most populated area within ZRB. The most particular case is the multimodal distribution of the Residential sector, which has two distinct peaks, with the most common one being the zero mean growth rate, and the other one 0.03%. Similarly, the mean of all the other sectors was at zero, revealing so lack in developing new technologies and making so production more efficient. These trends can be explained either by lack of technical support and mechanisms or by the significant unskilled employment at the agriculture and services sectors. However, these trends imply a risk for the future of the economy in these areas, since none of the sectors seems to adapt to the new challenges.

3.4 EMPIRICAL ILLUSTRATION

The inverse demand functions that will feed the economic model deployed in Section 2.2. have already been estimated in Subsection 3.2.2. per economic sector for each country of the ZRB. Due to the fact though that the set up of the final hydrological model for the ZRB, developed within the framework of WP3, presented some technical difficulties, it was not possible for the data needed to simulate the economic development model of Section 2 to be retrieved. In order to end up with results which will be consistent with the hydrological approach of WP3, it is crucial to first get hold of the output of the distributed hydrological model, which will deliver time series data at virtually any point of interest as the model does represent the physical processes quantified in the economic framework of Section 2. Once we have the needed data we will proceed with the simulation process as in the OTB case (cf. Deliverable 4.6, Subsection 3.4) and conclude with the corresponding socioeconomic results regarding sustainable water management within the ZRB. Our simulations will be carried out in Matlab R2018b to perform the essential computations required in applying the stochastic optimization method described in Section 2 for both the cooperative and the non-cooperative case.

Figure 16 - Sampling distributions of productivity growth by sector for Malawi

In contrast to the upcoming river basin level data, which will be used to simulate numerically the water resource dynamics of the ZRB according to the economic model developed of Section 2, the inverse demand functions per sector for the countries of the ZRB were estimated via national level data; limitations concerning data collection are discussed in Subsection 1.1. Due to matters of scale consistency, we will downscale our simulation results on both the optimal water abstraction path and the resulting net benefit of each country to the river basin level via the percentage of the water availability inside the river basin over the total water availability of each of the riparian countries. We will approximate the total water availability by the total renewable water resources and the water availability inside the river basin of each of the countries by their internal runoff within the basin. In particular, total renewable water resources may be considered as the sum of internal and external renewable water resources and correspond to the maximum theoretical yearly amount of water available for a country at a given moment.

In our simulation analysis we will study the non-cooperative and the cooperative approach. The non-cooperative approach describes a situation where each (downstream or upstream) area does not have any kind of trading relationship with the other one and so, it maximizes only its own Net Benefit function. Both players have two available strategies, myopic and non-myopic, with myopic declaring the case where the area of interest does not consider the benefits coming from the natural resource, i.e. from the river for the upstream area and from the lake for the downstream area, and non-myopic being the other way around. For these strategies we will provide comparison results with respect to the Net Benefit and optimal water abstraction for each of the 2 areas, investigating the existence of a Nash equilibrium state where no area may benefit by changing strategy while the other one keeps its own unchanged.

On the other hand, in the cooperative approach we will present an inter-sectoral water sharing strategy between the upstream and downstream area in a cooperative setting. In particular, the downstream area offers a discount price for hydropower exports to the upstream area, in exchange for greater transboundary water flow that results in a higher water reserve accumulation and sequentially in a higher production of energy. This will be a differential Stackelberg “leader–follower” game as described in Section 2.2. In this case, the upstream area, as considered here to be the

ZRB fraction that expands across Angola, Botswana, Namibia, Zambia and Zimbabwe, is meant to be the leader of the Stackelberg game due to its advantage of affecting the water reserves of lake Cahorra Bassa in the considered downstream area of Mozambique. Results with respect to the Net Benefit and optimal water usage for each of the two areas will be deployed in this cooperative setting as well. These results compared to those of the non-cooperative framework presented above will eventually allow us to identify sustainable water allocation policies between the two areas of interest.

Last but not least, it is well known that climate change increases the variability of water flow and may exacerbate conflicts among countries sharing transboundary water resources. Thus, we also plan to investigate whether in the cooperative approach our results guarantee stability even under variance increase of water flow, precipitation, runoff or outflow, reflecting extreme weather conditions (droughts, floods, etc.). If this is the case then any deviation from cooperation would be costly even under climate change, as in the OTB case (cf. Deliverable 4.6, Subsection 3.4).

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

4.1 SUMMARY OF RESULTS

The main focus of Section 2 was to present the development of two different models of an economy that have access to the same natural resource, in this case a river basin, and explore whether they can perform sustainable transboundary water sharing for each sector taking into account the uncertainty posed by climate change. The five sectors of interest for each economic model were: Agriculture and Fishing, Residential Water Supply, Mining and Quarrying, Energy including hydropower production, and Tourism. This water distribution problem was modelled by an upstream area that has the right to unilaterally divert water away from a downstream area, which though has access to water stock reserves that provide additional hydropower benefits, not enjoyed by the upstream area. We initially studied the non-cooperative case, where each area allocates water with respect to maximizing its own expected welfare without the presence of an international water sharing agreement. Employing a stochastic Stackelberg differential game via appropriate net benefit functions, our aim next was to establish an inter-sectoral cooperative water allocation trade-off between the two areas, where the downstream area offers to the upstream one hydroelectric power at a discount price in exchange for greater transboundary water flow, and to make the comparison with the non-cooperative framework.

Our main goal in Section 3 was to develop and study, using econometrical estimation methods, the production functions per sector for the upstream and downstream countries, because they appear in the mathematical model of Section 2 as the social benefit functions. Additionally, we got the relationships and the corresponding graphs of the demand curves which represent the relation between the price of the good, water, and the quantity demanded for a given period of time, giving exactly how many units of water will be purchased at various prices. It is well known that as the price of a good rises, buyers will choose to buy less of it, and as its price falls, they buy more. Therefore, based on this statement, as the price of the water increases over time due to decreasing water availability, water demand for each of these economic sectors reaches zero sequentially, ending up with an ordering via their demand function for all the riparian countries of ZRB.

One of the main outcomes of the econometric model was estimating the derived demand for water use of the producers. In particular, in all countries the agricultural sectors are extremely inelastic in water use, i.e. an increase in price would only slightly decrease the water use, revealing so a very intensive dependence between access to water and agricultural products. The agriculture sector in most countries of interest is contributing significantly to the total GDP with 28% of the GDP of Malawi and Mozambique being due to the agriculture. Another outcome was the exit order of the sectors in the event of a drought, revealing so the preferences of the producers for water use. In particular, in Malawi and Mozambique, where energy production is not based in Hydropower, the willingness to pay of the energy producers is not high. However, considering that Malawi and Mozam-

bique, which are two of the four poorest countries in the world, and the population of which is expected to double within the next 30 years, are suffering from unpredictable floods, policy makers will be needed with a view to improving the recognition of the situation.

4.2 ADDITIONAL REMARKS

Of particular importance at this stage is giving due consideration to the potential means of future integration of the economic model with other models from the project's WPs 3 and 4; as well as how it may be incorporated into the work of WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5 in particular. The different subtasks of WP2 provide a list of evaluation indicators and candidate actions.

As part of the DAF model, T5.1 will perform

- a) a screening (scoping) of the candidate actions according to qualitative/quantitative indications coming from social-governance-economic models
- b) a selection of design indicators from the large list of evaluations indicators to be used as objective in the optimization of the pathways; the design indicators which represent all the water-energy-food components of the nexus according to the characteristics of the strategic model (which will be coupled with the optimization tools)

Still in the DAF model, T5.2 will take the candidate pathways produced by the screening of the actions and the selected WEF design indicators and will run an optimization with the strategic model using observed streamflow in "entry" sections and observed irrigation demands. The DAF model will produce in outputs the optimal pathways, i.e. combinations of infrastructural (e.g., construction of new dam) and operational (e.g. reservoir operating policy) actions with timing of implementation.

The optimal pathways will be simulated by the WEF integrated model, which will produce the value of some evaluation indicators directly as output of the simulation as well as some trajectories that will be then post-processed by the social-governance-economic models to compute the value of additional evaluation indicators (e.g. indicators not directly implemented in the WEF model, for example about social aspects of the simulated pathways).

All the evaluation indicators will finally be sent to the Negotiation Simulation Lab to be discussed with the Stakeholders.

5 REFERENCES

- Abeyssekara, W.A.T. (1976) Production function analysis of paddy farming in Sri Lanka (M.Sc. Thesis), The University of British Columbia, UK.
- Ackerberg, D. A., Caves, K. and G. Frazer, (2015) Identification Properties of Recent Production Function Estimators, *Econometrica*, vol. 83, 2411-2451.
- AfDB/OECD, (2003a) African Economic Outlook – Botswana, OECD Publications: Paris.
- AfDB/OECD, (2003b) African Economic Outlook – Zambia, OECD Publications: Paris.
- AfDB/OECD, (2007) African Economic Outlook-Botswana, OECD Publications: Paris.
- AfDB, (2011) Infrastructure and Growth in Zimbabwe: An Action Plan for Sustained Strong Economic Growth, Summary Report.
- AfDB/OECD/UNDP, (2017) African Economic Outlook – Angola, Available at: www.africaneconomicoutlook.org (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- AfDB/OECD/UNDP, (2017b) African Economic Outlook – Botswana, Available at: www.africaneconomicoutlook.org (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- AfDB/OECD/UNDP, (2017c) African Economic Outlook – Malawi, Available at: www.africaneconomicoutlook.org (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- AfDB/OECD/UNDP, (2017d) African Economic Outlook – Mozambique, Available at: www.africaneconomicoutlook.org (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- AfDB/OECD/UNDP, (2017e) African Economic Outlook – Namibia, Available at: www.africaneconomicoutlook.org (Accessed: 21/12/2017).

- AfDB/OECD/UNDP, (2017f) African Economic Outlook – Tanzania, Available at: www.africaneconomicoutlook.org (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- AfDB/OECD/UNDP, (2017g) African Economic Outlook – Zambia, Available at: www.africaneconomicoutlook.org (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- AfDB/OECD/UNDP, (2017h) African Economic Outlook – Zimbabwe, Available at: www.africaneconomicoutlook.org (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- African Development Bank Group, (2017) Data Repository, Available at: <http://africaclimate.opendataforafrica.org> (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- African Development Bank Group, (2015) Fragile States - Socio Economic Database, Available at: <http://dataportal.opendataforafrica.org/wjwcyhb/fragile-states-socio-economic-database> (Accessed: 12/06/17).
- Allan, J.A. (2002) Water resources in semi-arid regions: Real deficits and economically invisible and politically silent solutions, in: Turton, A. et al. (eds.), *Hydropolitics in the developing world – A southern African perspective*, African Water Issues Research Unit, Pretoria, 23-36.
- Ambec, S. and L. Ehlers, (2008) Sharing a River among Satiabile Agents, *Games Econ. Behav.*, vol. 64, 35–50.
- Ambec, S. and Y. Sprumont, (2002) Water and Economic Growth, *Econ. Rec.*, vol. 80, 1–16.
- Andrieu, C., Doucet, A. and R. Holenstein, (2010) Particle Markov chain Monte Carlo methods, *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B*, vol. 72, 269–342.
- Ansink, E. and A. Ruijs, (2008) Climate Change and the Stability of Water Allocation Agreements, *Environ. Resource Econ.*, vol. 41, 133–287.
- Ashton, P.J. and V. Ramasar, (2002) Water and HIV/AIDS: Some strategic considerations in Southern Africa, in Turton, A.R. et. Al. (eds), *Hydropolitics in the Developing World: A Southern African Perspective*, Pretoria: African Water Issues Research Unit (AWIRU), 217-235.
- Barbier, E. (2000) Water and Economic Growth, *Econ. Rec.*, vol. 80, 1-16.
- Battese, G.E. and T.J. Coelli, (1995) A model for technical inefficiency effects in a stochastic frontier production function for panel data, *Empirical Economics*, vol. 20, 325-332.
- Beard, R.M. and S. McDonald, (2007) Time-Consistent Fair Water Sharing Agreements, in Jorgensen, S. et al. (eds), *Advances in Dynamic Game Theory and Applications Series: Annals of the International Society of Dynamic Games*, Norwell Kluwer Academic Publishing, New York, 393-410.
- Beekman, H.E., Saayman, I. and S. Hughes, (2003) Vulnerability of water resources to environmental change in Southern Africa, Report for the pan African START secretariat and UNEP, Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, Stellenbosch, South Africa.
- Bhaduri, A., Manna, U. and E. Barbier, (2011) Climate change and cooperation in transboundary water sharing: an application of stochastic Stackelberg differential game s in Volta river basin, *Natural Resource Modeling*, vol. 24(4), 409-444.
- Bhaduri, A., Nicostrato, P. and L. Jens, (2008) Scope and Sustainability of Cooperation in Transboundary Water Sharing of the Volta River, *Center for Development Research*, Discussion Paper 124.
- Birol, E., Hanley, N., Koundouri, P. and Y. Kountouris, (2009) Optimal management of wetlands: Quantifying trade-offs between flood risks, recreation, and biodiversity conservation, *Water Resources Research*, vol. 45, doi: 10.1029/2008WR006955
- Brauman, K.A., Van der Meulen, A. and J. Brils, (2014) Ecosystem Services and River Basin Management, in Brils, J. et al. (eds), *Risk-Informed Management of European River Basins Series: The Handbook of Environmental Chemistry*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, vol. 29.
- Brems, H., (1968) *Quantitative Economic Theory*, 62–74 pp., New York: Wiley.
- Brouwer, R., Brander, R., Kuik, O., Papyrakis, E. and I. Bateman, (2013) A synthesis of approaches to assess and value ecosystem services in the EU in the context of TEEB, Report to the European Commission.
- Brown, C.J. (1994) Namibia's Green Plan, Ministry of Environment and Tourism: Windhoek, Namibia.
- Brown, D., Chanakira, R.R., Chatiza, K., Dhliwayo, M., Dodman, D., Masiwa, M., Muchadenyika, D., Mugabe, P. and S. Zvigadza, (2012) Climate Change Impacts, Vulnerability and Adaptation in Zimbabwe, IIED Climate Change Working Paper Series No. 3, Climate Change Group: London.
- Bucx, T., W. van Driel, H. de Boer, S. Graas, V.T. Langenberg, M. Marchand and C. Van de Guchte, (2014) Comparative assessment of the vulnerability and resilience of deltas – extended version with 14 deltas - synthesis report, Delta Alliance report number 7, Delta Alliance International, Delft-Wageningen, The Netherlands.

- Cain, A. and M. Mulenga, (2009) Water service provision for the peri-urban poor in post conflict Angola, IIED Human Settlements Working Paper Series, Available at: <http://pubs.iied.org/pdfs/10577IIED.pdf>, (Accessed: 10/2/ 2011).
- Carr, C.J., (2017) *River Basin Development and Human Rights in Eastern Africa: A Policy Crossroads*, 157-189 pp., Springer Cham, ISBN 978-3-319-50469-8.
- Casarin, R. and J.M. Marin, (2007) Online data processing: Comparison of Bayesian regularized particle filters. University of Brescia, Department of Economics, Working Paper n. 0704.
- Caudill, S.B., Ford, J.M. and D.M. Gropper, (1993) Frontier estimation and firm-specific inefficiency measures in the presence of heteroskedasticity, *Journal of Business Economic Statistics*, vol. 13, 105-111.
- Chilung, Z. (2016) Price of water up by 23 percent, Available at: <https://www.nyasatimes.com/price-water-23-percent-malawi-govt-approves/>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- CIA, (2017a) Country comparison GDP per capita. Available at: <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/rankorder/2004rank.html#mz>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- CIA, (2017b) The World Fact Book – Angola, Available at: <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/geos/ao.html>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- CIA, (2017c) The World Fact Book – Country Comparison – Population Growth Rate, Available at: <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/rankorder/2002rank.html#ao>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- CIA, (2017d) The World Fact Book – Malawi, Available at: <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/geos/mi.html>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- CIA, (2017e) The World Fact Book – Mozambique, Available at: <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/geos/mz.html>.
- Clarance-Smith, W.G. and J.K. Thornton, (2018) Angola. Encyclopaedia Britannica. Available from: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Angola> (Accessed on December 12, 2018).
- Council of Ministers – Mozambique, (2012) Regulamento de Pesquisa e Exploração de Águas, Available at: <http://arazambeze.gov.mz/images/pdf/reg-pesq-exp-aguas.pdf> (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Council of Ministers – Mozambique, (2016) Regulamento de Fixacao de Taxas de Agua Bruta, Available at: <http://www.arazambeze.gov.mz/attachments/article/58/REGULAMENTO-DE-FIXACAO-DE-NOVAS-TAXAS-DE-AGUA-BRUTA-REGULARIZADA-E-NAO-REGULARIZADA.pdf>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Danaher, P.J. and M.S. Smith, (2011) Modeling multivariate distributions using copulas: Applications in marketing, *Marketing Science*, vol.30 (1), 4-21.
- De Groot, R. S., Wilson, M. A. and R. M. J. Boumans, (2002) A typology for the classification, description and valuation of ecosystem functions, goods and services, *Ecological Economics*, vol. 41, 393-408, doi:10.1016/S0921-8009(02)00089-7.
- Dinar, A., (2009) Climate Change and International Water: The Role of Strategic Alliances in Resource Allocation, in Dinar, A. et al. (eds), *Policy and Strategic Behaviour in Water Resource Management*, 301–324.
- Dinar, A., Blankepoorb, B., Dinar, S. and P. Kurukulasuriya, (2010) Does Precipitation and Runoff Variability Affect Treaty Cooperation between States Sharing International Bilateral Rivers?, *Ecol. Econ.*, vol. 69, 2568–2581.
- Directorate of Water Affairs, (1991a) Perspective on Water Affairs, MAWRD: Windhoek.
- Dirkx, E. Hager, C., Tadross, M., Bethune, S. and B. Curtis, (2008) Climate Change Vulnerability and Adaptation Assessment. Desert Research Foundation (DRFN) and Climate Systems Analysis Group: University of Cape Town for the Ministry of Environment and Tourism.
- Doucet, A., N., de Freitas and N. Gordon, (2001) *Sequential Monte Carlo Methods in Practice*, New York: Springer.
- Engelbert, D., Jorgensen, S., Long, N. V., & Sorger, G. (2000). *Differential Games in Economics and Management Scienc.*, Cambridge University Press, New York.
- Eora, (2017) The Eora MRIO Database, Available at: <http://www.worldmrio.com/country> (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Fanaian, S., (2013) Valuing ecosystem services linked to river flows in Lower Zambezi basin, Mozambique, MSc thesis, UNESCO-IHE Institute for Water Education, Delft, The Netherlands.
- FAO, (2006) Aquastat Malawi. Available from: http://www.fao.org/nr/water/aquastat/countries_regions/MWI/ (Accessed: 10/12/2018).
- FAO, (2005) Aquastat Malawi Country Profile. Available from: http://www.fao.org/nr/water/aquastat/countries_regions/MWI/MWI-CP_eng.pdf (Accessed: 10/12/2018).
- FAO, (2005) Irrigation in Africa in Figures, Aquastat Survey 2005.

- FAO, (2017) AQUASTAT: Main Database, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Available at: <http://www.fao.org/nr/water/aquastat/data/query/index.html?lang=en>.
- FAO, (2017) FAOSTAT: Food and Agriculture Data, Available at: <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data> (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Fearnhead, P. (2007) Computational methods for complex stochastic systems: a review of some alternatives to MCMC, *Statistics and Computing*, vol. 18(2), 151-171.
- Fibaek, M. (2010) Botswana's Modern Economic History Since 1966. Has Botswana Reached the Last Stage of Modern Growth Regime? University of Copenhagen.
- Flury, T. and N. Shephard, (2011) Bayesian inference based only on simulated likelihood: particle filter analysis of dynamic economic models, *Econometric Theory*, vol. 27, 933-956.
- Giodarno, M.A. and A. Wolf, (2003) Impact of Climate Change on Transboundary Water Sharing, *CEPR Discussion Paper*, vol.27(2), 163–171.
- Gleick, P.H. (1992). Effects of Climate Change on Shared Fresh Water Resources, in Mintzer, I.M. (eds.), *Confronting Climate Change; Risks, Implication and Responses*, (Chapter 9, pp. 127–141), Cambridge University Press, Sweden.
- Gordon, N.J., Salmond, D.J. and A.F.M. Smith, (1993) Novel approach to nonlinear/non-Gaussian Bayesian state estimation, *IEEE-Proceedings-F*, vol. 140, 107–113.
- Gordon, N.J. (1997) A hybrid bootstrap filter for target tracking in clutter, *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 33, 353– 358.
- Government of Namibia, (2002) Initial National Communication to the United Framework Convention on Climate Change.
- Government of Zimbabwe, (2010) Medium Term Plan, January 2010-December 2015, Ministry of Economic Planning and Investment Promotion: Harare.
- Grant, R. and L. Krugel, (2017) Economic Snapshot HI, 2017- - Namibia, KPMG Services Pty Ltd.
- Hall, J., Pitt, M.K. and R. Kohn, (2014) Bayesian inference for nonlinear structural time series models, *Journal of Econometrics*, vol. 179 (2), 99–111.
- Hidroeléctrica de Cahora-Bassa, (2018) Características técnicas da albufeira e da barragem, Available at: <http://www.hcb.co.mz/Engenharias/O-Empreendimento/Caracteristicas-Tecnicas-da-Albufeira-e-da-Barragem> (Accessed: 20/12/2018).
- Hidroeléctrica de Cahora-Bassa, (2017) 2016 Annual Report, Available at: <http://www.hcb.co.mz/content/download/4702/27397/file/R&C%20ANNUAL%20REPORT%20HCB%202016.pdf> (Accessed: 20/12/2018).
- IAPRI, (2013) Small Holder Livestock Production and Challenges in Zambia, Indaba Agriculture Policy Research Institute: Lusaka.
- ILO, (2017) ILOSTAT: Key Indicators of the Labour Market., Available at https://www.ilo.org/ilostat/faces/wcnav_defaultSelection?_afLoop=466209758859045&_afWindowMode=0&_afWindowId=null#!%40%40%3F%40%40%3Dnull%26%40%40%3D466209758859045%26%40%40%3D0%26%40%40%3Dhsk7m0x7f_4INE-Angola (2017). Principais Indicadores de Angola por Província. Available at: http://www.ine.gov.ao/xportal/xmain?xpid=ine&xpgid=indicators_province&indicators_province=6779606 (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Index Mundi, (2018) Malawi Economy Profile 2018, Available at: https://www.indexmundi.com/malawi/economy_profile.html (Accessed: 10/12/2018).
- INE-Mozambique, (2017) Statistical Yearbook 2016, Available at <http://www.ine.gov.mz/estatisticas/publicacoes/anuario/nacionais/anuario-estatistico-2016>, (Accessed 21/12/2017).
- International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/World Bank Group, (2005) Private Solutions for Infrastructure in Angola: A Country Framework Report, Available at: <http://documents.worldbank.org/credited/en/182741468009007177/pdf/344130PAPER0AN101Official0use0only1.pdf>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- IPCC, (2007) *Climate Change 2007: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fourth Assessment Report*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, ISBN 978 0521 88010-7.
- Janmatt, J. and A. Ruijs, (2007) Sharing the Load? Floods, Droughts and Managing International Rivers. *Environ Dev. Econ.*, vol. 4, 573–592.
- Jeffens, K. and T. Nemaora, (2015) Country Overview – Botswana, Capital Resources (Pty) Limited.
- Joint Monitoring Programme – J.M.P., (2018a) Drinking water ladder, Available from: <https://washdata.org/monitoring/drinking-water> (Accessed: 10/12/2018).

- Joint Monitoring Programme – J.M.P., (2018b) Sanitation ladder, Available from: <https://washdata.org/monitoring/sanitation> (Accessed: 10/12/2018).
- Joint Monitoring Programme – J.M.P., (2018c) WASH coverage data for Angola, Available from: <https://washdata.org/data#!/table?geo0=country&geo1=AGO> (Accessed: 10/12/2018).
- Joint Monitoring Programme – J.M.P., (2018d). WASH coverage data for Malawi, Available from: <https://washdata.org/data#!/table?geo0=country&geo1=MWI> (Accessed: 10/12/2018).
- Joint Monitoring Programme – J.M.P., (2018e). WASH coverage data for Mozambique, Available from: <https://washdata.org/data#!/table?geo0=country&geo1=MOZ> (Accessed: 10/12/2018).
- Joint Monitoring Programme – J.M.P., (2018f). WASH coverage data for Tanzania, Available from: <https://washdata.org/data#!/table?geo0=country&geo1=TZA> (Accessed: 10/12/2018).
- Jondrow, J., Lovell, C.A.K., Materov, I.S. and P. Schmidt, (1982) On the estimation of technical inefficiency in the stochastic frontier production function model, *Journal of Econometrics*, vol. 19 (2/3), 233-238.
- Juana, J.S., Makepe, P.M., Mangadi, K.T. and N. Narayana, (2014) The Socio-Economic Impact of Drought in Botswana, *International Journal of Environment and Development*, vol. 11(1), 43-60.
- Kim, C. S., Moore, M. R. and J. J. Hanchar, (1989) A Dynamic Model of Adaptation to Resource Depletion: Theory and an Application to Groundwater Mining, *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, vol. 17, 66-82.
- Koundouri, P., Akinsete, E., and S. Tsani, (2019) *Socio-Economic and Policy Implications of Multi-Stressed Rivers: A European Perspective. In Multiple Stressors in River Ecosystems*, 335-351pp., Elsevier, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-811713-2.00019-4>
- Koundouri, P. and C. Christou, (2006) Dynamic Adaptation to Resource Scarcity and Backstop Availability: Theory and Application to Groundwater, *The Australian Journal of Agricultural and Resources Economics*, vol. 50, 227-245.
- Koundouri, P., and O. G., Davila, (2015) The use of the ecosystem services approach in guiding water valuation and management: Inland and coastal waters, *Handbook of Water Economics*, 126-149. Available at: [https://books.google.gr/books?hl=el&lr=&id=166CCgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA126&dq=\).+The+Use+of+Ecosystem+Services+Approach+in+Guiding+Water+Valuation+and+Management:+Inland+and+Coastal+Waters.&ots=OdzKug90oF&sig=KURKJHv24pXg1or8wjYDhSYvwxQ&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false](https://books.google.gr/books?hl=el&lr=&id=166CCgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA126&dq=).+The+Use+of+Ecosystem+Services+Approach+in+Guiding+Water+Valuation+and+Management:+Inland+and+Coastal+Waters.&ots=OdzKug90oF&sig=KURKJHv24pXg1or8wjYDhSYvwxQ&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false).
- Kumar, P. (2012), *The economics of ecosystems and biodiversity: ecological and economic foundations*, Routledge, Available at: <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/9781136538803>.
- Kumbhakar, S., Parmeter, C.F. and E.G. Tsionas, (2013) A zero inefficiency stochastic frontier model, *Journal of Econometrics*, vol. 172, 66-76.
- Lange, G.M., (1997) *An Approach to Sustainable Water Management Using Natural Resource Accounts: the use of water, the economic value of water and implications for policy*, Research Discussion Paper No. 18. Directorate of Environmental Affairs, Ministry of Environment and Tourism: Windhoek.
- Lenzen, M., Kanemoto, K., Moran, D. and A. Geschke, (2012) Mapping the Structure of the World Economy, *Env. Sci. Tech.*, vol. 46(15), 8374-8381, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1021/es300171x>.
- Lenzen, M., Moran, D., Kanemoto, K. and A. Geschke, (2013). Building Eora: A Global Multi-Regional Input-Output Database at High Country and Sector Resolution, *Economic Systems Research*, vol. 25(1), 20-49, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09535314.2013.769938>.
- Levinsohn, J. and A. Petrin, (2003) Estimating production functions using inputs to control for unobservables, *The Review of Economic Studies*, vol. 70 (2), 317-341.
- Liu, J. and M. West, (2001) Combined parameter and state estimation in simulation-based filtering, in Doucet, A. et al. (eds.), *Sequential Monte Carlo Methods in Practice*, Springer-Verlag.
- Makurira, H. and N. Viriri, (2017) *Water Permit Systems, Policy Reforms and Implications for Equity in Zimbabwe*, Project Country Report by PEGASYS Institute, IWMI and REACH.
- Marschak, J., & William H. A. (1944). Random Simultaneous Equations and the Theory of Production. *Econometrica*, 12(3-4), 143–205.
- Ministry of Finance and Economic Development, (2014) 2015 National Budget Statement, Harare.
- Ministry of Finance and Economic Development, (2015b) 2016 National Budget Statement, Harare.
- Ministry of Water Affairs and Forestry, (1999) *A Pricing Strategy for Raw Water Use Charges*, Ministry of Water Affairs and Forestry: Lusaka.
- Ministry of Energy and Water Resource Development, (2008) *Zambia National Strategy for Water Resources Pricing and Financing*, Economic Consulting Associates Limited: London.
- Mkandawire, M. (2017) Malawi reverses illegal water tariff hike, Available at: <https://malawi24.com/2017/11/17/malawi-reverses-illegal-water-tariff-hike/> (Accessed: 21/12/2017).

- Moroney, J. R., (1967) Cobb-Douglass production functions and returns to scale in US manufacturing industry, *Western Economic Journal*, vol. 6(1), 39–51, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.14657295.1967.tb01174.x>.
- Namibia Country Profile and Market Opportunities, (2015) Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands: Pretoria.
- National Bureau of Statistics, (2014) Basic Demographic and Socio-Economic Profile, Ministry of Finance, Dar es Salaam.
- Nelsen, R.B. (2006) *An Introduction to Copula*, Vol. 139 of Springer Series in Statistics, Springer.
- Nemeth, C. and P. Fearnhead, (2014) Particle Metropolis adjusted Langevin algorithms for state-space models, Pre-print arXiv:1402.0694v1.
- NSO, (2016) Statistical Yearbook 2016, Available at: http://www.nsomalawi.mw/images/stories/data_on_line/general/yearbook/2016%20Statistical%20Yearbook.pdf (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Protected Planet, (2017) WDPA Lookup Tables, Available at: <https://www.protectedplanet.net/c/wdpa-lookup-tables>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- P.J.T.C. Kunene, (2017). Kunene River Awareness Kit, Available at: http://www.kunene.riverawarenesskit.com/KUNENERAK_COM/EN/MANAGEMENT/VALUE_OF_WATER/ECONOMIC_VALUE/ANGOLA.HTM, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Republic of Botswana (2015). Botswana Water Accounting Report 2015. Available at: http://www.water.gov.bw/images/Reports/DWA_Website/BWAR%202012_2014.pdf (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Olley, S. and A. Pakes, (1996) The dynamics of productivity in the telecommunications equipment industry, *Econometrica*, vol. 64, 1263-1297.
- Park, S. and S. Gupta, (2012) Handling endogenous regressors by joint estimation using Copulas, *Marketing Science*, vol. 31 (4), 567-586.
- Pistocchi, A., Udias, A., Grizzetti, B., Gelati, E., Koundouri, P., Ludwig, R., Papandreou A. and I. Souliotis, (2017) An integrated assessment framework for the analysis of multiple pressures in aquatic ecosystems and the appraisal of management options, *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 575, 1477-1488, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.10.020>
- Pitt, M.K. and N. Shephard, (1999) Filtering via simulation based on auxiliary particle filters, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, vol. 94 (446), 590-599.
- Pitt, M.K., Silva, R.S., Giordani, P. and R. Kohn, (2012) On some properties of Markov chain Monte Carlo simulation methods based on the particle filter, *J. Econom.*, vol. 171(2), 134–151.
- Praagman, E., Jacobs, C. and W. van Driel, (2013) Impacts of changing flow regimes to agricultural practices in the Zambezi delta- Mozambique case study, Delta Alliance Phase 3.
- Republic of Botswana, (2008) Resettlement Policy Framework Final Report, Arid Environmental Consultancy (Pty) Ltd. Department of Roads: Gaborone.
- Republic of Zambia, (2010) National Water Policy, Ministry of Energy and Water Development.
- Ristic, B., Arulampalam, S. and N. Gordon, (2004) *Beyond Kalman Filters: Particle Filters for Applications*, Norwood, MA: Artech House.
- Saari, S., (2006) Productivity. Theory and Measurement in Business. Espoo, Finland: European Productivity Conference.
- Saari, S., (2011). Production and Productivity as Sources of Well-being, *MIDO OY*, vol. 25, 1-25.
- SADC, (2012) Regional Infrastructure Development Masterplan (RIDMP), in ZAMCOM, SADC and SARDC (2015) Zambezi Environment Outlook 2015, SARDC Publishing: Harare.
- Schulze, R., Meigh, J. and M. Horan, (2001) Present and potential future vulnerability of eastern and southern Africa's hydrology and water resources, *South African Journal of Science*, vol. 97, 150 – 160.
- Shephard, R., (1970) *Theory of Cost and Production Functions*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Sklar, A., (1959) Functions de repartition a n dimensions et leurs marges, *Publications de l'Institut de Statistique de l'Université de Paris*, vol. 8, 229-231.
- Song, P.X.K., (2000) Multivariate dispersion models generated from Gaussian copula, *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics*, vol. 27 (2), 305-320.
- Stephen, D.E. and J. E. Kundell, (2008) Sharing Waters: Post-Rio International Water Management, *J. Water Resour. Plan. Manag.*, vol.133(5), 405–415.
- TNBS, (2016a) Statistics Highlight, Available at: http://www.nbs.go.tz/nbs/takwimu/references/Tanzania_in_Figures_2015.pdf (Accessed: 21/12/2017).

- TNBS, (2016b) Tanzania in Figures 2015, Available at:
http://www.nbs.go.tz/nbs/takwimu/references/Tanzania_in_Figures_2015.pdf (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Trading Economics, (2018) Mozambique - Employment in agriculture (% of total employment), Available at:
<https://tradingeconomics.com/mozambique/employment-in-agriculture-percent-of-total-employment-wb-data.html>.
- United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, (2016a) Country Profile – Botswana, Publications Section: Addis Ababa.
- United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, (2016b) Country Profile – Namibia, Publications Section: Addis Ababa.
- United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, (2016c) Country Profile – Zambia, Publications Section: Addis Ababa.
- United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, (2016d) Country Profile – Zimbabwe, Publications Section: Addis Ababa.
- United Nations Statistics Division, (2014) Energy Statistics Yearbook, Available at:
<https://unstats.un.org/unsd/energy/yearbook/default.htm>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Uwazi, (2010) Water Prices in Dar es Salaam: Do Water Kiosks Comply with Official Tariffs? Policy Brief TZ.09/2010E, Technical report, Uwazi at Twaweza, Available at: www.uwazi.org/uploads/files/Water%20kiosks%20in%20DSM%20Englsh.pdf, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Vorosmarty, C.J., (2002) Global Water Assessment and Potential Contributions from Earth Systems Science, *Aquat. Sci.*, vol. 64, 328–351.
- Wingqvist, G.O and E. Dahlberg, (2008) Botswana Environmental and Climate Change Analysis, SIDA: Stockholm.
- UNICEF, (2018) Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Promotion, Malawi, Available at:
https://www.unicef.org/malawi/wes_3975.html.
- WHO/UNICEF – JMP, (2017) Data, Available at: <https://washdata.org/data>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- World Bank, (2010) The Zambezi River Basin A Multi-Sector Investment Opportunities Analysis – Summary Report, Vol 1.
- World Bank, (2012) Mozambique - Country partnership framework for the period FY13 – FY16, Available at:
<http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/140731468269673229/pdf/741590CORRIGENDUM0IDA0R20130000302.pdf>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- World Bank, (2013) Angola - Country partnership strategy FY13 – FY16, Available at:
<http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/pt/469841468204833634/pdf/762250CAS0Ango0800OUO0900Box379823B.pdf> (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- World Bank, (2016) Zambia Economic Belief: Rising Revenue to Drive Economic Recovery, World Bank Group: Washington, D.C.
- World Bank, (2017a) Databank: Sustainable Energy for All, Available at:
<http://databank.worldbank.org/data/reports.aspx?source=Sustainable-Energy-for-All>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- World Bank, (2017b) Mozambique - Country partnership framework for the period FY17 - FY21, Available at:
<http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/540001493517702187/pdf/MZ-CPF-Final-clean-March-23-04052017.pdf>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- World Bank, (2017c) Tanzania Overview, Available at:
<http://www.worldbank.org/en/country/tanzania/overview>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- World Bank, (2017d) World Development Indicators: Zambia, World Bank: Washington, D.C.
- World Bank Group, (2017) Climate Change Knowledge Portal For Development Practitioners and Policy Makers, Available at: <http://sdwebx.worldbank.org/climateportal/>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- World Bank (2018). World Bank Open Data. Free and open access to global development data. Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org>
- World Tourism Organization, (2017) Yearbook of Tourism Statistics: Compendium of Tourism Statistics and data files <https://www.e-unwto.org/toc/unwtotfb/current>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).
- Yager. T.R., (2007) *The Mineral Industry of Mozambique*, 2006 Minerals Yearbook, U.S. Geological Survey.
- Young, R.A., (1996) Measuring Economic benefits for water investments and policies, World Bank Technical Paper No. 338.
- ZAMCOM, (2008) Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) Strategy and Implementation Plan for the Zambezi Basin (Zambezi Watercourse Commission - ZAMCOM), ZAMCOM: Lusaka.

ZAMCOM, SADC and SARDC, (2015) Zambezi Environment Outlook 2015, SARDC Publishing: Harare.

Zimbabwe National Statistics Agency, (2014) Labor Force Survey – 2014, Zimstat: Harare.

ZINWA, (2016) Simplifying the price of water, Available at: <http://www.zinwa.co.zw/simplifying-the-price-of-water/>, (Accessed: 21/12/2017).

2030 Water Resources Group, (2014). Tanzania: Hydro-economic overview – An initial analysis, Available at: http://www.2030wrg.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/2030WRG_TANZANIA.pdf, (Accessed on December 10, 2018).

APPENDIX 1 – ECOSYSTEM SERVICES INDICES

Table 10 - Description of Indices of Ecosystem Services

ES Services	Indicator	Description	Units	Source
	GVA per sector	Represents the contribution of labour and capital to the production process. Gross value added at basic prices is defined as output valued at basic prices less intermediate consumption valued at purchasers' prices. Although the outputs and inputs are valued using different sets of prices, for brevity the value added is described by the prices used to value the outputs. From the point of view of the producer, purchasers' prices for inputs and basic prices for outputs represent the prices actually paid and received. Their use leads to a measure of gross value added that is particularly relevant for the producer. Net value added is defined as the value of output less the values of both intermediate consumption and consumption of fixed capital.	\$	Input-Output Tables http://www.worldmrio.com/country
	Gross Fixed Capital Formation per sector	Gross fixed capital formation is measured by the total value of a producer's acquisitions, less disposals, of fixed assets during the accounting period plus certain additions to the value of non-produced assets (such as subsoil assets or major improvements in the quantity, quality or productivity of land) realized by the productive activity of institutional units.	\$	Input-Output Tables http://www.worldmrio.com/country
	Employment Per sector	Persons in employment are defined as all those of working age who, during a short reference period, were engaged in any activity to produce goods or provide services for pay or profit. They comprise employed persons "at work", i.e. who worked in a job for at least one hour; and employed persons "not at work" due to temporary absence from a job, or to working-time arrangements (such as shift work, flexi-time and compensatory leave for overtime).	Abs. Value	ILO (International LABOUR Organization)
Provis. services	WFN: Total Water Footprint per sector	Total water use which includes: – WFN: Total water footprint - Green – WFN: Total water footprint - Blue – WFN: Total water footprint - Grey	Mm ³ /yr	Input-Output Tables http://www.worldmrio.com
	Energy Use (Total) per sector	Natural Gas, Coal, Petroleum, Nuclear Electricity, Hydroelectric Electricity, Geothermal Electricity, Wind Electricity, Solar, Tide and Wave Electricity, Biomass and Waste Electricity	TJ	Input-Output Tables http://www.worldmrio.com/country
Regul. Services	Water Quality	Nitrogen Emissions exportable to water bodies from agriculture and household waste water	Gg	Input-Output Tables http://www.worldmrio.com/country
	Fertilizers:	Proportions of consumption of fertilizers (by nutrient	kg/ha	Food and

	Total Nitrogen and Phosphate (N and P2O5)	group) per unit of agricultural land area are calculated by UNSD using available consumption and land use data from FAOSTAT.		Agriculture Organization of United Nations (FAOSTAT)
Provis. services	Agricultural Area	Agricultural area, this category is the sum of areas under "Arable land", "Permanent crops" and "Permanent pastures"	10 ³ ha	Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations (FAOSTAT)
Provis. services	Raw Materials per Sector	For agriculture total biomass and for mining-quarries total construction material and total fossil fuel	t	Input-Output Tables http://www.worldmrio.com/country
Provis. services	Permanent Crops	Permanent crops is the land cultivated with long-term crops which do not have to be replanted for several years (such as cocoa and coffee); land under trees and shrubs producing flowers, such as roses and jasmine; and nurseries (except those for forest trees, which should be classified under "forest"). Permanent meadows and pastures are excluded from land under permanent crops.	10 ³ ha	Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations (FAOSTAT)
Provis. services	Arable Land	Arable land is the land under temporary agricultural crops (multiple-cropped areas are counted only once), temporary meadows for mowing or pasture, land under market and kitchen gardens and land temporarily fallow (less than five years). The abandoned land resulting from shifting cultivation is not included in this category. Data for "Arable land" are not meant to indicate the amount of land that is potentially cultivable.	10 ³ ha	Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations (FAOSTAT)
Provis. services	Crop Production	Crop statistics are recorded for 173 products, covering the following categories: Crops Primary, Fibre Crops Crop statistics are recorded for 173 products, covering the following categories: Crops Primary, Fibre Crops Primary, Cereals, Coarse Grain, Citrus Fruit, Fruit, Jute & Jute-like Fibres, Oilcakes Equivalent, Oil crops Primary, Pulses, Roots and Tubers, Treenuts and Vegetables and Melons. Data are expressed in terms of area harvested, production quantity, yield and seed quantity. The objective is to comprehensively cover production of all primary crops for all countries and regions in the world.	t	Input-Output Tables http://www.worldmrio.com/country
Regul. Services	Forest	Forest area is the land spanning more than 0.5 hectares with trees higher than 5 metres and a canopy cover of more than 10 percent, or trees able to reach these thresholds in situ. It does not include land that is predominantly under agricultural or urban land use. Forest is determined both by the presence of trees and the absence of other predominant land uses. The trees should be able to reach a minimum height of 5 metres (m) in situ. Areas under reforestation that have not yet reached but are expected to reach a canopy cover of 10 percent and a tree height of 5 m are included, as are temporarily unstocked	10 ³ ha	Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations (FAOSTAT)

		areas, resulting from human intervention or natural causes, which are expected to regenerate. Includes: areas with bamboo and palms provided that height and canopy cover criteria are met; forest roads, fire-breaks and other small open areas; forest in national parks, nature reserves and other protected areas such as those of specific scientific, historical, cultural or spiritual interest; windbreaks, shelterbelts and corridors of trees with an area of more than 0.5 ha and width of more than 20 m; plantations primarily used for forestry or protective purposes, such as: rubber-wood plantations and cork, oak stands. Excludes: tree stands in agricultural production systems, for example in fruit plantations and agroforestry systems. The term also excludes trees in urban parks and gardens.		
Provis. services	Total Area Equipped For Irrigation	Area equipped with irrigation infrastructure to provide water to the crops. This includes areas equipped for full and partial control irrigation, spate irrigation areas, and equipped wetland or inland valley bottoms.	10 ³ ha	Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations (FAOSTAT)
Provis. services	Total Fisheries Production	Total fisheries production measures the volume of aquatic species caught by a country for all commercial, industrial, recreational and subsistence purposes. The harvest from mariculture, aquaculture and other kinds of fish farming is also included.	t	Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations (FAOSTAT)
	Temperature	The yearly mean historical rainfall and temperature data can be mapped to show the baseline climate and seasonality yearly, and for rainfall and temperature.	°C	The World Bank Group Climate Change Knowledge PortalFor Development Practitioners and Policy Makers
	Rainfall	Yearly Mean historical rainfall	mm	The World Bank Group Climate Change Knowledge PortalFor Development Practitioners and Policy Makers
Habitat services	Biodiversity and Habitats	A “proximity-to-target methodology” is used to assess how close each country is to an identified policy target. Country scores are determined by how close or far countries are to targets. Scores are standardized (i.e., on a scale of 0 to 100) for comparability, weighting, and aggregation. The Environmental Performance Index (EPI) is constructed through the calculation and aggregation of 20 indicators reflecting national-level environmental	%	Environment and Climate Change Data Portal

		<p>data. These indicators are combined into nine issue categories, each of which fit under one of two overarching objectives. The two objectives that provide the overarching structure of the EPI are Environmental Health and Ecosystem Vitality. Biodiversity & Habitats belongs to the Ecosystem Vitality which measures ecosystem protection and resource management. These two objectives are further divided into nine issue categories that span high-priority environmental policy issues, including air quality, forests, fisheries, and climate and energy, among others. The issue categories are extensive but not comprehensive. Underlying the nine issue categories, 20 indicators are calculated from country-level data and statistics.</p> <p>In this case the Biodiversity and Habitat category includes four indicators: Critical Habitat Protection, Terrestrial Protected Areas (National Biome Weight), Terrestrial Protected Areas (Global Biome Weight), and Marine Protected Areas. The targets are: 100% for Critical Habitat Protection; 17% for Terrestrial Protected Areas (National Biome Weights); 17% for Terrestrial Protected Areas (Global Biome Weights); 10% for Marine Protected Areas. (c.f. http://archive.epi.yale.edu/our-methods/biodiversity-and-habitat)</p>		
<p>Regul. Services</p>	<p>Terrestrial Protected Areas</p>	<p>The definition of a “protected area”, as adopted by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), is “an area of land and/or sea especially dedicated to the protection and maintenance of biological diversity, and of natural and associated cultural resources, and managed through legal or other effective means”. (IUCN 1994. Guidelines for Protected Areas Management Categories. IUCN; Gland; Switzerland and Cambridge; UK). Protected areas increase with time and are not deleted from subsequent years. Only protected areas that are “nationally designated” are included in this indicator. The status “designated” is attributed to a protected area when the authority that corresponds, according to national legislation or common practice (e.g. by means of an executive decree), officially endorses a document of designation. The designation must be for conservation of biodiversity, not single species and not fortuitous de facto protection arising because of some other activity (e.g. military). Hence, a number of United States Marine Managed Areas as well as permanent fisheries closures are excluded. Data are adjusted to account for transboundary protected areas (protected areas that transcend international boundaries) to ensure that the appropriate area/extent from the total area for that site is attributed to the country in which it is contained. Similar adjustments have been made where a protected area transcends both marine and terrestrial environments. The size of the protected area (its “extent”) is the officially documented total area provided by the national authority or as listed by the World Database on Protected Areas and may be generated from spatial</p>	<p>Km²</p>	<p>World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA) website at: www.wdpa.org/.</p>

		(GIS) boundary data (see source for details). Many protected areas can contain proportions of both the marine and terrestrial environment, and the size of the protected area extent that falls into each environment is not always available. The table also includes some protected areas for which the year (date of establishment/designation) is unavailable. If no update is received for a given year, the total number and size of the protected area is assumed to be equal to the previous year's values.		
	Access to Electricity	Access to electricity is the percentage of population with access to electricity. Electrification data are collected from industry, national surveys and international sources.	% of population	World Bank, Sustainable Energy for All (SE4ALL) database
	People Using Basic Drinking Water Services	The percentage of people using at least basic water services. This indicator encompasses both people using basic water services as well as those using safely managed water services. Basic drinking water services is defined as drinking water from an improved source, provided collection time is not more than 30 minutes for a round trip. Improved water sources include piped water, boreholes or tubewells, protected dug wells, protected springs, and packaged or delivered water.	% of population	World Bank, from WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme (JMP) for Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene (washdata.org).
	International Tourism, Number of Arrivals	International inbound tourists (overnight visitors) are the number of tourists who travel to a country other than that in which they have their usual residence, but outside their usual environment, for a period not exceeding 12 months and whose main purpose in visiting is other than an activity remunerated from within the country visited. When data on number of tourists are not available, the number of visitors, which includes tourists, same-day visitors, cruise passengers, and crew members, is shown instead. Sources and collection methods for arrivals differ across countries. In some cases data are from border statistics (police, immigration, and the like) and supplemented by border surveys. In other cases data are from tourism accommodation establishments. For some countries number of arrivals is limited to arrivals by air and for others to arrivals staying in hotels. Some countries include arrivals of nationals residing abroad while others do not. Caution should thus be used in comparing arrivals across countries. The data on inbound tourists refer to the number of arrivals, not to the number of people traveling. Thus a person who makes several trips to a country during a given period is counted each time as a new arrival.	Abs. Value	World Bank, World Tourism Organization, Yearbook of Tourism Statistics, Compendium of Tourism Statistics and data files
Regul. Services	Renewable Electricity Production	Electricity production refers to gross production, which is the sum of the electrical energy production by all the generating units/installations concerned (including pumped storage) measured at the output terminals of the main generators. Renewable electricity production (%) refers to the proportion of total electricity produced that comes from a renewable origin. Electricity production refers to gross electricity	%	United Nations Statistics Division, Energy Statistics http://unstats.un.org/unsd/ener-

		<p>production, which is the sum of the electrical energy production by all the generating units/installations concerned (including pumped storage) measured at the output terminals of the main generators. This includes the consumption by station auxiliaries and any losses in the transformers that are considered integral parts of the station. Renewable electricity production was calculated as the sum of electricity produced from hydro, geothermal, solar, wind, tide, wave and ocean sources. All electricity production from combustible fuels is considered non-renewable; therefore electricity produced from burning biomass or renewable waste is not included as renewable electricity in this table. However, this has been observed to be a relatively negligible proportion of electricity production in most cases.</p>		<p>gy/yearbook/default.htm.</p>
<p>Regul. Services</p>	<p>CO₂</p>	<p>Public electricity and heat production Other Energy Industries Manufacturing Industries and Construction Domestic aviation Road transportation Rail transportation Inland navigation Other transportation Residential and other sectors Fugitive emissions from solid fuels Fugitive emissions from oil and gas International aviation International navigation Production of minerals Cement production Lime production Production of chemicals Production of metals Production of pulp/paper/food/drink Production of halocarbons and SF6 Refrigeration and Air Conditioning Foam Blowing Fire Extinguishers Aerosols F-gas as Solvent Semiconductor/Electronics Manufacture Electrical Equipment Other F-gas use Non-energy use of lubricants/waxes (CO₂) Solvent and other product use: paint Solvent and other product use: degrease Solvent and other product use: chemicals Solvent and other product use: other Enteric fermentation Manure management Rice cultivation Direct soil emissions Manure in pasture/range/paddock Indirect N₂O from agriculture Other direct soil emissions Savanna burning Agricultural waste burning Forest fires</p>	<p>Gg</p>	<p>Input-Output Tables http://www.worldmrio.com/country</p>

		<p>Grassland fires Decay of wetlands/peatlands Other vegetation fires Forest Fires-Post burn decay Solid waste disposal on land Wastewater handling Waste incineration Other waste handling Fossil fuel fires Indirect N₂O from non-agricultural NO_x Indirect N₂O from non-agricultural NH₃ Other sources</p>		
Regul. Services	NO₂	<p>Public electricity and heat production Other Energy Industries Manufacturing Industries and Construction Domestic aviation Road transportation Rail transportation Inland navigation Other transportation Residential and other sectors Fugitive emissions from solid fuels Fugitive emissions from oil and gas Memo: International aviation Memo: International navigation Production of minerals Cement production Lime production Production of chemicals Production of metals Production of pulp/paper/food/drink Production of halocarbons and SF6 Refrigeration and Air Conditioning Foam Blowing Fire Extinguishers Aerosols F-gas as Solvent Semiconductor/Electronics Manufacture Electrical Equipment Other F-gas use Non-energy use of lubricants/waxes (CO₂) Solvent and other product use: paint Solvent and other product use: degrease Solvent and other product use: chemicals Solvent and other product use: other Enteric fermentation Manure management Rice cultivation Direct soil emissions Manure in pasture/range/paddock Indirect N₂O from agriculture Other direct soil emissions Savanna burning Agricultural waste burning Forest fires Grassland fires Decay of wetlands/peatlands Other vegetation fires Forest Fires-Post burn decay</p>		

		<p>Solid waste disposal on land Wastewater handling Waste incineration Other waste handling Fossil fuel fires Indirect NO₂ from non-agricultural NO_x Indirect NO₂ from non-agricultural NH₃ Other sources</p>		
Regul. Services	Total Annual Freshwater Withdrawals	<p>Annual freshwater withdrawals refer to total water withdrawals, not counting evaporation losses from storage basins. Withdrawals also include water from desalination plants in countries where they are a significant source. Withdrawals can exceed 100 percent of total renewable resources where extraction from non-renewable aquifers or desalination plants is considerable or where there is significant water re-use. Withdrawals for agriculture and industry are total withdrawals for irrigation and livestock production and for direct industrial use (including withdrawals for cooling thermoelectric plants). Withdrawals for domestic uses include drinking water, municipal use or supply, and use for public services, commercial establishments, and homes. Data are for the most recent year available for 1987-2002.</p>	10 ⁹ m ³	<p>Food and Agriculture Organization, AQUASTAT data.</p>
Regul. Services	Floods and Droughts	<p>Number of floods/droughts events.</p>	[-]	<p>The Emergency Events Database - Université catholique de Louvain (UCL) - CRED, D. Guha-Sapir, www.emdat.be, Brussels, Belgium. http://emdat.be/emdat_db/</p>
Cultural and amenity services	Cultural-Natural-Mixed Heritage Sites	<p>To be included on the World Heritage List, sites must be of outstanding universal value and meet at least one out of ten selection criteria. These criteria are explained in the Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention which, besides the text of the Convention, is the main working tool on World Heritage. The criteria are regularly revised by the Committee to reflect the evolution of the World Heritage concept itself. Access to an improved water source refers to the percentage of the population with reasonable access to an adequate amount of water from an improved source, such as a household connection, public standpipe, borehole, protected well or spring, and rainwater collection. Unimproved sources include vendors, tanker trucks, and unprotected wells and springs. Reasonable access is defined as the availability of at least 20 liters a person a day from a source within one kilometer of the dwelling.</p>	[-]	<p>UNESCO World Heritage Centre – World Heritage List</p>

APPENDIX 2 – DECOUPLING METHOD

In this appendix we derive analytical solutions for the stochastic optimization problems presented in Section 2.2 by making use of a decoupling method for linear FBSDEs.

Non-Cooperative Approach: Upstream Case

For the j -exit stage, the Hamiltonian of the optimization problem (12) is formulated as follows:

$$H_j^U(W_{jt}^U, w_{jt}^U, \dots, w_{5t}^U, \lambda_{jt}^U) \triangleq \sum_{i=j}^5 \left[\frac{a_i^U}{b_i^U} w_{it}^U - \frac{1}{2b_i^U} \cdot (w_{it}^U)^2 - (k_2^U - k_1^U W_{jt}^U) w_{it}^U \right] + \lambda_{jt}^U \left[W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{it}^U \right], \quad j=1,2,\dots,5, \quad (41)$$

where λ_{jt}^U is the j -exit stage adjoint variable that represents water scarcity rents for the upstream area. Making use of (41), the necessary conditions for optimality are given as follows:

$$\frac{\partial H_j^U}{\partial w_{it}^U} = \frac{a_i^U}{b_i^U} - \frac{1}{b_i^U} \cdot w_{it}^U - (k_2^U - k_1^U W_{jt}^U) - \lambda_{jt}^U = 0, \quad i=j,\dots,5, \quad j=1,2,\dots,5, \quad (42)$$

$$d\lambda_{jt}^U = \left[-\frac{\partial H_j^U}{\partial W_{jt}^U} + r\lambda_{jt}^U \right] dt \Leftrightarrow d\lambda_{jt}^U = \left[-k_1^U \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{it}^U + r\lambda_{jt}^U \right] dt, \quad i=j,\dots,5, \quad j=1,2,\dots,5. \quad (43)$$

From (42) we have that:

$$w_{it}^U = a_i^U - b_i^U (k_2^U - k_1^U W_{jt}^U) - b_i^U \lambda_{jt}^U, \quad i=j,\dots,5, \quad j=1,2,\dots,5. \quad (44)$$

Setting

$$A_j^U \triangleq \sum_{i=j}^5 a_i^U \quad \text{and} \quad B_j^U \triangleq \sum_{i=j}^5 b_i^U, \quad j=1,2,\dots,5, \quad (45)$$

the state equation of (3) and the adjoint equation of (43) form the FBSDEs system:

$$\begin{aligned} dW_{jt}^U &= \left[-k_1^U B_j^U W_{jt}^U + B_j^U \lambda_{jt}^U + W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U \right] dt, \\ d\lambda_{jt}^U &= \left[-(k_1^U)^2 B_j^U W_{jt}^U + (k_1^U B_j^U + r)\lambda_{jt}^U - k_1^U A_j^U + k_1^U k_2^U B_j^U \right] dt, \\ W_{00}^U &= wr_0, \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_{jt}^U = 0, \quad j=1,2,\dots,5. \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

To solve the above system of FBSDEs we impose a solution $(W_{jt}^U, \lambda_{jt}^U)$, $j=1,2,\dots,5$, of the form:

$$\lambda_{jt}^U = N_{jt}^U W_{jt}^U + M_{jt}^U, \quad j=1,2,\dots,5, \quad (47)$$

where N_{jt}^U and M_{jt}^U are processes to be determined. Taking differentials in (47) and using the forward equation of (46) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} d\lambda_{jt}^U &= W_{jt}^U dN_{jt}^U + N_{jt}^U dW_{jt}^U + dM_{jt}^U \\ &= W_{jt}^U dN_{jt}^U + dM_{jt}^U + \left\{ \left[B_j^U (N_{jt}^U)^2 - k_1^U B_j^U N_{jt}^U \right] W_{jt}^U + B_j^U N_{jt}^U M_{jt}^U + \left[W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U \right] N_{jt}^U \right\} dt, \end{aligned}$$

while from the backward equation of system (46) we get:

$$d\lambda_{jt}^U = \left\{ \left[(k_1^U B_j^U + r) N_{jt}^U - (k_1^U)^2 B_j^U \right] W_{jt}^U + (k_1^U B_j^U + r) M_{jt}^U - k_1^U A_j^U + k_1^U k_2^U B_j^U \right\} dt.$$

Sufficient conditions for the last two relationships to be equivalent are given by

$$dN_{jt}^U = \left[-B_j^U (N_{jt}^U)^2 + (2k_1^U B_j^U + r) N_{jt}^U - (k_1^U)^2 B_j^U \right] dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N_{jt}^U = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a backward Riccati equation (RE) that can be solved numerically for N_{jt}^U , $j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$,

and by

$$dM_{jt}^U = \left[(-B_j^U N_{jt}^U + k_1^U B_j^U + r) M_{jt}^U - (W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U) N_{jt}^U - k_1^U A_j^U + k_1^U k_2^U B_j^U \right] dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} M_{jt}^U = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which given the above solution is a backward linear first-order stochastic differential equation (SDE) that can be easily solved for M_{jt}^U , $j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$.

Substituting the linear solution form of (47) to the forward equation of the FBSDEs system (46), we obtain that

$$dW_{jt}^U = \left[(-k_1^U + N_{jt}^U) B_j^U W_{jt}^U + B_j^U M_{jt}^U + W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U \right] dt,$$

$$W_{00}^U = wr_0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a forward linear SDE that can be solved for W_{jt}^U , $j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$. Then the backward adjoint variable λ_{jt}^U , $j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, follows from (47) and the optimal water use w_{it}^U , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, follows from the optimality condition (44).

Non-Cooperative Approach: Downstream Case

For the (j, k) -th exit-stage the Hamiltonian of the optimization problem (14) is formulated by

$$H_{jk}^D(S_{jk}, w_{jkt}^D, \dots, w_{j5t}^D, \lambda_{jkt}^D) \triangleq \sum_{l=k}^5 \left[\frac{a_l^D}{b_l^D} w_{jlt}^D - \frac{1}{2b_l^D} \cdot (w_{jlt}^D)^2 \right] - (k_2^D - k_1^D S_{jkt}) \sum_{l=k}^5 w_{jlt}^D + \lambda_{jkt}^D \left[W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{it}^U - \sum_{l=k}^5 w_{jlt}^D + R_t - O_t \right], \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (48)$$

where λ_{jkt}^D is the (j, k) -th exit stage adjoint variable that represents water scarcity rents for the downstream area. Thanks to (48) the necessary conditions for optimality are given as follows:

$$\frac{\partial H_{jk}^D}{\partial w_{jlt}^D} = \frac{a_l^D}{b_l^D} - \frac{1}{b_l^D} \cdot w_{jlt}^D - (k_2^D - k_1^D S_{jkt}) - \lambda_{jkt}^D = 0, \quad l = k, \dots, 5, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (49)$$

$$d\lambda_{jkt}^D = \left[-\frac{\partial H_{jk}^D}{\partial S_{jkt}} + r\lambda_{jkt}^D \right] dt \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad d\lambda_{jkt}^D = \left[-k_1^D \sum_{l=k}^5 w_{jlt}^D + r\lambda_{jkt}^D \right] dt, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \quad (50)$$

From (49) we have the optimal water abstraction policy:

$$w_{jlt}^D = a_l^D - b_l^D (k_2^D - k_1^D S_{jkt}) - b_l^D \lambda_{jkt}^D, \quad l = k, \dots, 5, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \quad (51)$$

Then making use the notation of (45), we may reformulate the state equation (5) and the adjoint equation (50) to obtain the system of FBDEs:

$$\begin{aligned} dS_{jkt} &= \left[-k_1^D B_k^D S_{jkt} + B_k^D \lambda_{jkt}^D + W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{it}^U + R_t - O_t - A_k^D + k_2^D B_k^D \right] dt, \\ d\lambda_{jkt}^D &= \left[-\left(k_1^D\right)^2 B_k^D S_{jkt} + \left(k_1^D B_k^D + r\right) \lambda_{jkt}^D - k_1^D A_k^D + k_1^D k_2^D B_k^D \right] dt, \\ S_{000} &= s_0, \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_{jkt}^D = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

To solve the above system of FBDEs we impose a solution $(S_{jkt}, \lambda_{jkt}^D)$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, of the form:

$$\lambda_{jkt}^D = N_{jkt}^D S_{jkt} + M_{jkt}^D, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (53)$$

where N_{jkt}^D and M_{jkt}^D are functions to be determined. Taking differentials in (53) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} d\lambda_{jkt}^D &= S_{jkt} dN_{jkt}^D + N_{jkt}^D dS_{jkt} + dM_{jkt}^D \\ &= S_{jkt} dN_{jkt}^D + dM_{jkt}^D \\ &\quad + \left\{ \left[B_k^D \left(N_{jkt}^D\right)^2 - k_1^D B_k^D N_{jkt}^D \right] S_{jkt} + B_k^D N_{jkt}^D M_{jkt}^D + \left[W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{it}^U + R_t - O_t - A_k^D + k_2^D B_k^D \right] N_{jkt}^D \right\} dt, \end{aligned}$$

while the backward equation of the FBSDEs system (52) becomes:

$$d\lambda_{jkt}^D = \left\{ \left[\left(k_1^D B_k^D + r\right) N_{jkt}^D - \left(k_1^D\right)^2 B_k^D \right] S_{jkt} + \left(k_1^D B_k^D + r\right) M_{jkt}^D - k_1^D A_k^D + k_1^D k_2^D B_k^D \right\} dt.$$

The latter are equivalent under the following sufficient conditions:

$$dN_{jkt}^D = \left[-B_k^D \left(N_{jkt}^D\right)^2 + \left(2k_1^D B_k^D + r\right) N_{jkt}^D - \left(k_1^D\right)^2 B_k^D \right] dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N_{jkt}^D = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a backward RE that can be solved numerically for N_{jkt}^D , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, and

$$dM_{jkt}^D = \left[\begin{aligned} &\left(-B_k^D N_{jkt}^D + k_1^D B_k^D + r\right) M_{jkt}^D - \left(W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{it}^U + R_t - O_t - A_k^D + k_2^D B_k^D\right) N_{jkt}^D \\ &- k_1^D A_k^D + k_1^D k_2^D B_k^D \end{aligned} \right] dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} M_{jkt}^D = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which given the above solution is a backward linear first-order SDE that can be easily solved for M_{jkt}^D , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$.

Substituting the linear solution form of (53) to the forward equation of the FBSDEs system (52), we get that

$$dS_{jkt} = \left[\left(-k_1^D + N_{jkt}^D\right) S_{jkt} + B_k^D M_{jkt}^D + W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{it}^U + R_t - O_t - A_k^D + k_2^D B_k^D \right] dt,$$

$$S_{000} = s_0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a forward linear SDE that can be solved for $S_{jk\cdot}$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$. Thus, the backward adjoint variable $\lambda_{jk\cdot}^D$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, follows from the linear transformation of (53) and the optimal water use w_{il}^D , $i, l = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, follows from the optimality condition (51).

Cooperative Approach: Upstream Case

For the (j, k) -th exit stage the optimization problem (17) admits the augmented Hamiltonian:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{H}_{jk}^U(W_{jt}^U, S_{jkt}, \lambda_{jkt}^D, w_{jkt}^U, \dots, w_{5kt}^U, \mu_{jkt}, \nu_{jkt}, \xi_{jkt}) \triangleq & \sum_{i=j}^5 \left[\frac{a_i^U}{b_i^U} w_{ikt}^U - \frac{1}{2b_i^U} \cdot (w_{ikt}^U)^2 - (k_2^U - k_1^U W_{jt}^U) w_{ikt}^U \right] \\ & + \eta_1^U S_{jkt} + \eta_2^U + \mu_{jkt} \left[W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{ikt}^U \right] \\ & + \nu_{jkt} \left[W_t - \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{ikt}^U + R_t - O_t - A_k^D + B_k^D (k_2^D - k_1^D S_{jkt}) + B_k^D \lambda_{jkt}^D \right] \\ & + \xi_{jkt} \left\{ -k_1^D \left[A_k^D - B_k^D (k_2^D - k_1^D S_{jkt}) \right] + (r + k_1^D B_k^D) \lambda_{jkt}^D \right\}, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

where $(\mu_{jk\cdot}, \nu_{jk\cdot}, \xi_{jk\cdot})$ is the vector of the associated adjoint variables. Due to (54), the necessary optimality conditions are given below:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{H}_{jk}^U}{\partial w_{ikt}^U} = \frac{a_i^U}{b_i^U} - \frac{1}{b_i^U} \cdot w_{ikt}^U - (k_2^U - k_1^U W_{jt}^U) - \mu_{jkt} - \nu_{jkt} = 0, \quad i = j, \dots, 5, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (55)$$

$$d\mu_{jkt} = \left[-\frac{\partial \bar{H}_{jk}^U}{\partial W_{jt}^U} + r\mu_{jkt} \right] dt \Leftrightarrow d\mu_{jkt} = \left[-k_1^U \sum_{i=j}^5 w_{ikt}^U + r\mu_{jkt} \right] dt, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (56)$$

$$d\nu_{jkt} = \left[-\frac{\partial \bar{H}_{jk}^U}{\partial S_{jkt}} + r\nu_{jkt} \right] dt \Leftrightarrow d\nu_{jkt} = \left[-\eta_1^U + k_1^D B_k^D \nu_{jkt} + (k_1^D)^2 B_k^D \xi_{jkt} + r\nu_{jkt} \right] dt, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (57)$$

$$d\xi_{jkt} = \left[-\frac{\partial \bar{H}_{jk}^U}{\partial \lambda_{jkt}^D} + r\xi_{jkt} \right] dt \Leftrightarrow d\xi_{jkt} = \left[-B_k^D \nu_{jkt} - k_1^D B_k^D \xi_{jkt} \right] dt, \quad \xi_{000} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \quad (58)$$

From (55) we have that the optimal water consumption strategy is given by

$$w_{ikt}^U = a_i^U - b_i^U (k_2^U - k_1^U W_{jt}^U) - b_i^U \mu_{jkt} - b_i^U \nu_{jkt}, \quad i = j, \dots, 5, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \quad (59)$$

Then, recalling also the notation of (45), it is easily seen that the adjoint variables of both (57) and (58) satisfy the system of FBSDEs:

$$\begin{aligned} d\xi_{jkt} &= -\left[k_1^D B_k^D \xi_{jkt} + B_k^D \nu_{jkt} \right] dt, \\ d\nu_{jkt} &= \left[(k_1^D)^2 B_k^D \xi_{jkt} + (r + k_1^D B_k^D) \nu_{jkt} - \eta_1^U \right] dt, \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

$$\xi_{000} = 0, \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \nu_{jkt} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5.$$

In order to solve this FBSDEs system we are looking for solutions $(\xi_{jk\cdot}, \nu_{jk\cdot})$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, that satisfy the linear transformation:

$$\mathbf{v}_{jkt} = N_{jkt} \xi_{jkt} + M_{jkt}, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (61)$$

where N_{jkt} and M_{jkt} are stochastic processes to be determined. Taking differentials in (61) we get

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathbf{v}_{jkt} &= N_{jkt} d\xi_{jkt} + \xi_{jkt} dN_{jkt} + dM_{jkt} \\ &= \xi_{jkt} dN_{jkt} + dM_{jkt} - \left[\left(B_k^D N_{jkt}^2 + k_1^D B_k^D N_{jkt} \right) \xi_{jkt} + B_k^D N_{jkt} M_{jkt} \right] dt, \end{aligned}$$

while the backward equation of (60) may be written as

$$d\mathbf{v}_{jkt} = \left\{ \left[\left(r + k_1^D B_k^D \right) N_{jkt} + \left(k_1^D \right)^2 B_k^D \right] \xi_{jkt} + \left(r + k_1^D B_k^D \right) M_{jkt} - \eta_1^U \right\} dt.$$

Sufficient conditions for the latter to be equivalent are provided by

$$dN_{jkt} = \left[B_k^D N_{jkt}^2 + \left(2k_1^D B_k^D + r \right) N_{jkt} + \left(k_1^D \right)^2 B_k^D \right] dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N_{jkt} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a backward RE that can be solved numerically for N_{jkt}^D , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, and by

$$dM_{jkt} = \left[\left(B_k^D N_{jkt}^U + r + k_1^D B_k^D \right) M_{jkt} - \eta_1^U \right] dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} M_{jkt} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which given the above solution is a backward linear first-order SDE that can be easily solved for M_{jkt}^D , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$.

Substituting the linear solution form of (61) to the forward equation of the FBSDEs system (60), we obtain

$$d\xi_{jkt} = \left[-B_k^D \left(N_{jkt} + k_1^D \right) \xi_{jkt} - B_k^D M_{jkt} \right] dt,$$

$$\xi_{000} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a forward linear SDE that can be solved for ξ_{jkt} , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$. Then the backward adjoint variable \mathbf{v}_{jkt} , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, follows from the linear transformation of (61).

Given the obtained solution $(\xi_{jkt}, \mathbf{v}_{jkt})$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, of the FBSDEs system (60), as described above, we may put in use (45) and (59) to derive that the upstream area water resources state equation of (3) and the adjoint variable of (56) form the subsequent system of FBSDEs:

$$dW_{jt}^U = \left[-k_1^U B_j^U W_{jt}^U + B_j^U \mu_{jkt} + B_j^U \mathbf{v}_{jkt} + W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U \right] dt,$$

$$d\mu_{jkt} = \left[-\left(k_1^U \right)^2 B_j^U W_{jt}^U + \left(k_1^U B_j^U + r \right) \mu_{jkt} + k_1^U B_j^U \mathbf{v}_{jkt} - k_1^U A_j^U + k_1^U k_2^U B_j^U \right] dt, \quad (62)$$

$$W_{00}^U = wr_0, \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_{jkt} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5.$$

To find a solution process pair (W_{jt}^U, μ_{jkt}) , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, for this system of FBSDEs, we impose the linear transformation:

$$\mu_{jkt} = \Lambda_{jkt} W_{jt}^U + \Xi_{jkt}, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (63)$$

where Λ_{jkt} and Ξ_{jkt} are stochastic processes to be determined. Taking differentials in (63) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} d\mu_{jkt} &= \Lambda_{jkt} dW_{jt}^U + W_{jt}^U d\Lambda_{jkt} + d\Xi_{jkt} \\ &= W_{jt}^U d\Lambda_{jkt} + d\Xi_{jkt} \\ &\quad + \left\{ \left[B_j^U \Lambda_{jkt}^2 - k_1^U B_j^U \Lambda_{jkt} \right] W_{jt}^U + B_j^U \Lambda_{jkt} \Xi_{jkt} + B_j^U \nu_{jkt} \Lambda_{jkt} + \left[W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U \right] \Lambda_{jkt} \right\} dt, \end{aligned}$$

while the backward equation of (62) may be reformulated as

$$d\mu_{jkt} = \left\{ \left[-\left(k_1^U\right)^2 B_j^U + \left(k_1^U B_j^U + r\right) \Lambda_{jkt} \right] W_{jt}^U + \left(k_1^U B_j^U + r\right) \Xi_{jkt} + k_1^U B_j^U \nu_{jkt} - k_1^U A_j^U + k_1^U k_2^U B_j^U \right\} dt.$$

Sufficient conditions for the latter to be equivalent are given as follows:

$$d\Lambda_{jkt} = \left[-B_j^U \Lambda_{jkt}^2 + \left(2k_1^U B_j^U + r\right) \Lambda_{jkt} - \left(k_1^U\right)^2 B_j^U \right] dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \Lambda_{jkt} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a backward RE that can be solved numerically for Λ_{jkt} , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, and

$$d\Xi_{jkt} = \left\{ \left[-B_j^U \Lambda_{jkt} + \left(k_1^U B_j^U + r\right) \right] \Xi_{jkt} - B_j^U \nu_{jkt} \Lambda_{jkt} - \left[W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U \right] \Lambda_{jkt} \right. \\ \left. + k_1^U B_j^U \nu_{jkt} - k_1^U A_j^U + k_1^U k_2^U B_j^U \right\} dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \Xi_{jkt} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which given the above solution is a backward linear first-order SDE that can be easily solved for Ξ_{jkt} , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$.

Substituting the linear transformation of (63) to the forward equation of the FBSDEs system (62), we deduce that

$$dW_{jt}^U = \left\{ \left[-k_1^U B_j^U + B_j^U \Lambda_{jkt} \right] W_{jt}^U + B_j^U \Xi_{jkt} + B_j^U \nu_{jkt} + W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U \right\} dt,$$

$$W_{00}^U = w_0^U, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a forward linear SDE that can be solved for W_{jt}^U , $j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$. Then the backward adjoint variable μ_{jkt} , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$ follows readily from the linear transformation of (63).

Given now the solutions (ξ_{jk}, ν_{jk}) , (W_{jt}^U, μ_{jkt}) , $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, of the FBSDES systems (60) and (62), respectively, we may combine (45) and (59) to write equivalently the Hamiltonian FBSDEs state system of the downstream area as

$$\begin{aligned} dS_{jkt} &= \left[\begin{array}{l} -k_1^U B_j^U W_{jt}^U - k_1^D B_k^D S_{jkt} + B_k^D \lambda_{jkt}^D + B_j^U \mu_{jkt} + B_j^U \nu_{jkt} + W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U \\ + R_t - O_t - A_k^D + k_2^D B_k^D \end{array} \right] dt, \\ d\lambda_{jkt}^D &= \left[-\left(k_1^D\right)^2 B_k^D S_{jkt} + \left(r + k_1^D B_k^D\right) \lambda_{jkt}^D - k_1^D A_k^D + k_1^D k_2^D B_k^D - \eta_1^D \right] dt, \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

$$S_{000} = s_0, \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_{jkt}^D = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5.$$

Imposing once again a solution $(S_{jkt}, \lambda_{jkt}^U)$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, that satisfies the linear transformation:

$$\lambda_{jkt}^D = \Pi_{jkt} S_{jkt} + \Sigma_{jkt}, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5, \quad (65)$$

we will determine in what follows the stochastic processes $\Pi_{jk\cdot}$ and $\Sigma_{jk\cdot}$. Taking differentials in (65) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} d\lambda_{jkt}^D &= \Pi_{jkt} dS_{jkt} + S_{jkt} d\Pi_{jkt} + d\Sigma_{jkt} \\ &= S_{jkt} d\Pi_{jkt} + d\Sigma_{jkt} + \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left[B_k^D \Pi_{jkt}^2 - k_1^D B_k^D \Pi_{jkt} \right] S_{jkt} + B_k^D \Pi_{jkt} \Sigma_{jkt} - k_1^U B_j^U W_j^U \Pi_{jkt} \\ & + \left[B_j^U \mu_{jkt} + B_j^U \nu_{jkt} + W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U + R_t - O_t - A_k^D + k_2^D B_k^D \right] \Pi_{jkt} \end{aligned} \right\} dt, \end{aligned}$$

while the backward equation of (64) may be written equivalently as

$$d\lambda_{jkt}^D = \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left[-\left(k_1^D\right)^2 B_k^D + \left(r + k_1^D B_k^D\right) \Pi_{jkt} \right] S_{jkt} + \left(r + k_1^D B_k^D\right) \Sigma_{jkt} - k_1^D A_k^D + k_1^D k_2^D B_k^D \end{aligned} \right\} dt.$$

Sufficient conditions for the latter to be equivalent are provided by

$$d\Pi_{jkt} = \left[-B_k^D \left(\Pi_{jk}^U\right)^2 + \left(2k_1^D B_k^D + r\right) \Pi_{jkt}^U - \left(k_1^D\right)^2 B_k^D \right] dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \Pi_{jkt} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a backward RE that can be solved numerically for $\Pi_{jk\cdot}$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, and by

$$d\Sigma_{jkt} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left[-B_k^D \Pi_{jkt} + \left(k_1^D B_k^D + r\right) \right] \Sigma_{jkt} \\ & - \left[-k_1^U B_j^U W_j^U + B_j^U \mu_{jkt} + B_j^U \nu_{jkt} + W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U + R_t - O_t - A_k^D + k_2^D B_k^D \right] \Pi_{jkt} \\ & - k_1^D A_k^D + k_1^D k_2^D B_k^D \end{aligned} \right\} dt,$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \Sigma_{jkt} = 0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which given the above solution is a backward linear first-order SDE that can be easily solved for $\Sigma_{jk\cdot}$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$.

Substituting the linear transformation (65) to the forward equation of the FBSDEs system (64), we obtain

$$dS_{jkt} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} & B_k^D \left[\Pi_{jkt} - k_1^D \right] S_{jkt} + B_k^D \Sigma_{jkt} - k_1^U B_j^U W_j^U + B_j^U \mu_{jkt} + B_j^U \nu_{jkt} \\ & + W_t - A_j^U + k_2^U B_j^U + R_t - O_t - A_k^D + k_2^D B_k^D \end{aligned} \right\} dt,$$

$$S_{000} = s_0, \quad j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5,$$

which is a forward linear SDE that can be solved for $S_{jk\cdot}$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$. Then the backward adjoint variable $\lambda_{jk\cdot}^D$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, follows immediately from the linear transformation of (65). Clearly the optimal water abstraction policies $w_{jk\cdot}^U, w_{jk\cdot}^D$, $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, of the upstream and downstream areas follow from (59) and (51), respectively.

APPENDIX 3 – SEQUENTIAL MONTE CARLO

The particle filter methodology can be applied to state space models of the general form:

$$y_T \sim p(y_t | x_t), s_t \sim p(s_t | s_{t-1}), \quad (66)$$

where s_t is a state variable. For general introductions see *Gordon (1997)*, *Gordon et al. (1993)*, *Doucet et al. (2001)* and *Ristic et al. (2004)*.

Given the data Y_t the posterior distribution $p(s_t | Y_t)$ can be approximated by a set of (auxiliary) particles $\{s_t^{(i)}, i = 1, \dots, N\}$ with probability weights $\{w_t^{(i)}, i = 1, \dots, N\}$ where $\sum_{i=1}^N w_t^{(i)} = 1$. The predictive density can be approximated by:

$$p(s_{t+1} | Y_t) = \int p(s_{t+1} | s_t) p(s_t | Y_t) ds_t \approx \sum_{i=1}^N p(s_{t+1} | s_t^{(i)}) w_t^{(i)}, \quad (67)$$

and the final approximation for the filtering density is:

$$p(s_{t+1} | Y_t) \propto p(y_{t+1} | s_{t+1}) p(s_{t+1} | Y_t) \approx p(y_{t+1} | s_{t+1}) \sum_{i=1}^N p(s_{t+1} | s_t^{(i)}) w_t^{(i)}. \quad (68)$$

The basic mechanism of particle filtering rests on propagating $\{s_t^{(i)}, w_t^{(i)}, i = 1, \dots, N\}$ to the next step, viz. $\{s_{t+1}^{(i)}, w_{t+1}^{(i)}, i = 1, \dots, N\}$ but this often suffers from the weight degeneracy problem. If parameters $\theta \in \Theta \in \mathfrak{R}^k$ are available, as is often the case, we follow *Liu and West (2001)* parameter learning takes place via a mixture of multivariate normals:

$$p(\theta | Y_t) \approx \sum_{i=1}^N w_t^{(i)} N(\theta | a\theta_t^{(i)} + (1-a)\bar{\theta}_t, b^2 V_t), \quad (69)$$

where $\bar{\theta}_t = \sum_{i=1}^N w_t^{(i)} \theta_t^{(i)}$, and $V_t = \sum_{i=1}^N w_t^{(i)} (\theta_t^{(i)} - \bar{\theta}_t)(\theta_t^{(i)} - \bar{\theta}_t)'$. The constants a and b are related to shrinkage and are determined via a discount factor $\delta \in (0, 1)$ as $a = (1 - b^2)^{1/2}$ and $b^2 = 1 - [(3\delta - 1) / 2\delta]^2$. See also *Casarin and Marin (2007)*.

Andrieu and Roberts (2009), *Flury and Shephard (2011)* and *Pitt et al. (2012)* provide the Particle Metropolis-Hastings (PMCMC) technique which uses an unbiased estimator of the likelihood function $\hat{p}_N(Y | \theta)$ as $p(Y | \theta)$ is often not available in closed form.

Given the current state of the parameter $\theta^{(j)}$ and the current estimate of the likelihood, say $L^j = \hat{p}_N(Y | \theta^{(j)})$, a candidate θ^c is drawn from $q(\theta^c | \theta^{(j)})$ yielding $L^c = \hat{p}_N(Y | \theta^c)$. Then, we set $\theta^{(j+1)} = \theta^c$ with the Metropolis - Hastings probability:

$$A = \min \left\{ 1, \frac{p(\theta^c) L^c}{p(\theta^{(j)}) L^j} \frac{q(\theta^{(j)} | \theta^c)}{q(\theta^c | \theta^{(j)})} \right\}, \quad (70)$$

otherwise we repeat the current draws: $\{\theta^{(j+1)}, L^{j+1}\} = \{\theta^{(j)}, L^j\}$.

Hall, Pitt and Kohn (2014) propose an auxiliary particle filter which rests upon the idea that adaptive particle filtering (*Pitt et al., 2012*) used within PMCMC requires far fewer particles than the standard particle filtering algorithm to approximate $p(Y | \theta)$. From *Pitt and Shephard (1999)* we know that auxiliary particle filtering can be implemented easily once we can evaluate the state

transition density $p(s_t | s_{t-1})$. When this is not possible, *Hall et al.* (2014) present a new approach when, for instance, $s_t = g(s_{t-1}, u_t)$ for a certain disturbance. In this case we have:

$$p(y_t | s_{t-1}) = \int p(y_t | s_t) p(s_t | s_{t-1}) ds_t, \quad (71)$$

$$p(u_t | s_{t-1}; y_t) = p(y_t | s_{t-1}, u_t) p(u_t | s_{t-1}) / p(y_t | s_{t-1}). \quad (72)$$

If one can evaluate $p(y_t | s_{t-1})$ and simulate from $p(u_t | s_{t-1}; y_t)$ the filter would be fully adaptable (*Pitt and Shephard*, 1999). One can use a Gaussian approximation for the first-stage proposal $g(y_t | s_{t-1})$ by matching the first two moments of $p(y_t | s_{t-1})$. So, in some way we find that the approximating density $p(y_t | s_{t-1}) = N(E(y_t | s_{t-1}), V(y_t | s_{t-1}))$. In the second stage, we know that $p(u_t | y_t, s_{t-1}) \propto p(y_t | s_{t-1}, u_t) p(u_t)$. For $p(u_t | y_t, s_{t-1})$ we know it is multimodal so suppose it has M modes are \hat{u}_t^m , for $m = 1, \dots, M$. For each mode we can use a Laplace approximation. Let $l(u_t) = \log[p(y_t | s_{t-1}, u_t) p(u_t)]$. From the Laplace approximation we obtain:

$$l(u_t) \approx l(\hat{u}_t^m) + \frac{1}{2} (u_t - \hat{u}_t^m)' \nabla^2 l(\hat{u}_t^m) (u_t - \hat{u}_t^m). \quad (73)$$

Then we can construct a mixture approximation:

$$g(u_t | x_t, s_{t-1}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \lambda_m (2\pi)^{-d/2} |\Sigma_m|^{-1/2} \exp\left\{\frac{1}{2} (u_t - \hat{u}_t^m)' \Sigma_m^{-1} (u_t - \hat{u}_t^m)\right\}, \quad (74)$$

where $\Sigma_m = -[\nabla^2 l(\hat{u}_t^m)]^{-1}$ and $\lambda_m \propto \exp\{l(u_t^m)\}$ with $\sum_{m=1}^M \lambda_m = 1$. This is done for each particle s_t^i . This is known as the Auxiliary Disturbance Particle Filter (ADPF).

An alternative is the independent particle filter (IPF) of *Lin et al.* (2005). The IPF forms a proposal for s_t directly from the measurement density $p(y_t | s_t)$ although *Hall et al.* (2014) are quite right in pointing out that the state equation can be very informative.

In the standard particle filter of *Gordon et al.* (1993) particles are simulated through the state density $p(s_t^i | s_{t-1}^i)$ and they are re-sampled with weights determined by the measurement density evaluated at the resulting particle, viz. $p(y_t | s_t^i)$.

The ADPF is simple to construct and rests upon the following steps:

For $t = 0, \dots, T-1$ given samples $s_t^k \sim p(s_t | Y_{1:t})$ with mass π_t^k for $k = 1, \dots, N$.

1) For $k = 1, \dots, N$ compute $\omega_{t|t+1}^k = g(y_{t+1} | s_t^k) \pi_t^k$, $\pi_{t|t+1}^k = \omega_{t|t+1}^k / \sum_{i=1}^N \omega_{t|t+1}^i$.

2) For $k = 1, \dots, N$ draw $\tilde{s}_t^k \sim \sum_{i=1}^N \pi_{t|t+1}^i \delta_{s_t^i}(ds_t)$.

3) For $k = 1, \dots, N$ draw $u_{t+1}^k \sim g(u_{t+1} | \tilde{s}_t^k, y_{t+1})$ and set $s_{t+1}^k = h(s_t^k; u_{t+1}^k)$.

4) For $k = 1, \dots, N$ compute

$$\omega_{t+1}^k = \frac{p(y_{t+1} | s_{t+1}^k) p(u_{t+1}^k)}{g(y_{t+1} | s_t^k) g(u_{t+1}^k | \tilde{s}_t^k, y_{t+1})}, \quad \pi_{t+1}^k = \frac{\omega_{t+1}^k}{\sum_{i=1}^N \omega_{t+1}^i}. \quad (75)$$

It should be mentioned that the estimate of likelihood from ADPF is:

$$p(Y_{1:T}) = \prod_{t=1}^T \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \omega_{t-1}^i \right) \left(N^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N \omega_t^i \right). \quad (76)$$

Particle Metropolis Adjusted Langevin Filters

Nemeth et al. (2014) provide a particle version of a Metropolis Adjusted Langevin algorithm (MALA). In Sequential Monte Carlo we are interested in approximating $p(s_t | Y_{1:t}, \theta)$. Given that:

$$p(s_t | Y_{1:t}, \theta) \propto g(y_t | x_t, \theta) \int f(s_t | s_{t-1}, \theta) p(s_{t-1} | y_{1:t-1}, \theta) ds_{t-1}, \quad (77)$$

where $p(s_{t-1} | y_{1:t-1}, \theta)$ is the posterior as of time $t-1$. If at time $t-1$ we have a set of particles $\{s_{t-1}^i, i=1, \dots, N\}$ and weights $\{w_{t-1}^i, i=1, \dots, N\}$ which form a discrete approximation for $p(s_{t-1} | y_{1:t-1}, \theta)$ then we have the approximation:

$$\hat{p}(s_{t-1} | y_{1:t-1}, \theta) \propto \sum_{i=1}^N w_{t-1}^i f(s_t | s_{t-1}^i, \theta). \quad (78)$$

See Andrieu et al. (2010) and Cappe et al. (2005) for reviews. From (78) Fernhead (2007) makes the important observation that the joint probability of sampling particle s_{t-1}^i and state s_t is:

$$\omega_t = \frac{w_{t-1}^i g(y_t | s_t, \theta) f(s_t | s_{t-1}^i, \theta)}{\xi_t^i q(s_t | s_{t-1}^i, y_t, \theta)}, \quad (79)$$

where $q(s_t | s_{t-1}^i, y_t, \theta)$ is a density function amenable to simulation and

$$\xi_t^i q(s_t | s_{t-1}^i, y_t, \theta) \simeq c g(y_t | s_t, \theta) f(s_t | s_{t-1}^i, \theta), \quad (80)$$

and c is the normalizing constant in (77).

In the MALA algorithm of Roberts and Rosenthal (1998)² we form a proposal:

$$\theta^c = \theta^{(s)} + \lambda z + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \nabla \log p(\theta^{(s)} | Y_{1:T}), \quad (81)$$

where $z \sim N(0, I)$ which should result in larger jumps and better mixing properties, plus lower autocorrelations for a certain scale parameter λ . Acceptance probabilities are:

$$a(\theta^c | \theta^{(s)}) = \min \left\{ 1, \frac{p(Y_{1:T} | \theta^c) q(\theta^{(s)} | \theta^c)}{p(Y_{1:T} | \theta^{(s)}) q(\theta^c | \theta^{(s)})} \right\}. \quad (82)$$

Using particle filtering it is possible to create an approximation of the score vector using Fisher's identity:

$$\nabla \log p(Y_{1:T} | \theta) = E \left[\nabla \log p(s_{1:T}, Y_{1:T} | \theta) | Y_{1:T}, \theta \right], \quad (83)$$

²The benefit of MALA over Random-Walk-Metropolis arises when the number of parameters n is large. This happens because the scaling parameter λ is $O(n^{-1/2})$ for Random-Walk-Metropolis but it is $O(n^{-1/6})$ for MALA, see Roberts et al. (1997) and Roberts and Rosenthal (1998)

which corresponds to the expectation of:

$$\nabla \log p(s_{1:T}, Y_{1:T} | \theta) = \nabla \log p(s_{1:T-1}, Y_{1:T-1} | \theta) + \nabla \log g(y_T | s_T, \theta) + \nabla \log f(s_T | s_{1:T-1}, \theta),$$

over the path $s_{1:T}$. The particle approximation to the score vector results from replacing $p(s_{1:T} | Y_{1:T}, \theta)$ with a particle approximation $\hat{p}(s_{1:T} | Y_{1:T}, \theta)$. With particle i at time $t-1$ we can associate a value $\alpha_{t-1}^i = \nabla \log p(s_{1:t-1}^i, Y_{1:t-1} | \theta)$, which can be updated recursively. As we sample κ_i in the APF (the index of particle at time $t-1$ that is propagated to produce the i -th particle at time t) we have the update:

$$\alpha_t^i = \alpha_{t-1}^{\kappa_i} + \nabla \log g(y_t | s_t^i, \theta) + \nabla \log f(s_t^i | s_{1:t-1}^i, \theta). \quad (84)$$

To avoid problems with increasing variance of the score estimate $\nabla \log p(Y_{1:t} | \theta)$ we can use the approximation:

$$\alpha_{t-1}^i \sim N(m_{t-1}^i, V_{t-1}). \quad (85)$$

The mean is obtained by shrinking α_{t-1}^i towards the mean of α_{t-1} as follows:

$$m_{t-1}^i = \delta \alpha_{t-1}^i + (1-\delta) \sum_{i=1}^N w_{t-1}^i \alpha_{t-1}^i, \quad (86)$$

where $\delta \in (0, 1)$ is a shrinkage parameter. Using Rao-Blackwellization one can avoid sampling α_t^i and instead use the following recursion for the means:

$$m_t^i = \delta m_{t-1}^{\kappa_i} + (1-\delta) \sum_{i=1}^N w_{t-1}^i m_{t-1}^i + \nabla \log g(y_t | s_t^i, \theta) + \nabla \log f(s_t^i | s_{1:t-1}^{\kappa_i}, \theta), \quad (87)$$

which yields the final score estimate:

$$\nabla \log \hat{p}(Y_{1:t} | \theta) = \sum_{i=1}^N w_t^i m_t^i. \quad (88)$$

As a rule of thumb *Nemeth et al.* (2014) suggest taking $\delta = 0.95$. Furthermore, they show the important result that the algorithm should be tuned to the asymptotically optimal acceptance rate of 15.47% and the number of particles must be selected so that the variance of the estimated log-posterior is about 3. Additionally, if measures are not taken to control the error in the variance of the score vector, there is no gain over a simple random walk proposal.

Of course, the marginal likelihood is:

$$p(Y_{1:T} | \theta) = p(y_1 | \theta) \prod_{t=2}^T p(y_t | Y_{1:t-1}, \theta), \quad (89)$$

where

$$p(y_t | Y_{1:t-1}, \theta) = \int g(y_t | s_t) \int f(s_t | s_{t-1}, \theta) p(s_{t-1} | Y_{1:t-1}, \theta) ds_{t-1} ds_t, \quad (90)$$

provides, in explicit form, the predictive likelihood.

